

**GLOBAL RESEARCH
AGENDA**
for
SERVICE-LEARNING
and
COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

*International Association for Research
on Service-Learning and Community Engagement*

Andrew Furco
Rochelle Smarr
Stacey Muse
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All publications, presentations, reports, or other scholarly products that draw on data from the *Global Research Agenda for Service-Learning and Community Engagement* should include the following acknowledgement:

This work draws on data from the Global Research Agenda for Service-Learning and Community Engagement, a participatory, multi-year initiative led by the International Association for Research on Service-Learning and Community Engagement (IARSLCE). The Global Research Agenda was developed through 29 data input forums and regional analysis meetings involving nearly 700 scholars, practitioners, and community partners from 44 countries. We acknowledge and honor the collective contributions of all participants whose insights and expertise shaped this global research framework.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

FOREWORD	i
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	iii
INTRODUCTION	1
AT A GLANCE	13
NUMBER OF DATA INPUT FORUMS HELD = 29	13
REGIONAL DISTRIBUTION OF FORUM PARTICIPANTS.....	14
HOME COUNTRIES OF DATA INPUT FORUM PARTICIPANTS.....	14
TOTAL NUMBER OF RESEARCH QUESTIONS/ISSUES FROM DATA INPUT FORUMS BY REGION.....	15
DISTRIBUTION OF FORUM DATA BY RESEARCH SECTION AND REGION.....	15
REGIONAL DATA ANALYSIS MEETINGS	16
GLOBAL MAP OF HOME COUNTRIES — ALL CONTRIBUTORS (<i>FORUM PARTICIPANTS AND DATA ANALYSTS</i>).....	17
NUMBER OF THEMES AND (RESEARCH QUESTIONS/ISSUES) PER RESEARCH DIMENSION BY REGION.....	18
REGIONALRESEARCH AGENDAS	19
AFRICA REGION.....	20
ASIA REGION.....	44
AUSTRALIA REGION	79
EUROPE REGION	111
NORTH AMERICA REGION.....	139
REGIÓN AMÉRICA LATINA/ AMÉRICA DEL SUR (<i>VERSIÓN EN ESPAÑOL</i>)	187
SOUTH AMERICA/LATIN AMERICA REGION (<i>ENGLISH VERSION</i>)	231

FOREWORD

A MESSAGE FROM THE IARSLCE BOARD CHAIR

Dear IARSLCE Members,

As a practitioner-scholar whose service to the International Association for Research on Service Learning and Community Engagement (IARSLCE) began during the inception of the Global Research Agenda on Service-Learning and Community Engagement (GRA), it is both humbling and deeply meaningful to offer this foreword. I have had the privilege of witnessing this project take shape across many roles—first as a Board Member, then as Conference Chair, Vice Chair, and now as Chair of the Board during the Association’s 25th anniversary year. To see a multi-faceted research project be born out of inclusivity, stewarded with love, and finalized through deep commitment to advancing the field—it has truly been a dream realized.

The *Global Research Agenda (GRA) on Service-Learning and Community Engagement* began in 2019, when the IARSLCE Board approved (and continues to affirm) a bold and timely initiative: to deepen international engagement, decentralize SLCE scholarship from the Global North, and listen to the broader global community of scholars, practitioners, researchers, and community members about what research matters most to them. The process was designed to be participatory from the beginning, with a focus on gathering perspectives about how SLCE is interpreted, practiced, and researched across diverse contexts.

Throughout the data collection and analysis phases of this multi-year initiative, we received thoughtful and important feedback from participants regarding the title and framing of the “Global Research Agenda.” Specifically, many raised concerns that the term *agenda* can carry problematic implications. For some, the term suggested that the direction of the field had already been defined by the Global North, and that regional voices were simply being invited to comment, rather than co-create.

This critique challenged us to reflect and respond. If this initiative is to truly represent our global community, it must reflect collective ownership—not just in its content, but also in its name and intent. What emerged is not an “agenda” in the traditional sense, but a living framework: one grounded in our mission to promote the development and dissemination of SLCE across all educational systems, globally.

For the purposes of this report, IARSLCE defines the term *agenda* as a strategic framework that activates our mission: *to promote the development and dissemination of research on service learning and community engagement (SLCE) internationally and across all levels of the education system.* In this context, the *Global Research Agenda (GRA) on Service-Learning and Community Engagement* serves not only as a reflection of our mission and vision, but also as a renewed call to action—engaging our membership in scholarship that is grounded in regional priorities while contributing to a shared global dialogue. Unlike traditional organizational

reports, the regional “agendas” presented here are not meant to be prescriptive or final. Instead, they are open invitations—for members to explore the research questions raised, develop responsive research designs, collaborate across borders, and bring that work back into the IARSLCE community. Whether through conference presentations, published papers, or new partnerships, we hope members will use the GRA as a launching point for inquiry, innovation, and connection.

The six regional agendas, along with the global agenda compiled in this document, are not fixed endpoints. They offer starting points: shared themes, emergent questions, and pressing priorities meant to spark inquiry, innovation, and collaboration. Rather than prescribing a single path, this framework outlines multiple, interconnected routes—rooted in local contexts, yet responsive to global challenges.

We invite IARSLCE members and partners to use GRA to design responsive research, form cross-regional collaborations, and bring this work into practice—through conferences, publications, proposals, and community action. Whether cited, adapted, or reimagined, GRA is meant to be a tool for ongoing, member-driven knowledge production and connection.

On behalf of former and current IARSLCE Board of Directors (2019 to 2025), I extend our deepest appreciation to IARSLCE co-founder, **Dr. Andrew “Andy” Furco**, whose vision, tireless dedication, and extraordinary leadership made this Agenda possible. From countless miles traveled to thousands of hours spent facilitating, listening, coding, and analyzing, his stewardship has been nothing short of transformational—both for IARSLCE, and for the wider service-learning and community engagement field. Truly thank you for your vision of IARSLCE back in 2001 and your continued commitment to IARSLCE and the field through this initiative. Thank you!

I am thrilled to celebrate the release of the *Global Research Agenda (GRA) on Service-Learning and Community Engagement* during IARSLCE’s 25th anniversary gathering in Durban, South Africa. It is especially meaningful to launch this framework in the presence of nearly 250 members from around the world—what a moment to mark together!

In solidarity,

Rochelle Smarr, Ed.D.

- Chair 2025, Board of Directors
 - International Association for Research on Service-Learning and Community Engagement (IARSLCE) (*ey-er-slice*)
- Director of Experiential Learning
 - Teaching and Learning Commons, University of California, San Diego

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The development and production of this Global Research Agenda for Service-Learning and Community Engagement would not have been possible without the contributions and involvement of many individuals, organizations, networks, and associations who enthusiastically stepped up to lend their participation and support to this field-building initiative.

We wish to thank all of individuals who served as facilitators of the data input forums and the regional data analysis meetings. Your work helped capture the full and rich array of research questions and key themes that have become the research agenda. Thank you Lentson Amos, David Barrientos, Fiora Biagi, Glenn Bowen, Lavinia Bracci, Stephen Chan, Betsabé Cuevas, Irene Culcasi, Paulo Duran, Matias Flores, Andrew Furco, Alžbeta Brozmanová Gregorová, Susan Corban Harris, Alejandra Herrero, Jason Ho, Alberto Infante, Hui Yu (Cindy) Lam, Lisa Lam, Atsuko Kuronuma, Leticia Lopez, Darren Lortan, Star Plaxton Moore, Carol Hok Ka Ma, Moses Mugambi, Amy Meuers, Agnieszka Nance, Katrina Norvell, Nicholas Oi, Hector Opazo, Francisco Pacheco, Carlos Palmas, Drew Pearl, Judith Pete, Matthew Pink, Chris Ponce, Rachayita Shah, Nascira Ramia, Pam Siebert, Kaat Somers, Maria Rosa Tapia, Sharon Valarmathi, Nicole Webster, and Hironori Yamaguchi.

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Most of all, we are immensely grateful to all the service-learning and community engagement scholars, practitioners, and partners who volunteered their time to share their perspectives through the data input forms and the regional data analysis meetings. Thank you for providing our field with a robust set of research themes and questions on which we can reflect and build future research endeavors to advance service-learning and community engagement across the globe in the years to come.

INTRODUCTION

AN AGENDA FOR THE FUTURE

The International Association for Research on Service-Learning and Community Engagement (IARSLCE) is the premier international professional association focused on advancing research on service-learning and community engagement (SLCE) across the educational spectrum. IARSLCE was established to bring to light the latest research in the field through international convenings of SLCE scholars and practitioners who engage in peer-exchange and network building. IARSLCE promotes the cultivation and presentation high quality trans-disciplinary research across a wide range of SLCE approaches and forms and builds the capacity of scholars, practitioners, and community partners to engage in such research.

As the study and practice of SLCE have increased exponentially across the globe in recent years, IARSLCE has set in motion several field-building initiatives designed to give greater visibility to the emergent forms and innovative approaches to SLCE research across cultural contexts and to expand networking opportunities for members of the SLCE community.

As part of this field-building effort, the IARSLCE board of directors approved in January 2019 an action plan focused on developing and producing a forward-looking, broad-based, global research agenda for service-learning and community engagement. The primary goal of the global agenda is to engage members of SLCE community in identifying the key research questions and issues that future research studies should investigate to advance SLCE over the next 20 years.

A PARTICIPATORY APPROACH

The global research agenda initiative is designed to help ensure that the future research in the field reflects the diverse and evolving interests and perspectives of scholars, practitioners, collaborators, and supporters of SLCE from across the globe. To achieve this goal, the process for developing the agenda is purposely internationally-focused and it is driven by a participatory process that incorporates input from members from the SLCE community situated in various national, cultural, and disciplinary settings and contexts.

The research agenda development process is designed to elicit from participants ideas and perspectives on the research questions and issues that future SLCE studies should incorporate. The process is structured to encourage participants to consider ways to broaden the methodologies, epistemologies, and standards used in SLCE research to align with new and emerging forms of SLCE study and practice. In addition, in fulfillment of IARSLCE's mission, contributors to the research agenda are asked to attend to research questions and issues focused on advancing SLCE across the educational spectrum (primary, secondary, and higher education).

DATA INPUT FORUMS

The research agenda presented in this document was developed by engaging SLCE colleagues from across the globe in a set of *data input forums*. Soon after announcing its effort to build a

global research agenda in early 2019, IARSLCE invited organizations, associations, and networks (formal and informal) to host one or more data input forums with their members and/or affiliates. Hosting a forum involved providing a space where members of the SLCE community could gather to engage in a facilitated data input process designed to capture participants' thoughts and perspectives on future research questions and issues.

Held in different geographical regions and cultural settings, the forums offered a mechanism for members of the SLCE community to convene and engage in facilitated reflections on the future of SLCE research. The facilitators of these forums were guided by a reflection tool designed to elicit from participants perspectives on different dimensions of SLCE research (e.g., impact, implementation, institutionalization, and methodological considerations, etc.). The reflection tool helped ensure that as the forums were held in different settings, in different parts of the globe, and in the different languages, they would have a similar structure and follow a similar process.

Structure of the Forums

All of the data input forums were open access; that is, anyone who wished to participate in a forum was welcome to do so. The structure of the forum and data input process for gathering participants' perspectives involved the following steps:

- The facilitator(s) began by providing background information about IARSLCE and the intended purposes, goals, and scope of the research agenda (i.e., it is global in focus, focuses on new and emerging SLCE paradigms, speaks to SLCE across the education spectrum, etc.).
- The facilitator(s) then explained that participants would be asked to reflect on a set of prompts. Each prompt asked participants to identify research questions and issues they believe future research studies should pursue in regard to a particular research dimension (e.g., research questions pertaining to SLCE's *impact*, or questions pertaining to SLCE *implementation*, SLCE *institutionalization*, etc.) (See Table 1).
- Participants were shown the first reflection prompt, which asked participants to identify research questions they would like to see on the research agenda regarding the *impact* of SLCE on students, faculty, institutions, and community. The participants individually reflected and wrote down their research questions on a set of sticky notes/post-its (or via virtual postings option during virtual meetings). Participants were instructed to post one question per sticky note. For example, if an individual's reflection produced five research questions/issues, they would complete five sticky notes.
- Following their individual reflections on this first prompt (focused on questions pertaining to SLCE impact), participants then shared their reflections and research questions with the participants at their table.
- The facilitator(s) then collected the sticky-notes containing participants' research questions for the first prompt (impact) and posted them on the wall.

- The facilitator(s) then moved to the next reflection prompt (questions about SLCE implementation) and repeated the previous process.
- The process was repeated again until participants had an opportunity to reflect on the prompts in the reflection tool and all of their questions were collected for posting.

At each forum meeting, participants were invited to submit their names and institutional affiliation if they wished to be acknowledged in the final report as contributors of the research agenda.

Photos from Various Data Input Forums

Table 1. Data Collection Forums: Research Dimensions and Corresponding Reflection Prompts

RESEARCH DIMENSION	REFLECTION PROMPT
I. Impact	Impact studies focus on assessing the impacts of service-learning and community engagement on participants, including students, faculty, staff, institutions and the community . They cross a broad range of short-term and long-term outcomes. The research agenda should identify questions that explore the impact of service-learning and community engagement across all participants and stakeholders. The questions should be nuanced, and the impacts on specific participant populations should be considered.
II. Implementation	Implementation studies focus on examining the practices of service-learning and community engagement and the ways in which these practices are effective in achieving particular goals. Implementation studies seek to improve practice and provide guidance on best practices across a broad range of service-learning and community engagement programmatic approaches. The research agenda should identify questions that center on the process of delivering service-learning and community engagement across a broad range of community, cultural, geographic, disciplinary, and institutional contexts.
III. Institutionalization	Institutionalization studies focus on examining the factors that promote the sustainability and institutionalization of service-learning and community engagement across institutional and community contexts. Studies in this area seek to conceptualize the idea of institutionalization in light of the changing contexts of educational institutions and the varied approaches to service-learning and community engagement.
IV. COVID/ Post-COVID	Questions and issues that explore service-learning and community engagement practices during and beyond COVID. The issues might include, but are not limited to: new emerging practices for service-learning and community engagement results from the pandemic; changes regarding the conduct of service-learning and community engagement research due to COVID; impact of COVID on the quality of service-learning and community engagement; and advantages and disadvantages of conducting service-learning and community engagement during or after COVID
V. Equity and Social Advancement	Issues that explore the role of equity in service-learning and community engagement practices within and across cultures, populations, and regions. The issues might include, but are not limited to, implications for conducting equity-focused research within and across different groups, populations, communities, and/or cultures.
VI. Cultural/Regional and Cross- Cultural/ Cross Regional	Issues that explore service-learning and community engagement practices within and across cultures and regions are to be embraced and discussed, with an eye toward identifying questions or action steps for the research agenda. The issues might include, but are not limited to: conducting research within and across different cultural or geographic settings; examining service-learning and community engagement across the educational spectrum; community voice; multiple frames of service-learning and community engagement.
VII. Conceptual Framings/ Theory Development	The field of service-learning and community engagement has been criticized for being under-theorized and for lacking well-developed and well-tested conceptual frameworks. Studies in this area of work focus on theory testing and building conceptual models and frameworks that explain various phenomena in the study and practice of service-learning and community engagement.
VIII. Methodological Considerations	The field of service-learning and community engagement has been criticized for being under-theorized and for lacking well-developed and well-tested conceptual frameworks. Studies in this area of work focus on theory testing and building conceptual models and frameworks that explain various phenomena in the study and practice of service-learning and community engagement.
IX. Instruments and Measures	Over the years, there has been much debate over the kinds of methods that are appropriate for the study of service-learning and community engagement. A broad range of research designs, methods, and approaches are needed in order to gain a full understanding of the nature of the field. A broad range of epistemologies are required in designing and operationalizing today's research on service-learning and community engagement.
X. Replication	No one study provides all the evidence, understanding, or knowledge that is needed to draw firm conclusions about service-learning or community engagement. Replication is a critical feature of scientific inquiry and research. Only a handful of service-learning and community engagement studies have been replicated. Replicating high quality studies is a way to strengthen evidence and secure more conclusive findings about the strengths and limitations of service-learning and community engagement practices, outcomes, and approaches.

PREPARING FOR THE 20TH ANNIVERSARY CONFERENCE

The original plan for the research agenda initiative was to hold as many data input forums as possible over an 15-month period between February 2019 and May 2020. Once the forums were completed and participants' perspectives were captured, IARSLCE would then put out a call to members of the SLCE community to engage in a three-day meeting (June/July 2020) to systematically analyze the collected data.

The data analysis process would involve organizing and categorizing the full suite of collected data, with the goals of identifying the key themes that emerged, prioritizing and selecting the research questions to be highlighted in the global research agenda, and finalizing the global research agenda. The agenda would be published and unveiled in October 2020 as a feature of the 20th anniversary of IARSLCE's annual research conference, to be held in city of Minneapolis in the United States.

This 20th anniversary conference was seen as a perfect moment to present the global research agenda, given that this milestone gathering served as both a real and symbolic opportunity to reflect on the changing landscape of the SLCE field and to think about the future of SLCE research. The SLCE field had matured substantially over the 19 years that had passed since the first offering of the annual research conference in Berkeley, California in October 2001. The emergence of new forms and innovative approaches to SLCE, as well as increased global interest in SLCE programming in more regions and educational sectors, had resulted in greater interest in SLCE research situated in particular cultural, regional, and linguistic contexts. While the 20th anniversary conference provided an opportunity to celebrate the growth and maturity of the SLCE field and the important field-building role that research has played, the presentation of the global research agenda would provide a means to shift the focus to the future and what the next twenty years of SLCE research might entail.

The first data input forum was held March 21, 2019 in Hong Kong, hosted by the Hong Kong Polytechnic University. By the end of 2019, nine forums had been held in Asia, South/Latin America, Europe and North America, with preparations underway for five additional data input forums to be held in Europe, Africa, and Australia during the first half of 2020.

THE IMPACT OF COVID-19

With the arrival of the global COVID pandemic in late 2019, opportunities to host data input forums diminished as associations, networks, and professional groups canceled or postponed their meetings. This raised questions about the fate of the research agenda and how to ensure that the agenda, if it was to be completed, would capture enough of the field's diverse voices. In addition, the 20th Anniversary conference scheduled for October 2020 was canceled when it became evident that pandemic would be lasting longer than initially assumed.

There was strong agreement that it would be unwise to simply shelve the research agenda. The nine data input forums held during 2019 had garnered rich and robust data and several organizations had already signed on to contribute to the research agenda and host data input forums when it would be safe again to hold convenings. In response, IARSLCE extended the

timeline for producing the research agenda, establishing the goal of continuing with the data input forums until an appropriate time and venue for presenting the research agenda to the SLCE field could be secured post-pandemic.

As meetings switched from in-person convenings to online gatherings during the pandemic, the data input forums shifted to a virtual modality. These virtual offerings, which continued through 2021, provided great opportunities to reach and engage additional members of the global SLCE community in shaping the research agenda.

The COVID pandemic had a profound effect not only on the ability to convene in-person, but also on the operationalization and advancement of service-learning and community engagement. Major programmatic changes were underway. SLCE projects were moving to remote offerings and some SLCE programs were simply put on hold. Concurrently, various countries and societies were facing a broad range of political and social challenges, such as the war in Ukraine, the killing of George Floyd in the United States, and major weather disasters, such as the floods in Australia and Pakistan, the major earthquakes in Afghanistan and Indonesia, and the devastating droughts and heatwaves in China and Europe. These and other such major societal challenges shifted the ways SLCE was practiced and supported.

It was clear that SLCE was developing in new and different ways, and that IARSLCE's future-focused research agenda would need to capture and reflect the essence of this evolving SLCE global landscape.

THE FORUMS CONTINUE

Between January 2021 and December 2022, five virtual data input forums were held. Based on the same process and structure as the in-person forums, these forums focused on capturing the key issues and research questions undergirding the changing global SLCE landscape. With international virtual meetings becoming more common, a priority of these forums was to find opportunities to engage participants from diverse backgrounds and regions who were engaged with different and emerging approaches to service-learning and community engagement. New prompts focusing on soliciting participants' reflections on issues and questions pertaining to conducting SLCE work during and after COVID, as well their perspectives on equity and social advancement aspects of SLCE, were now included in the Forums. While there was an eagerness to finalize and produce the research agenda and share the findings of the already collected data, IARSLCE was committed to more fully capturing the cultural and regional nuances inherent in SLCE work in light of the prevailing social, political, and economic challenges that were shaping the field.

As the COVID pandemic waned in early 2023, IARSLCE set its eyes on the 25th Anniversary research conference, another milestone set to take place in 2025, now just two years away. This next anniversary milestone provided another real and symbolic opportunity to consider the future of the field and present a future-focused global research agenda for service-learning and community engagement. The Executive Board approved a plan to continue to conduct data input forums through 2023, complete a systematic analysis of the data by the end of 2024, and produce a global research agenda to be presented at the 25th Anniversary conference some time in 2025.

During 2023, 10 input forums were held via in-person, virtual, and hybrid convenings, engaging SLCE colleagues in Europe, Asia, Africa, North America, and South/Latin America. While the data collection forums officially ended in December 2023, several groups reached out to IARSLCE in early 2025 eager to contribute to the research agenda and interested in offering a forum. In turn, four additional data input forums were held in South Africa, Australia, Kenya, and the United States during the first half of 2025, bringing the total number of data input forums to 29 (see *At a Glance*). Collectively, these 29 Forum engaged 695 participants from 44 countries who submitted 6,759 research questions and issues for the research agenda.

REGIONAL CONTEXTS

With more than 6,500 submitted research questions/items to consider, there needed to be a systematic approach to organizing and analyzing this large amount data. An analysis protocol was developed that provided a step-by-step process to guide the data analysts as they categorized the various research questions into themes, prioritized the resulting themes, and then decided on which research questions/items in each of the ten research dimensions to select for inclusion in the research agenda.

Throughout the various data input forum meetings, it had become evident that regional and cultural contexts greatly influenced the kinds of research questions forum participants submitted. Indeed, many of the submitted research questions and items reflected particular social, cultural, political, and economic conditions that members of the SLCE community were facing in their local context. Therefore, the original data analysis plan—to convene a group of SLCE practitioners, scholars, and researchers from across the globe for a three-day meeting to analyze the full set of data and then produce the global research agenda—likely would not adequately capture the various regional nuances in the research questions and themes.

In light of this situation, the decision was made to switch the data analysis plan from a three-day global meeting to a set of data analysis meetings to be held regionally (one analysis meeting per continent). Following the established data analysis protocol, each of these regional data analysis meetings convened SLCE practitioners, scholars, and researchers from the region to analyze the data from the forums that were held in that region. Each meeting resulted in the production of a *regional* research agenda for service-learning and community engagement. The completed regional agendas were then compiled to form this *Global Research Agenda for Service-Learning and Community Engagement*.

REGIONAL DATA ANALYSIS MEETINGS

IARSLCE put out calls to groups and networks to host a data analysis meeting in their regions. Each regional host handled the participation list, the communication process for its meeting, determined the venue and meeting capacity, and handled the registration process.

The first regional data analysis meeting was the European regional data analysis meeting, which took place on November, 2024 in Antwerp, Belgium. This meeting was followed by four regional data analysis meetings in Asia (Hong Kong, China), North America (Atlanta/Raleigh/San Diego, United States), South/Latin America (Buenos Aires, Argentina), and Australia

(Sydney, Australia), all of which were completed by the end of July 2025 and each which resulted in the production of a research agenda for the region (See Figure 1).

The Europe, Asia, and North America regional data analysis meetings were held in-person. The Australia regional meeting was held virtually to accommodate participants from across the country. The South/Latin America meeting was held in hybrid format and was conducted in Spanish to reflect the primary language of the research questions and items that had been submitted during the four data collection forums that held in the region. All of the regional data analysis meetings were held over two days, except for the North America meeting, which took place over four days (in three different cities). (See At A Glance summary).

Figure 1. Setting a Global Research Agenda Process

As is noted in Figure 1, the Africa region research agenda was developed following a different data analysis protocol due to timing. Three data input forums had been completed in the region: one Cameroon in December 2023; one in South Africa in February 2025, and on Kenya in April 2025. The full set of collected data was made available for analysis in June 2025. Upon receipt of the data, several calls were made to encourage groups in the region to host the a data analysis meeting for the Africa region. Despite interest from several organizations to host the meeting, none had availability before the IARSLCE 25th Anniversary conference to coordinate and organize a data analysis meeting and finalize the production of a regional research agenda for Africa. As a result, to ensure that the voices of those who participated in the three Africa region forums are considered in this Global Research Agenda, the decision was made to conduct an independent preliminary analysis of the data using artificial intelligence analytical tools. Nicole Webster, an internationally-recognized SLCE scholar and member of the IARSLCE board, conducted the analysis and produced a preliminary copy of the Africa region research agenda, which appears in this Global Research Agenda document along with the other regions' research agendas.

DATA ANALYSIS PROCEDURES

The approach to the data analysis was the same at each of the five hosted regional meetings. The goal was to conduct a systematic and transparent review of the data that had been submitted during the forums. All the raw data from forums held in the same region were grouped. For example, all of the research questions and items collected during the five data input forums held in Europe were compiled into one document for the analysis at the European regional data analysis meeting. Members of the SLCE community from the region were invited to analyze the regional data and produce a research agenda for the region.

The participants (data analysts) at each of the regional data analysis meetings worked in small groups, with each group responsible for reviewing, organizing, categorizing, and prioritizing the research questions/items in one or more of the research agenda ten sections (research dimensions/reflection prompts) listed in Table 1.

Within each group, the analysts were asked to apply the following protocol to their analysis of the research questions/items contained in their section(s) of the regional agenda:

1. Identify, sort, and group together similar questions and items into themes or categories, and label the categories.
2. Identify questions that are vague and unclear, and set them aside. Discuss among the group what their meaning or intention might be and come to a consensus as to their focus and topic. Set aside those items and questions that are vague and cannot be well-interpreted.
3. Identify and set aside items on that may actually speak to another portion (section) of the research agenda. Identify the which research area(s) the items might belong. At a point during the meeting, you will have an opportunity to transfer those items to one

of the other groups. (NOTE: Your group may receive additional items from other groups).

4. Within each category/theme of questions and items you have established, rank the questions and items in order of priority based on your experience and expertise, using the following criteria:
 - ***The items that are mentioned most often.*** For example, if there are 7 items and questions about a particular topic and 3 about another topic, the questions mentioned most often should be given higher priority. You can skip the ranking process for categories that only have one item or question.
 - ***The items and questions for which there is very little existing research in the literature and/or topics that existing research has not explored.*** Items that focus on fresh topics that have not been well-researched should be prioritized over those that already have been well-researched.
 - ***The items and questions that are important for advancing service-learning and community engagement in the region.*** Issues and topics that are most important for advancing SLCE within the region and in your particular cultural contexts should be prioritized.
 - ***Other criteria that you deem important to further the research on service-learning and community engagement.***

Upon completing this task, you should have a set of labeled categories, each containing one or more questions/items in rank order.

5. For each category/theme, select the top ranked questions (e.g., 4-7 items) that will be included in the research agenda as representative research questions/items for the theme.
6. Prioritize the labeled categories/themes based on the same criteria as before. The order in which your themes are prioritized will be the order in which they will appear in the research agenda.
 - ***The categories with the most items and questions.***
 - ***The categories for which there is very little research and/or have not previously been explored.*** Items and topics that have not been well-researched should have priority over those that have been well-researched.

→ *The categories that are important for advancing service-learning and community engagement in the region.*

→ *Other criteria that you believe is important to further the research on service-learning and community engagement.*

The completed, analyzed sections were combined to form the research agenda for that region. At the end of the regional meeting, a preliminary copy of the agenda was presented to the analysts. Following the meeting, the participating analysts were given the option of reviewing the regional research agenda draft for final comments and edits.

STRUCTURE OF THE GLOBAL RESEARCH AGENDA

While the content of each of the completed regional research agendas is unique to the region, the agendas have the same structure and format. Each regional agenda is organized into ten sections, with each section corresponding to the research dimensions and reflection prompts presented in Table 1.

Following a statement of the prompt, a set of themes, which emerged from the data analysis, are presented. In essence, these themes (presented in bold font) are the focal point of the agenda in that they represent an encapsulation and prioritization of research questions the participants of the data input forums and data analysis meetings deemed important for future SLCE research. The number of themes and research questions included in research agenda varies (See At a Glance). Under each theme is a brief description of the theme's focus, followed by a set of research questions/topics, drawn from actual questions submitted during the forums. The questions/topics serve as suggestions for the particular questions one might investigate to advance knowledge of the stated theme.

In total, the Global Research Agenda inclusive of all six regional agendas presents 1,277 research questions/items organized within 244 themes that members of SLCE field who participated in the forums and data analysis meetings believe future studies of SLCE should consider.

At end of each regional agenda are the names and affiliations of all who contributed to the agenda as meeting hosts, facilitators, support personnel and all who participated in the data collection forums and the regional data analysis meetings. These are the individuals who built the global research agenda, and in essence, it is their proposed research agenda for the field. To them, we extend much appreciation for making this global research agenda possible.

SOME IMPORTANT CONSIDERATIONS

This research agenda represents the thoughts, ideas, and perspectives of close to 900 SLCE scholars, practitioners, partners, and researchers from more than 40 countries who volunteered their time to participate in the data collection forums and/or data analysis meetings, all in the service of building a forwarding-looking global research framework to advance the study and

practice of service-learning and community engagement across the educational spectrum. However, this research agenda should *not* be viewed as complete or comprehensive. It is only a snapshot of issues and hopes for future research from those who had the opportunity to voice their perspectives. However, today's SLCE field extends far and wide and there remain many voices from various regions, contexts, and perspectives that still need to be heard.

While this document presents a research "agenda", it should not be viewed as a prescription for research or a set plan of action. Rather, this document presents a set of reflections *from the field, for the field* as we continue to explore ways to conduct more and better research that attends to the emerging forms and practices of SLCE. In this regard, this research agenda is a touch point from which additional perspectives can be explored and other focused "agendas" can be added. The hope is that this agenda will spark further discussion about SLCE research and bring greater awareness of the cultural and regional influences that shape the ways in which SLCE is distinctly practiced and studied in different parts of the world.

GLOBAL RESEARCH AGENDA FOR SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

AT A GLANCE

NUMBER OF DATA INPUT FORUMS HELD = 29

- **March 21, 2019** Hong Kong, SAR China
- **June 20, 2019** Singapore
- **July 28, 2019** Kyoto, Japan
- **August 28, 2019** Buenos Aires, Argentina
- **September 21, 2019** Antwerp, Belgium
- **October 21, 2019** Albuquerque, New Mexico, United States
- **October 23, 2019** Albuquerque, New Mexico, United States
- **October 25, 2019** Albuquerque, New Mexico, United States
- **December 6, 2019** Monterrey, México
- **March 27, 2020** United States (*Virtual*)
- **May 18, 2020** United Kingdom (*Virtual*)
- **July 15, 2020** Slovakia (*Virtual*)
- **May 12, 2021** Hong Kong, SAR China (*Virtual*)
- **October 21, 2021** United States (*Virtual*)
- **April 21, 2022** Minneapolis, Minnesota, United States
- **March 16, 2023** Honolulu, Hawaii, United States
- **June 2, 2023** Montclair, New Jersey, United States
- **June 21, 2023** Munich, Germany [*Virtual*]
- **July 21, 2023** Bangalore, India [*Hybrid*]
- **August 25, 2023** Buenos Aires, Argentina
- **August 28, 2023** Santiago, Chile [*Virtual*]
- **September 27, 2023** Rome, Italy
- **October 24, 2023** New Orleans, Louisiana, United States
- **October 26, 2023** New Orleans, Louisiana, United States
- **December 11, 2023** Cameroon [*Virtual*]
- **February 3, 2025** Boston, Massachusetts, United States
- **February 3-8, 2025** Durban, South Africa [*Virtual*]
- **April 10, 2025** Nairobi, Kenya
- **May 14, 2025** Australia [*Virtual*]

TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS: 695

REGIONAL DISTRIBUTION OF FORUM PARTICIPANTS

HOME COUNTRIES OF DATA INPUT FORUM PARTICIPANTS

Africa

Cameroon
Kenya
Mali
Namibia
Nigeria
South Africa
Tunisia

Asia

China
Hong Kong, SAR China
India
Indonesia
Japan
Korea
Philippines
Singapore
Taiwan
Thailand
Vietnam

Australia

Australia

Europe

Belgium
Croatia
Czech Republic
Germany
Ireland
Italy
Latvia
Netherlands
Portugal
Romania
Slovakia
Spain
Ukraine
United Kingdom

Middle East

Lebanon
Saudi Arabia

North America

Canada
United States

South/Latin America

Argentina
Brazil
Chile
Colombia
Cuba
Ecuador
Mexico

TOTAL NUMBER OF RESEARCH QUESTIONS/ISSUES FROM DATA INPUT FORUMS BY REGION

Region	Number of Data Input Forums	Total Number of Items Submitted
Africa	3	1,556
Asia	5	956
Australia	1	274
Europe	5	508
North America	11	2,541
South/Latin America	4	924
TOTAL	29	6,759

DISTRIBUTION OF FORUM DATA BY RESEARCH SECTION AND REGION

REGION	RESEARCH AGENDA SECTION										<i>Total</i>
	I Imp.	II Impl.	III Inst.	IV COV.	V Equity	VI Cult.	VII Conc.	VIII Meth.	IX Instr.	X Repli.	
Africa	269	277	237	68	46	50	117	170	212	110	1,556
Asia	216	238	82	62	12	82	83	119	51	11	956
Australia	50	45	40	24	22	34	14	21	15	9	274
Europe	108	75	79	33	12	34	55	45	37	30	508
N. America	506	343	411	146	137	216	267	261	163	91	2,541
S./Lat. America	174	163	134	33	42	76	103	81	76	42	924
TOTAL	1,323	1,141	983	366	271	492	639	697	554	293	6,759

REGIONAL DATA ANALYSIS MEETINGS

- **Europe**
 - *Date:* November 20-21, 2024
 - *Location:* Antwerp, Belgium
 - *Number of Participants:* 24
 - *Participants' Home Countries:* Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Spain, United Kingdom

- **Asia**
 - *Dates:* December 2, 2024 & December 6, 2024
 - *Location:* Hong Kong, SAR China
 - *Number of Participants:* 51
 - *Participants' Home Countries:* Australia, China, Hong Kong-China, India, Japan, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, Vietnam

- **North America**
 - *Dates:* March 30, 2025; April 3-4, 2025; & May 30, 2025
 - *Locations:* United State: Atlanta, Georgia; Durham, North Carolina; & San Diego, California
 - *Number of Participants:* 44
 - *Participants' Home Country:* United States

- **South/Latin America**
 - *Dates:* June 11-12, 2025
 - *Location:* Buenos Aires, Argentina [*Hybrid*]
 - *Number of Participants:* 43
 - *Participants' Home Country:* Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Ecuador, Mexico

- **Australia**
 - *Dates:* June 24, 2025 & July 8, 2025
 - *Location:* Sydney, Australia [*Virtual*]
 - *Number of Participants:* 15
 - *Participants' Home Country:* Australia

Total No. of Data Analysts: 177

Global Representation: 27 countries

Note: For the Regional Research Agenda for Africa, a preliminary analysis of the data collected from the three data input Forums held in Africa were conducted independently by Nicole Webster of Pennsylvania State University via Thematic Analysis and Notebook LM.

GLOBAL MAP OF HOME COUNTRIES — ALL CONTRIBUTORS (FORUM PARTICIPANTS AND DATA ANALYSTS)

**NUMBER OF THEMES AND (RESEARCH QUESTIONS/ISSUES) PER RESEARCH
DIMENSION BY REGION**

REGION	RESEARCH AGENDA SECTION										Total
	I Imp.	II Impl.	III Inst.	IV COV.	V Equity	VI Cult.	VII Conc.	VIII Meth.	IX Instr.	X Repli.	
Africa	4 (20)	4 (20)	4 (20)	4 (20)	4 (20)	4 (20)	4 (20)	4 (20)	4 (20)	4 (20)	40 (200)
Asia	4 (36)	7 (33)	7 (17)	4 (13)	3 (13)	4 (17)	2 (6)	3 (12)	4 (15)	1 (3)	39 (165)
Australia	7 (39)	4 (18)	5 (23)	7 (21)	5 (21)	4 (17)	4 (14)	4 (24)	3 (16)	3 (11)	46 (204)
Europe	4 (38)	8 (21)	5 (12)	5 (8)	5 (7)	5 (10)	4 (10)	4 (8)	5 (10)	1 (4)	46 (128)
N. America	8 (41)	8 (30)	5 (18)	3 (12)	10 (53)	7 (39)	4 (23)	5 (32)	4 (12)	4 (17)	58 (277)
S./Lat. America	5 (28)	12 (35)	3 (56)	4 (23)	6 (24)	7 (26)	7 (53)	4 (18)	6 (36)	1 (4)	55 (303)
TOTAL	32 (202)	43 (157)	29 (146)	27 (97)	33 (138)	31 (129)	25 (126)	24 (114)	26 (109)	14 (59)	284 (1,277)

REGIONAL RESEARCH AGENDAS

**GLOBAL RESEARCH AGENDA FOR
SERVICE-LEARNING AND
COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT**

AFRICA REGION

Global Research Agenda for Service-Learning and Community Engagement

AFRICA REGION

This part of the global research agenda is based on an analysis of 1,556 research questions and items submitted by 47 individuals who participated in 3 forums held in Africa between December 2023 and April 2025. The information below represents a preliminary categorization and prioritization of the research questions and items conducted by Nicole Webster via a combination of discourse analysis and Notebook LM in July 2025. Additional analyses of the data and refinement of this agenda are scheduled.

I. IMPACTS

Impact research focuses on assessing the impacts of service-learning and community engagement on participants, including students, faculty, staff, institutions and the community. They cross a broad range of short-term and long-term outcomes. The agenda ideas broad areas of impact to be investigated along with a particular set of themes within each impact area. This section of the agenda presents broad areas of impact to be investigated along with a particular set of themes within each impact area.

STUDENT AND FACULTY DEVELOPMENT

Examines how service-learning/community engagement fosters academic, personal, and professional growth for students and faculty across short-, medium-, and long-term outcomes.

- How does SLCE enhance students' civic engagement, academic performance, and career readiness?
- What are the long-term effects of SLCE on students' professional identity and social responsibility?

- How does SLCE participation influence faculty teaching practices, research agendas, and tenure pathways?
 - What support systems promote sustained faculty engagement and mitigate burnout?
 - How does SLCE participation affect student development in underrepresented groups?
-

INSTITUTIONAL TRANSFORMATION

Focuses on how service-learning/community engagement influences curriculum design, institutional culture, mission alignment, and resource allocation.

- How does SLCE shape curriculum innovation and interdisciplinary collaboration?
 - What institutional policies support the integration and assessment of SLCE?
 - What is the role of SLCE in strategic planning and achieving university mission goals?
 - How does institutional participation in SLCE affect its reputation and stakeholder trust?
 - How do alumni perceive the impact of SLCE on their careers and values?
-

COMMUNITY EMPOWERMENT AND RECIPROCITY

Explores how communities perceive and benefit from service-learning/community engagement, emphasizing shared ownership and sustainable impact.

- What are the tangible and intangible impacts of SLCE on local communities?
 - How do community members define success and sustainability in partnerships?
 - What strategies ensure community voice, leadership, and feedback integration?
 - What mechanisms sustain equitable, long-term community partnerships?
 - How does SLCE promote social capital, community identity, and local development?
-

INCLUSIVE AND EQUITABLE IMPACT ASSESSMENT

Assesses how service-learning/community engagement outcomes vary across diverse populations and contexts and whether systemic disparities are addressed.

- How does SLCE participation differ for students by gender, disability, rural status, or income?
- What barriers prevent equal access to SLCE programs and benefits?
- How do institutions track the impact of SLCE on underrepresented communities and students?
- What are the unintended consequences of SLCE for different stakeholders?
- How can evaluation practices be adapted to measure inclusivity and justice outcomes?

II. IMPLEMENTATION

Implementation research focuses on examining the practices of service-learning and community engagement and the ways in which these practices are effective in achieving particular goals. Implementation studies seek to improve practice and provide guidance on best practices across a broad range of service-learning and community engagement programmatic approaches.

The research agenda identifies questions that centre on the process of delivering service-learning and community engagement across a broad range of community, cultural, geographic, disciplinary, and institutional contexts.

PROGRAM DESIGN AND PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICE

Examines how service-learning/community engagement models, instructional strategies, and reflection practices influence learning outcomes and engagement effectiveness.

- How do different SLCE models (e.g., direct service, project-based, research-based) influence outcomes for students and communities?
- What design elements (duration, intensity, reflection) lead to effective SLCE?
- How do course-based vs. co-curricular approaches compare in effectiveness?
- What reflective practices most effectively promote critical thinking and civic awareness?
- How can program designs adapt to disciplinary and cultural contexts?

COMMUNITY PARTNERSHIPS AND RECIPROCITY

Explores how institutions build, sustain, and assess mutually beneficial partnerships with communities.

- What strategies promote reciprocal, ethical partnerships between academic institutions and communities?
- How do community partners evaluate SLCE effectiveness and value?
- What are the barriers to and drivers of long-term, community-led SLCE initiatives?

- How are community-identified needs integrated into project design and assessment?
 - What mechanisms mitigate extractive engagement and reinforce shared ownership?
-

FACULTY AND INSTITUTIONAL SUPPORT STRUCTURES

Investigates faculty incentives, institutional readiness, and administrative coordination needed to scale effective service-learning and community engagement.

- What institutional policies and leadership structures support or hinder SLCE implementation?
 - How do faculty perceive workload, recognition, and resources related to SLCE?
 - What training and professional development structures prepare faculty and staff?
 - How do tenure and promotion systems affect faculty participation in SLCE?
 - What models exist for centralizing SLCE offices and cross-department coordination?
-

CONTEXTUAL AND INCLUSIVE IMPLEMENTATION

Focuses on adapting service-learning/community engagement models to specific cultural, geographic, and institutional contexts while ensuring equitable access.

- How can SLCE be implemented in underserved and rural communities?
- What adaptations ensure cultural relevance and language accessibility?
- How do institutions design programs for marginalized populations, including disabled and displaced persons?
- How do students' readiness and motivations influence SLCE outcomes?
- What implementation challenges arise in global, crisis, or hybrid learning contexts?

III. INSTITUTIONALISATION

Institutionalisation research focuses on examining the factors that promote the sustainability and institutionalisation of service-learning and community engagement across institutional and community contexts.

Studies in this area seek to conceptualize the idea of institutionalisation in light of the changing contexts of educational institutions and the varied approaches to service-learning and community engagement.

POLICY, GOVERNANCE, AND STRATEGIC ALIGNMENT

Explores how institutional policies, leadership, and governance structures embed and sustain service-learning/community engagement as part of institutional missions.

- What institutional policies and frameworks best support long-term SLCE sustainability?
 - How do service-learning goals align with institutional vision and strategic planning?
 - What role does senior leadership play in championing institutionalization of SLCE?
 - How do governance models (centralized vs. decentralized) affect SLCE growth?
 - What are the most effective methods for embedding SLCE into accreditation, policy, and quality assurance systems?
-

CURRICULAR AND CO-CURRICULAR INTEGRATION

Examines how service-learning/community engagement is incorporated into academic programs, learning outcomes, and cross-disciplinary initiatives.

- How can SLCE be systematically embedded across academic disciplines and levels?
 - What curriculum mapping strategies ensure SLCE integration and alignment?
 - How do academic programs ensure coherence between SLCE and disciplinary learning outcomes?
 - How does co-curricular SLCE complement and reinforce academic learning?
 - What institutional processes support cross-unit collaboration in SLCE integration?
-

SUSTAINABLE PARTNERSHIPS AND COMMUNITY LEADERSHIP

Focuses on maintaining long-term, equitable community relationships that inform institutional service-learning/community engagement practices.

- What strategies ensure continuity of partnerships across leadership or staffing transitions?
- How can institutions support community-led SLCE initiatives?
- What are best practices for balancing academic objectives with community-defined priorities?
- What indicators best measure community trust and satisfaction in long-term partnerships?
- How can SLCE contribute to structural changes in community development?

FACULTY ENGAGEMENT AND INSTITUTIONAL CULTURE

Investigates how institutions incentivize faculty, build institutional memory, and cultivate a culture of engagement.

- What types of incentives support faculty integration of SLCE into teaching, research, and service?
- What professional development approaches prepare faculty for SLCE leadership?
- How do institutions maintain faculty engagement beyond initial involvement?
- How does SLCE shape or reflect institutional culture, identity, and public reputation?
- How can institutionalization survive leadership changes or shifting priorities?

IV. COVID/POST-COVID

Questions and issues that explore service-learning and community engagement practices during and beyond COVID.

The issues include, but are not limited to:

- new emerging practices for service-learning and community engagement results from the pandemic;
- changes regarding the conduct of service-learning and community engagement research due to COVID;
- impact of COVID on the quality of service-learning and community engagement; and advantages and disadvantages of conducting service-learning and community engagement during or after COVID.

DIGITAL AND HYBRID MODELS OF ENGAGEMENT

Examines the design, delivery, and impact of virtual and hybrid SLCE programs developed during and after the COVID-19 pandemic.

- How do online and hybrid SLCE models compare to traditional in-person programs in terms of learning outcomes and impact?
- What digital tools and platforms have proven most effective in sustaining engagement during COVID?
- How do virtual models impact participation and partnership in rural and underserved areas?
- What innovations emerged in remote service-learning and how can they be scaled post-pandemic?
- What are best practices for shifting SLCE projects to online formats without loss of quality?

EQUITY AND ACCESS IN POST-COVID SLCE

Assesses the extent to which the pandemic amplified disparities in service-learning/community engagement access, and explores strategies for building more inclusive post-COVID practices.

- How did the digital divide affect equitable access to SLCE during the pandemic?

- What policies or supports are needed to ensure students from marginalized communities can participate fully in hybrid SLCE?
 - How did COVID-era adaptations address or exacerbate challenges for students with disabilities?
 - What funding or infrastructure investments are needed to support inclusive digital SLCE?
 - How has COVID affected student well-being and inclusion in virtual SLCE?
-

INSTITUTIONAL AND COMMUNITY ADAPTATION

Investigates how institutions and community partners responded to COVID and what lessons can inform resilient service-learning/community engagement practices moving forward.

- How did institutional commitment to SLCE change during the pandemic?
 - What were the key challenges and opportunities for faculty and community partners in adapting engagement?
 - How did community needs and engagement expectations shift during and after COVID?
 - What risk management and safety protocols are now necessary for post-pandemic SLCE?
 - How did COVID reshape institutional priorities and resource allocation for SLCE?
-

LONG-TERM INNOVATIONS AND STRUCTURAL SHIFTS

Identifies enduring shifts in service-learning/community engagement approaches catalysed by the pandemic and explores opportunities to integrate these into future practice.

- What innovations from the COVID era should be retained to enhance SLCE in the future?
- How did remote modalities improve accessibility, community input, or scalability?
- How did the pandemic change students' understanding of global citizenship and interconnectedness?
- What frameworks emerged for digital collaboration between universities and communities?
- What are the long-term implications of integrating artificial intelligence (AI) and tech into SLCE?

V. EQUITY AND SOCIAL ADVANCEMENT

Research in this area focuses on issues that explore the role of equity in service-learning and community engagement practices within and across cultures, populations, and regions. The issues include, but are not limited to, implications for conducting equity-focused research within and across different groups, populations, communities, and/or cultures.

POWER, POSITIONALITY, AND INCLUSIVE ENGAGEMENT

Investigates how power dynamics, institutional privilege, and positionality shape equity in service-learning/community engagement design, partnerships, and research.

- How do power dynamics between institutions and communities affect SLCE collaborations?
- How can SLCE shift power and amplify community agency?
- What are best practices for ensuring mutual benefit in partnerships with marginalized communities?
- How do researcher and student positionality impact equity-focused SLCE?
- How can institutions confront and dismantle systemic inequities in their SLCE practices?

INCLUSIVE ACCESS TO PARTICIPATION AND RESOURCES

Focuses on the barriers to and enablers of full participation in service-learning/community engagement among historically marginalized groups across socioeconomic, geographic, and ability lines.

- How can SLCE be designed to ensure accessibility for persons with disabilities, rural youth, and low-income students?
 - What institutional policies or financial supports reduce participation gaps in SLCE?
 - What strategies address the digital divide in virtual SLCE?
 - How do gender and intersectionality influence access to and experience of SLCE?
 - What accommodations are needed for equitable SLCE implementation across linguistic and cultural barriers?
-

CULTURALLY RESPONSIVE AND EQUITY- CENTRED PRACTICE

Explores approaches to service-learning/community engagement that centre community values, respect diverse identities, and promote equity through curriculum, pedagogy, and research design.

- What culturally responsive practices are most effective in SLCE across African contexts?
- How can curriculum and pedagogy reflect community priorities and lived experience?
- What tools and frameworks support culturally grounded equity assessments?
- How does equity-centred design differ across institutional and community contexts?
- How can institutions integrate intersectional justice into SLCE program design?

CRITICAL REFLECTION, SOCIAL JUSTICE AND IMPACT

Examines how service-learning/community engagement fosters social justice orientation among students and communities and how equity-focused impacts are measured and sustained.

- How can students be guided to reflect on privilege, oppression, and justice in SLCE?
- How do equity-focused SLCE programs impact community development and resilience?
- What long-term indicators assess equitable social change outcomes?
- How can SLCE be aligned with broader anti-racism and social transformation goals?
- What evaluation tools assess inclusion and agency in SLCE partnerships?

VI. CULTURAL/REGIONAL AND CROSS-CULTURAL/CROSS-REGIONAL

Issues that explore service-learning and community engagement practices within and across cultures and regions are to be embraced and discussed, with an eye toward identifying questions or action steps for the research agenda.

The research issues include, but is not limited to:

- conducting research within and across different cultural or geographic settings;
- examining service-learning and community engagement across the educational spectrum;
- community voice;
- multiple frames of service-learning and community engagement.

CONTEXTUAL ADAPTION AND LOCAL KNOWLEDGE INTEGRATION

Explores how service-learning/community engagement practices and research adapt to local cultural, linguistic, and geographic contexts while incorporating indigenous knowledge systems.

- How can service-learning be adapted to respect cultural norms, traditions, and community values?
- What role does indigenous knowledge play in shaping locally responsive SLCE?
- What challenges arise when implementing SLCE in rural or linguistically diverse communities?
- How can institutions ensure ethical engagement that aligns with community cultural protocols?
- How can SLCE be decolonized to elevate community agency and knowledge systems?

CROSS-CULTURAL COMPETENCE AND COMPARATIVE LEARNING

Focuses on building intercultural understanding among students, faculty, and partners while examining differences and commonalities across regions and cultures.

- How do service-learning experiences foster intercultural competencies and global citizenship?
- What are the similarities and differences in SLCE practices across African regions?
- How can faculty and students be trained to navigate cross-cultural contexts in SLCE?

- What research paradigms are most effective for comparing SLCE across regional and cultural settings?
 - What challenges arise in cross-cultural partnerships and how can they be mitigated?
-

MULTI-LINGUAL AND ETHICAL RESEARCH PRACTICE

Investigates how service-learning/community engagement research can be conducted in diverse linguistic and cultural contexts while adhering to ethical principles and inclusion.

- How can research tools be developed in local languages to improve accessibility?
 - What confidentiality and consent practices are appropriate in different cultural settings?
 - How can researchers avoid imposing Western frameworks and instead co-create methodologies with communities?
 - What role do community advisory boards play in ethical and inclusive research?
 - How can comparative research contribute to local knowledge without extraction?
-

REGIONAL COLLABORATION AND SHARED FRAMEWORKS

Encourages collaboration across institutions and regions to develop shared service-learning/community engagement frameworks that reflect African contexts and values.

- How can cross-institutional partnerships support capacity building in SLCE?
- What regional narratives and principles can anchor African-led SLCE frameworks?
- How can regional evaluation tools support SLCE monitoring and improvement?
- How can institutions share knowledge to support supported and developing SLCE sites?
- How do supported institutions interpret and apply SLCE practices in culturally diverse areas?

VII. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORKS AND THEORIES

The field of service-learning and community engagement has been criticised for being under-theorized and for lacking well-developed and well-tested conceptual frameworks.

Research in this area of work focuses on theory testing and building conceptual models and frameworks that explain various phenomena in the study and practice of service-learning and community engagement.

DEVELOPMENT OF AFRICAN-CENTRIC FRAMEWORKS

Focuses on creating service-learning/community engagement models rooted in African philosophies and indigenous knowledge systems.

- How can indigenous African philosophies (e.g., Ubuntu) be incorporated into SLCE frameworks?
- What cultural values underpin community engagement practices in different African contexts?
- How do traditional community decision-making structures influence SLCE partnerships?
- What role do language and local customs play in shaping effective engagement models?
- How do African-centric frameworks compare with Western models in achieving desired outcomes?

THEORY TESTING IN DIVERSE CONTEXTS

Examines how existing service-learning/community engagement theories apply and adapt across varied African contexts.

- How effective are established Western SLCE theories when applied in African institutions?
- What modifications are needed to adapt these theories to rural versus urban African settings?
- How do political and economic conditions influence the theoretical underpinnings of SLCE?

- What indicators can validate the contextual relevance of these theories in Africa?
 - Are there common theoretical challenges experienced across multiple African institutions?
-

INTEGRATION WITH CRITICAL PEDAGOGY

Explores the use of critical pedagogy to address power, equity, and social justice in service-learning and community engagement.

- How can critical pedagogy enhance students' understanding of power, privilege, and equity in SLCE?
 - In what ways does critical reflection contribute to transformative learning in SLCE?
 - What are the implications of using critical theory for engaging marginalized communities?
 - How does student activism interface with community-engaged learning?
 - Can critical pedagogy be effectively implemented in hierarchical academic settings?
-

MULTIDISCIPLINARY THEORETICAL CONSTRUCTS

Combines theories from various disciplines to form comprehensive service-learning/community engagement models.

- How can SLCE theory benefit from integration with theories from public health, sociology, or environmental science?
- What are the synergies between disciplinary perspectives in explaining SLCE outcomes?
- Which disciplines offer the most robust theoretical contributions to community engagement?
- How can transdisciplinary models be used to address complex community challenges?
- What are the limits of multidisciplinary approaches in framing SLCE research?

VIII. METHODOLOGICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The issues in this section focus on identifying the kinds of methods that are appropriate for the study of service-learning and community engagement. The items consider the research designs, methods, epistemologies and approaches that are needed and required in designing and operationalizing future research on service-learning and community engagement.

ENHANCING METHODOLOGICAL RIGOR IN SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT RESEARCH

This theme focuses on strengthening the validity, reliability, and credibility of research methods used in service-learning and community engagement (SLCE).

- How can methodological rigor be ensured in qualitative and mixed-method SLCE studies?
- What are the best practices for addressing bias and researcher subjectivity in SLCE evaluations?
- How do context-specific variables affect methodological rigor in African SLCE research?
- What role does triangulation play in improving data quality and interpretation?
- How can peer debriefing and audit trails be used to validate findings in SLCE studies?

ADAPTING AND LOCALIZING RESEARCH DESIGNS

This theme explores the customization of research methodologies to suit local cultural, political, and institutional contexts across Africa.

- How can SLCE research methodologies be adapted to fit rural vs. urban African contexts?
- What local knowledge systems can inform culturally responsive research design?
- How do regional education policies influence methodological choices in SLCE research?
- What are the challenges and benefits of co-designing research with community stakeholders?
- How can localized methods maintain academic rigor while respecting community norms?

PARTICIPATORY AND COMMUNITY-BASED METHODOLOGIES

This theme emphasizes inclusive approaches that involve community members in research planning, data collection, and analysis.

- What frameworks best support community participation in SLCE research?
- How does participatory research influence data ownership and ethics?
- What are the impacts of co-researcher models on research outcomes?
- How can trust be built and maintained throughout participatory research processes?
- What tools ensure equitable participation of marginalized voices in data collection?

INNOVATIONS IN DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

This theme highlights new tools, technologies, and approaches for data gathering and analysis in SLCE research.

- What role do digital tools (e.g., mobile apps, online platforms) play in SLCE data collection?
- How can visual or arts-based methods enhance understanding of community experiences?
- What innovations are most effective for longitudinal SLCE research in low-resource settings?
- How can artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning be integrated into qualitative SLCE analysis?
- What ethical considerations arise with the use of new technologies in community-based research?

IX. INSTRUMENTS AND MEASURES

Securing quality research requires valid and appropriate instruments and measures that can secure the best data and provide opportunities for thorough, systematic analyses. Many of the instruments that have been developed for the study of service-learning and community engagement are home grown instruments that are often applied to single studies and are not cultivated further for potential use in other studies. In addition, there are many instruments that are available for studies of service-learning and community engagement, but it is sometimes unclear regarding the suitability of such instruments for programs or populations for which they were not initially designed.

The research agenda identifies issues for improving the instrumentation and measurement of service-learning and community engagement across the many contexts in which the work takes place.

CONTEXTUAL VALIDITY OF TOOLS

Assesses how well existing instruments fit African cultural and institutional contexts.

- How culturally appropriate are Western-developed SLCE assessment tools for African populations?
- What modifications are needed to make existing instruments relevant in local contexts?
- How do students and community partners perceive the relevance of these tools?
- Are there regional differences in the suitability of these instruments?
- What validation strategies are most effective in testing contextual fit?

DEVELOPMENT OF STANDARDIZED INSTRUMENTS

Aims to create consistent and validated tools for service-learning and community engagement evaluation across institutions.

- What core dimensions of SLCE should be measured across programs?
- How can consistency in assessment support comparative research across institutions?

- What challenges exist in developing standardized instruments for diverse African settings?
 - Can a pan-African SLCE assessment toolkit be developed and validated?
 - What key performance indicators should be used to evaluate program impact?
-

PARTICIPATORY EVALUATION APPROACHES

Involves communities in designing and assessing service-learning and community engagement tools to enhance relevance and trust.

- How can community members contribute to the design of SLCE measurement tools?
 - What are the benefits and limitations of participatory evaluation in SLCE?
 - How does co-creation influence the legitimacy and accuracy of impact assessments?
 - What ethical considerations arise in community-led measurement?
 - Can participatory approaches improve stakeholder buy-in and trust?
-

LONGITUDINAL DATA COLLECTION TOOLS

Focuses on tools for tracking long-term service-learning and community engagement outcomes for students and communities.

- What tools are effective for tracking long-term student and community outcomes?
- How can digital technologies (e.g., mobile surveys, apps) support longitudinal SLCE research?
- What are the challenges of retaining participants in long-term studies?
- How do long-term outcomes differ between students and community partners?
- What institutional support is needed to maintain long-term data systems?

X. REPLICATION

No one study provides all the evidence, understanding, or knowledge that is needed to draw firm conclusions about service-learning or community engagement. Replication is a critical feature of scientific inquiry and research.

Only a handful of service-learning and community engagement studies have been replicated. Replicating high quality studies is a way to strengthen evidence and secure more conclusive findings about the strengths and limitations of service-learning and community engagement practices, outcomes, and approaches.

REPLICATION OF HIGH-IMPACT MODELS

Tests proven service-learning and community engagement programs in new contexts to validate their broader applicability.

- What criteria should guide the selection of SLCE programs for replication?
 - How do contextual variables affect the scalability of successful programs?
 - What are common success factors in replicated SLCE initiatives?
 - How can communities be engaged in the replication process?
 - What pitfalls should be avoided when attempting replication?
-

METHODOLOGICAL RIGOR IN REPLICATION

Promotes consistent and precise methods for reliable replication studies.

- What research designs best support robust replication?
 - How can fidelity to original interventions be maintained across contexts?
 - What are the methodological challenges in replicating community-based research?
 - How can triangulation improve the validity of replication outcomes?
 - What lessons can be learned from failed replications?
-

CROSS-COUNTRY COMPARATIVE STUDIES

Replicates studies across countries to explore cultural and contextual differences.

- How do SLCE outcomes compare across different African countries?
 - What role do national education policies play in shaping replication potential?
 - How can cultural and socio-political differences be accounted for in cross-country studies?
 - What indicators are most transferable between countries?
 - What models of SLCE have shown effectiveness across borders?
-

BUILDING A CULTURE OF REPLICATION

Encourages institutional support and incentives to make replication common in service-learning and community research.

- How can academic institutions promote replication as a standard research activity?
 - What incentives (e.g., funding, publication outlets) are needed to encourage replication?
 - How can replication be integrated into faculty development and student training?
 - What infrastructure (e.g., databases, research networks) supports replication?
 - How does a replication culture enhance the credibility of SLCE research?
-

CONTRIBUTORS

Forum Participants

CAMEROON [VIRTUAL] (December 11, 2023)

Hosted by the Network of Protestant Universities in Central Africa

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SOUTH AFRICA (February 5-8, 2025)

Hosted by the South African Higher Education Community Engagement Forum (SAHECEF)
Darren Lortan (SAHECEF)

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Note: 13 additional individuals participated anonymously.

NAIROBI, KENYA (April 10, 2025)

Hosted by Tangaza University

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Data Analysis

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Preliminary Analysis conducted via Thematic analysis and Notebook LM – July 2025.

**GLOBAL RESEARCH AGENDA FOR
SERVICE-LEARNING AND
COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT**

ASIA REGION

Global Research Agenda for Service-Learning and Community Engagement

ASIA Region

The content contained in this part of the global research agenda is based on an analysis of 956 research questions and items submitted by 197 individuals who participated in 5 data input Forums held in Asia between March 2019 and July 2023. The questions and items were categorized and prioritized by 51 individuals from across the Asia region who participated in two data analysis meetings held in Hong Kong, SAR China in December 2024. The results of their analyses and discussions are presented here.

I. IMPACTS

Impact research focuses on assessing the impacts of service-learning and community engagement on participants, including students, faculty, staff, institutions and the community. They cross a broad range of short-term and long-term outcomes. This section of the agenda presents broad areas of impact to be investigated along with a particular set of themes within each impact area.

IMPACT ON STUDENTS

Investigate the ways in which participation in service-learning and community engagement impact students' career and civic development, soft skills, and sense of agency.

Career Development, Soft Skills, and Generic Competencies

- What are the impacts of service-learning and community engagement on students' leadership development?

- How can service-learning and community engagement inspire students' and institutions' entrepreneurship?
- Does service-learning and community engagement involvement pre-dispose students to follow career paths that emphasize community engagement?
- Does service-learning and community engagement involvement pre-dispose students to undertake more volunteering work after graduation?
- What's the impact on students' career design/plan and formation? Does service-learning and community engagement provide advantages to students' future, long-term plans?
- What is service-learning's and community engagement's impacts on enhancing students' willingness and ability to communicate?
- What is the impact of service-learning and community engagement on students' epistemological viewpoint, such as critical inquiry or positionality.

Student Civic-Mindedness, Citizenship, and Cultural Awareness

- What is the impact of service-learning and community engagement participation on students' civic development, particularly in the longer run?
- To what extent do international students who participate in service-learning and community engagement impact local communities? To what extent do they keep their culture or change their culture as a result of service-learning and community engagement participation in international contexts?
- How does service-learning positively or negatively influence awareness or value of culturally relevant/ indigenous knowledge systems on students?
- What is the impact on the community when service-learning students share a different language/culture from that of the community?
- What is the impact of service-learning and community engagement on students' civic and citizenship behaviour outside the classroom?

Student Motivation and Agency

- How does mandatory service-learning and community engagement impact the motivation of students and other participants?
 - In what ways and to what extent does service-learning promote the agency of students?
-

IMPACT ON COMMUNITY

Conduct investigation that examine the contributions and impact of service-learning and community engagement on the community and ways in which community partners participate in service-learning and community engagement programs.

Contributions to the Community

- What are the contributions of service-learning and community engagement participants on the challenges and difficult situations of partner community members?
- What are effective strategies for measuring community impact through informal means?
- Connect research impacts to community impact.
- Measure the impact of both in-person and online service-learning on the community.

Community Collaboration

- What is the willingness of community to participate in service-learning and community engagement?
 - What is the effect of giving a leadership role to a stakeholder in a service-learning or community program (e.g., student participant or member of the community)?
-

IMPACT ON ACADEMIC INSTITUTIONS

Investigate the effects that the advancement of service-learning and community engagement has on institutions' policies, innovation, and image.

Institutional Policy

- How does service-learning and community engagement impact the ways in which faculty development is delivered?
- How does service-learning impact teachers? Are the impacts positive or negative on their career? on their motivation?
- What are factors that affect faculty members' satisfaction with service-learning and community engagement? What promotes teachers' service-learning/community engagement burn-out?
- How does mandatory service-learning impact the motivation of participants?

- To what extent does institutional financial support impact an institution's ability to advance the institutionalization of service-learning and community engagement efforts?

Academic Institutional Innovation

- How can service-learning and community engagement inspire students' and institutions' innovation?

Institutional Image

- How are service activities in the community changing local people's understanding of the university?

IMPACT ON SOCIETY

Investigate the ripple effects of service-learning and community engagement on broad societal issues that might extend beyond the particular communities in which service-learning and community engagement take place.

Long-term Changes and Broader Impacts

- What is the long-term impact of service-learning and community engagement on building a more inclusive community?
- To what extent can service-learning and community engagement help further innovate the society by transferring knowledge from university to the community?
- What are the differential benefits of service-learning/community engagement for the various stakeholders and participants?
- What types of ripple effects are promoted by service-learning/community engagement that lead to long-term changes?
- What is the role of service-learning/community engagement participants in advancing the socio-economic situation among community partners?

Policy Changes

- How can service-learning/community engagement within the higher institutions impact the changes within a community, which in turn affects policy changes on a national level?
- Does a university's community engagement efforts contribute positively to an aging society with a declining birthrate?

- What are the micro, mezzo, and macro level effects of service-learning/community engagement on communities and educational systems?

Internationalization

- How service learning can be a tool for integration of international students, internationalization of domestic students, and renewal of community organizations/local community?

II. IMPLEMENTATION

Implementation research focuses on examining the practices of service-learning and community engagement and the ways in which these practices are effective in achieving particular goals. Implementation studies seek to improve practice and provide guidance on best practices across a broad range of service-learning and community engagement programmatic approaches.

The research agenda identifies questions that centre on the process of delivering service-learning and community engagement across a broad range of community, cultural, geographic, disciplinary, and institutional contexts.

TEACHING AND LEARNING – KNOWLEDGE

Conduct studies that build knowledge and understanding of best practices for implementing high quality service-learning and community engagement.

- Considering the limited resources and time, what are reasonable learning outcomes for the institution, staff, and students from service-learning and community engagement programs?
- What are some effective professional development models for teachers/faculty guiding service-learning/community engagement projects?
- Are there reflection models that are more suitable for different types of service-learning/community engagement experiences?
- What is the appropriate type and effective amount pre-learning students should engage in before beginning their service-learning experience?
- Diversity in service-learning activity and empathy building for virtual service-learning is important. Online platform constrain teaching and learning for both students and faculties. How could we improve virtual teaching and learning for students to engage and build empathy?
- What are that ineffective strategies used in implementing service-learning and community engagement that should be avoided?

TEACHING AND LEARNING - ASSESSMENT

Conduct studies that build knowledge and understanding of best practices for assessing the quality and impact of service-learning and community engagement.

- What are effective ways for measuring the performance of students who are good at local activities and leadership, but are not good at writing reports?
- For effective reflection, it is important to set goals before (but during) the service-learning activity. What are the best practices for sharing the project goals and setting personal

growth goals while in the process of achieving them?

- How can we better promote better visualization and verbalization of the impressive service-learning/community engagement experiences by students and community members? In particular, how we get students to describe their relationship with community members and capture the emotional sides of their service-learning/community engagement experiences?
 - Which are the most effective approaches to reflection? Reflection with oneself, with someone, with the community, with all stakeholders?
-

PARTNERSHIP AND COLLABORATION

Conduct studies that explore best practices in deepening community partnerships and collaboration in service-learning and community engagement programming.

- How do we best facilitate interdisciplinary collaboration in service-learning and community engagement?
 - What are effective practices for gaining community members' support for service-learning and community engagement?
 - What are effective practices for motivating local communities (organizations) to participate in service-learning and community engagement? What are good materials to share with partners?
 - What is the level of involvement of the communities in service learning/community engagement initiatives? Is it collaborative and participatory or is it only beneficiary?
 - What community cultural issues (e.g., dialects, norms, etc.) need to be considered in the development of service-learning/community engagement methods rooted in local communities?
 - Feedback is often collected from community partners for each service-learning activity, but the data remains inside the class doing the service-learning and the use of the data is limited (e.g., used only to reflect on how to improve the service-learning activity). What are other potential effective uses might there be for this important and valuable feedback?
 - What are effective strategies for building strong partnerships among higher education institutions, community organizations, and corporates?
-

PARTICIPANT MOTIVATION

Investigate strategies and best practices for enhancing stakeholders' motivation to participate in service-learning and community engagement.

- What are effective strategies for changing students' motivations from extrinsic motivation to intrinsic motivation? Does engaging students face-to-face with the organization help make this shift from extrinsic to intrinsic motivation?
 - What are ways to build students' intrinsic motivation for service-learning and community engagement, rather than seeing service-learning as something the university is asking them to do?
 - What are ways to optimize the willingness of students/communities/teachers/institutions to engage in service-learning and community engagement?
-

SUSTAINABILITY

Conduct studies to identify best practices for mitigating common challenges and barriers to service-learning and community engagement implementation.

- How do we effectively teach large classes in service-learning classes?
 - How do we make service-learning and community engagement projects less time consuming?
 - How do you sustain long-term involvement in regions and communities that are rapidly changing?
 - While longer activities may produce a larger effect, the reality is that service-learning/community engagement can only be done for a short while there are classes. What are ways to optimize the effect of service-learning/community engagement when the duration of the experience is relatively short?
 - What are best approaches and practices for teachers to fill in the missing parts of the solutions that service-learning students have come up with to solve local problems? Should they fill in the missing parts for the students?
-

STRUCTURE AND DESIGN

Build a clearer understanding of the most effective structures and designs for implementing and advancing service-learning and community engagement.

- How is service-learning distinct from field study, internship, curriculum education, venture business, social entrepreneurship?

- How does the location and community affect how service-learning is interpreted in different contexts?
- To what extent should service-learning and community engagement activities be structured? Too much structure restricts students' agency. Not enough structure can confuse students about the purpose and expectations of the experience. What is the proper balance to achieve to optimize program impact?
- What are the different models of service-learning and community engagement practiced at institutions? How are they similar and different, and what is the relationship between the structures/foci of the models and the impacts they produce?
- Is it appropriate to modify learning and service goals in the middle of the service-learning/community engagement experience? What are the implications of making such modifications?
- Develop a guide that consolidates practice wisdom for conducting high quality e-Service-learning.
- What are effective strategies for instituting successful incentives to engage faculty in service-learning/community engagement at an institution that emphasizes research, and in light of the fact that many faculty members are not trained to conduct service-learning or community engagement?

TEACHING AND LEARNING - ETHICS

Conduct studies that examine ethical issues that undergird service-learning and community engagement practices.

- What are ethical issues of allowing not well-prepared students to engage in service-learning/community engagement activities?

III. INSTITUTIONALISATION

Institutionalisation research focuses on examining the factors that promote the sustainability and institutionalisation of service-learning and community engagement across institutional and community contexts.

Studies in this area seek to conceptualize the idea of institutionalisation in light of the changing contexts of educational institutions and the varied approaches to service-learning and community engagement.

INSTITUTIONAL CULTURE AND SUPPORT

Conduct investigations that examine the key indicators, structures, and approaches to institutionalising service-learning and community engagement in educational institutions.

- What are considerations and effective strategies for advancing leadership for service-learning and community engagement?
 - How do we integrate an institutionalised program/discipline of service-learning and community engagement with the full suite of institutional priorities and strategic efforts?
 - What are the most effective and comprehensive institutional enablers/support and resources for institutionalising service-learning and community engagement?
 - How do we embed service-learning and community engagement into an institution as part of the institution's mission and values?
 - What university attitudes or culture withholds an institution from supporting service-learning/community engagement?
 - What is the role of the central administration office in furthering the institutionalisation of service-learning/community engagement?
 - At what point can community engagement/service-learning be considered a 'way of life' at the institution? What are the key indicators of institutionalisation?
 - What are the best practices for building closer collaborations among the offices on campus housed with the different units of the organizational structure?
-

ROLE OF STAKEHOLDERS IN INSTITUTIONALISATION

Investigate the roles and contributions of key stakeholders in advancing the institutionalisation of service-learning and community engagement in educational institutions.

- How do institutions enable the faculty team to institutionalize service-learning?
 - What is the role of the community in institutionalising service-learning/community engagement?
-

INSTITUTIONALISATION SUSTAINABILITY AND STABILITY

Investigate models and effective strategies for sustaining service-learning/community engagement over the long-term after institutionalisation has been achieved.

- Once institutionalisation has been achieved, how do we sustain service-learning/community engagement within rigid educational systems (e.g., educational systems that are becoming more risk averse)?
 - Globally, is there a point of institutionalization that can withstand changes in leadership, service-learning/community engagement champions, etc.?
-

BEST PRACTICES/MODELS OF INSTITUTIONALISATION IN THE REGION

Conduct investigations that unpack the regional cultural dimensions that help explain how to best institutionalise service-learning and community engagement in the Asia-Pacific context.

- What are institutionalisation best practices, models, and experiences of universities in the Asia-Pacific context?
-

TRACKING AND EVALUATION

Investigate the ways in which metrics, measurement, and assessment can further institutionalisation of service-learning and community engagement in educational institutions.

- What is the role of monitoring and evaluation for ensuing effective institutionalisation of service-learning and community engagement/
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MANDATORY/COMPULSORY SERVICE-LEARNING

Investigate the advantages and drawbacks of required service-learning.

- What are different models, advantages, and downsides in institutionalising mandatory service-learning requirement (both curricular and co-curricular requirements)?
 - What kinds of service-learning requirements, if any, produce the most positive outcomes for students, faculty, and community partners?
-

INTERACTION WITH GLOBAL RANKINGS/Frameworks

Conduct studies that examine the relationship between service-learning/community engagement efforts and institutional ranking systems.

- Does institutionalising service-learning help in the ranking system for higher education institutions?

IV. COVID/POST-COVID

Questions and issues that explore service-learning and community engagement practices during and beyond COVID.

The issues include, but are not limited to:

- new emerging practices for service-learning and community engagement results from the pandemic;
- changes regarding the conduct of service-learning and community engagement research due to COVID;
- impact of COVID on the quality of service-learning and community engagement; and
- advantages and disadvantages of conducting service-learning and community engagement during or after COVID.

IMPACT AND CHALLENGES OF E-SERVICE-LEARNING

Conduct investigations that identify the best practices for conducting high quality e-Service-learning and the impacts that particular e-Service-learning practices have on participants.

- How do we observe and evaluate progress and impact of service-learning when service-learning is conducted online?
- How do we mitigate the constraints of online platforms that limit the kinds and amounts of interactions that students can have with their community partners and each other?
- What are strategies for developing student empathy via online service-learning?
- How does service learning affect the students of the community who do not have access to internet?
- Were the community issues addressed effectively through e-Service-learning?

PEDAGOGY AND ASSESSMENT FOR E-SERVICE-LEARNING

Investigate the ways in which COVID has shaped how service-learning and e-Service-learning are practised and assessed.

- To what extent and in what ways have the practices of service-learning and e-Service-learning changed/evolved from during the COVID-19 pandemic to post-COVID-19 pandemic?
- Is the student evaluation rubric made in non-pandemic times valid in the pandemic period as well?

- What are the best practices for conducting effective evaluations to capture e-Service-learning results, including capturing the results and impacts for the community/society?
 - How can we set or measure the genuineness of the conduct of the online service-learning? Are there measures to follow?
 - How are our community organizations moving forward after the pandemic? Has their work changed? Have their views on partnerships changed?
-

INTERNATIONAL SERVICE-LEARNING

Conduct investigations that examine the extent to which COVID has influenced the approaches to international service-learning.

- How have electronic tools been used and benefitted international service-learning programs?
 - To what extent, if any, has COVID shifted traditional in-person international service-learning experience to e-Service-learning experiences?
-

ETHICAL CONSIDERATION FOR E-SERVICE-LEARNING

Investigate the various ethical issues and challenges that may arise in e-Service-learning.

- What are the ethics issues that need to be considered in conducting e-Service-learning?

V. EQUITY AND SOCIAL ADVANCEMENT

Research in this area focuses on issues that explore the role of equity in service-learning and community engagement practices within and across cultures, populations, and regions. The issues include, but are not limited to, implications for conducting equity-focused research within and across different groups, populations, communities, and/or cultures.

DEFINITION AND MEASUREMENT OF EQUITY

Explore the different definitions and conceptualisations of equity in the conduct of service-learning and community engagement across cultures and contexts.

- How do we define and measure equity among all stakeholders of service-learning?
 - What does equity mean to individuals and groups in different community and cultural contexts?
 - Can we really define an ‘equity’ in different contexts?
-

EQUITY ISSUES IN THE PRACTICE OF SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

Identify the particular aspects of equity (cultural, religious, economic, racial, ability, etc.) that are of most interest to community partners.

- Service-learning and community engagement always have issues with economic and social inequities across cultures due to the fact that community partners are always identified as more disadvantaged. How does this view impact how students and faculty approach their community partners in service-learning and community engagement programs?
 - What are some negative impacts of service-learning when service-learning work/projects on equity and social advancement are stopped/ended before it comes to fruition?
-

BEST PRACTICES IN SERVICE-LEARNING/COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT FOR EQUITY AND SOCIAL ADVANCEMENT

Explore best practices to effectively address issues of equity and social advancement in service-learning and community engagement programs.

- What are best practices for advocating for and advancing epistemic justice in service-learning?
 - What are best practices for making equity and social development a more intentional component of service-learning and community engagement programs?
 - What processes must be in place to ensure that service learning and community engagement do not reinforce the status quo but rather advances equity?
 - What are the best practices for conducting orientation on equity to all stakeholders.
 - To enhance the equity between countries in international service-learning, to what extent should service-learning include post-colonial studies, reconciliation (e.g. on the past war experiences) and other historical learning? Does selecting some topics/issues over others unintentionally create a sense of exclusion?
 - What are the best practices for ensuring maintenance of equity amongst students and community members while practising service-learning?
 - How can we leverage service-learning and community engagement to bring social equity?
 - What service-learning empowerment program is best for least-privileged communities?
-

VI. CULTURAL/REGIONAL AND CROSS-CULTURAL/CROSS-REGIONAL

Issues that explore service-learning and community engagement practices within and across cultures and regions are to be embraced and discussed, with an eye toward identifying questions or action steps for the research agenda.

The research issues include, but is not limited to:

- conducting research within and across different cultural or geographic settings;
- examining service-learning and community engagement across the educational spectrum;
- community voice;
- multiple frames of service-learning and community engagement.

CROSS-CULTURAL PRACTICES IN SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

Conduct studies to explore effective strategies for conducting service-learning and community engagement across cultures, borders, and contexts.

- How do you prepare service-learners to work with cultures or nations different from their own?
 - What aspects of service-learning and community engagement in a region can be expanded to other regions?
 - How transferable are service-learning initiatives across cultures and communities?
 - How can we have a shared common knowledge of service-learning and community engagement despite cultural differences?
 - How to contextualize the outcome of service-learning and community engagement practice in cross-border institutions by replicating the studies?
 - What are practices that make service-learning/community engagement in and across Asia unique or similar to service-learning/community engagement in other places?
 - How can leading coordinating organizations provide common platform for spreading service-learning and community engagement best practices between cross border institutions?
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COMMUNITY VOICE

Investigate effective strategies to leverage community assets and voice to produce better outcomes for all service-learning and community engagement stakeholders and participants.

- How do we understand the community voice in different cultural and social settings?
- What are the best mechanisms to empower the community in service-learning and community engagement through the leveraging of community partner assets and expertise?
- Because people with different norms will be involved in service-learning and community engagement, how can we encourage them to not only respect differences, but also see common ground and points of convergence? What guidance is needed to build this sense of cross-cultural respect?
- How can the current community priorities influence how we integrate the different disciplines of the institution using service-learning/community engagement? What are the best approaches to inline service-learning/community engagement studies with government policies and agenda to get the needed support for educational institutions?

RESEARCH WITHIN AND ACROSS COUNTRIES AND CULTURES

Conduct comparative studies across countries and cultural settings to identify similarities and differences in service-learning and community engagement practice and impact.

- Conduct a multi-national comparison study that examples the elements (e.g., leadership, political climate, history, cultural context) that may influence an institutions' ability to institutionalize service-learning and community engagement?
 - What are some issues that may arise when working cross culturally (e.g., among the different Asian countries)? What do these issues look like within each country? How similar or different are they across countries.
 - Conduct a study on how a country's or region's culture and language play a role in service-learning and community engagement programs.
 - Cultural contexts are different so the contexts need to be explained in great detail. Is it possible to use the same assessment in different cultural settings? What are the rules for applying research instruments and approaches across different contexts?
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SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT ACROSS THE EDUCATIONAL SPECTRUM

Investigate how the different political environments across the region impact the ways in which service-learning and community engagement are practiced and institutionalized.

- Conduct studies that identify the cross-cultural gaps which inhibits students from diverse background in implementing service-learning projects at different levels of the educational spectrum (primary, secondary, tertiary education)?
- Conduct a comparison of student learning in national and international service-learning programs, examining the commonalities and differences in growth at different educational levels.

VII. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORKS AND THEORIES

The field of service-learning and community engagement has been criticised for being under-theorized and for lacking well-developed and well-tested conceptual frameworks.

Research in this area of work focuses on theory testing and building conceptual models and frameworks that explain various phenomena in the study and practice of service-learning and community engagement.

SERVICE-LEARNING FRAMEWORKS/MODELS IN THE ASIAN CONTEXT

Build a deeper and expanded conceptual understanding of service-learning in the Asian context and explore the elements that contribute to high quality service-learning programming, based on that understanding.

- Develop a typology of service-learning in Asian regional contexts that is reflective of national culture, political ideologies, educational systems, religious dimensions, etc.
- Develop a framework for high quality curricular and co-curricular service-learning course/module design and development that considers Asian service-learning context.

APPLICATION OF THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT IN ASIAN CONTEXTS

Examine how different theories and conceptual frameworks can be best applied to advance service-learning and community engagement practice and impact across Asia.

- What are some non-Western non-White decolonizing theories/conceptual frameworks that can adopt be adopted or learned from to better understand the role of and best approaches to service-learning and community engagement in the various Asian contexts.
- What are the ways that service-learning and community engagement impact participants' development of spirituality and personal reflection?
- Develop measures that more precisely defines the relationship or "life-changing" experience which students often experience after service-learning.
- Explore the use and application of Communitarianism (e.g., Etzioni, John Rawls) as a philosophical, socio-moral underpinning for service-learning in Asia.

VIII. METHODOLOGICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The issues in this section focus on identifying the kinds of methods that are appropriate for the study of service-learning and community engagement. The items consider the research designs, methods, epistemologies and approaches that are needed and required in designing and operationalizing future research on service-learning and community engagement.

A broad range of research designs, methods, and approaches are needed in order to gain a full understanding of the nature of the field. A broad range of epistemologies are required in designing and operationalizing today's research on service-learning and community engagement.

QUANTITATIVE METHODS

Advance the development of high quality quantitative methodological approaches and apply them judiciously to investigate new and important research questions that will advance service-learning and community engagement in Asia.

- Develop approaches to quantitatively measure levels of authenticity and reciprocity in service-learning and community engagement experiences.
 - Systematically quantify and develop evidence that demonstrates regional contributions of service-learning and community engagement.
 - Conduct validation with the Asian context of existing quantitative measures used in service-learning and community engagement.
-

QUALITATIVE METHODS

Examine the potential value, use, and role of different qualitative methods in studies of service-learning and community engagement.

- Conduct ethnographic research method studies to study the community perspective in service-learning and community engagement.
 - Explore the advantages and limitations of using participatory action research in service-learning and community engagement research.
-

MULTI-FACETED RESEARCH DESIGNS (MIXED-METHOD, LONGITUDINAL, COMPARATIVE)

Examine the potential value, use, and role of mixed methods in studies of service-learning and community engagement.

- Design longitudinal studies of factors outside of service-learning/community engagement that contribute to the impact of stakeholders (students, community partners, institutions).
- Develop more effective/standardized methods involving the community partners and secure their input (through surveys or interviews) regarding the perceptions of the service activities performed.
- Apply more mixed methods that use the narrative analysis, documentary analysis, and focus group discussion with descriptive research analysis to develop more comprehensive results.
- Use the Carnegie community engagement classification (currently used in the United States and Australia) to learn about community engagement in the Asia context and to build institutional support for community engagement globally? What are some key similarities and differences observed in how community engagement is operationalized, advanced, and institutionalised?
- Conduct meta-analyses and qualitative meta-synthesis to further evidence for service-learning and community engagement.
- Explore the use, benefits, and limitations of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning for research on service-learning and community engagement.
- Employ a three-phased assessment to study service-learning and community engagement that includes pre- (apply quantitative measure), during (apply case study), and post- (apply mixed methods case study).

IX. INSTRUMENTS AND MEASURES

Securing quality research requires valid and appropriate instruments and measures that can secure the best data and provide opportunities for thorough, systematic analyses. Many of the instruments that have been developed for the study of service-learning and community engagement are home grown instruments that are often applied to single studies and are not cultivated further for potential use in other studies. In addition, there are many instruments that are available for studies of service-learning and community engagement, but it is sometimes unclear regarding the suitability of such instruments for programs or populations for which they were not initially designed.

The research agenda identifies issues for improving the instrumentation and measurement of service-learning and community engagement across the many contexts in which the work takes place.

CAPTURING COMMUNITY IMPACT (MULTI-DIMENSIONAL LEVEL)

Develop and validate new types of instruments and measures that can be used to assess community impact from service-learning and community engagement.

- Develop and utilise scales that measure students' and teachers' levels of the empathy toward community and conduct studies that investigate whether that outcome is produced from service-learning experiences (both short- and long-term experiences).
- Develop instruments that can evaluate the impact of service-learning and community engagement on the community and the region, from the perspective of the community.
- Develop and test different measurement approaches and instruments (questionnaires, role playing, photovoice, observation, etc.) that can effectively capture the impact of service-learning on the community?
- Design and develop community assessment tools/inventories that can be used to capture the outcomes of short-term service-learning experience, such as international service-learning experiences where students and faculty spend a relatively short time in the community.

MULTI-PERSPECTIVE/MULTI-STAKEHOLDER EVALUATION/MEASUREMENT

Develop research instruments that consider the roles and perspectives of all participants (students, faculty, staff, institutions) engaged in the service-learning or community engagement experience.

- Develop a rubric incorporates both evaluation of individual growth and group development. Develop the rubric with input from students, teachers, and the community.
- For service-learning experiences that went well, put in place systems and mechanisms that capture what about the experience made it successful and impactful. What is the situation? Ask stakeholders to provide input and perspectives on their experiences.

MEASURING/EVALUATING STUDENT DEVELOPMENT (E.G., LIFE SKILLS, CAREER, CIVIC, LEADERSHIP) - LONGITUDINAL STUDIES

Develop and validate new instruments that measure different domains in student development, with an eye toward assessing transformational and long-term outcomes of service-learning and community engagement participation.

- Develop an instrument to measure the longitudinal change in students' civic learning.
- Develop a spiritual well-being measure and conduct studies to measure the impact of service-learning and community engagement on participants' spiritual well-being.
- Develop and validate a life skills assessment scale to investigate students' development of life skills through service-learning and community engagement.
- Develop and validate an instrument that measures digital leadership and utilise it to investigate online service-learners' ability to cope with digital transformation.

DEVELOPING MULTI-MODAL FRAMEWORKS/MEASUREMENTS FOR SERVICE-LEARNING/IMPACT

Explore the development of more multi-faceted, multi-modal approaches to instrument development and use those instruments to investigate unexplored issues pertaining to service-learning/community engagement sustainability, institutionalization, and partnership development.

- Develop a measure, instrument, or strategy that can evaluate and calibrate whether the service-learning partnership is truly a mutual partnership.
- Develop instruments designed to measure the quality of different kinds of partnerships.
- What are the measures that ensure sustainability and institutionalization of service-learning and community engagement within Asian contexts? Do the measures differ among communities in Asia? Are they the same as or different from the measures found in other parts of the globe?
- Develop instruments and approaches that can capture and measure the process and achievement of transformation, and the role that service-learning and community engagement may have played.
- Apply multi-media approaches to capturing the outcomes of service-learning and community engagement, such as (videos, photographs, social media posts, etc.).

X. REPLICATION

No one study provides all the evidence, understanding, or knowledge that is needed to draw firm conclusions about service-learning or community engagement. Replication is a critical feature of scientific inquiry and research.

Only a handful of service-learning and community engagement studies have been replicated. Replicating high quality studies is a way to strengthen evidence and secure more conclusive findings about the strengths and limitations of service-learning and community engagement practices, outcomes, and approaches.

REPLICATION APPROACHES AND STANDARDS

Establish regional guidance, standards, and protocols for conducting study replication in the Asian context.

- Develop a set of suggested methodological guidelines for quantitative, qualitative, mixed-methods, and meta-analytical designs that support the replicability of service-learning studies.
 - Recommend and/or develop some common instruments that can be applied to the same student to measure service-learning and community engagement phenomena across Asian contexts and communities.
 - Develop a list of well-designed research studies on service-learning and community engagement conducted in the Asian context that are prime for replication.
-

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**GLOBAL RESEARCH AGENDA FOR
SERVICE-LEARNING AND
COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT**

AUSTRALIA REGION

Global Research Agenda for Service-Learning and Community Engagement

AUSTRALIA Region

The content contained in this part of the global research agenda is based on an analysis of 275 research questions and items submitted by 39 individuals from the region who participated in a forum held virtually on May 13, 2025. The questions and items submitted during this forum were categorized and prioritized by 15 individuals from various institutions in Australia and the broader region who participated in two data analysis meetings held virtually on June 24, 2025 and July 8, 2025. The results of their analysis are presented in this part of the agenda report.

I. IMPACTS

Impact research focuses on assessing the impacts of service-learning and community engagement on participants, including students, faculty, staff, institutions and the community. They cross a broad range of short-term and long-term outcomes. This section of the agenda presents broad areas of impact to be investigated along with a particular set of themes within each impact area.

PARTNER OUTCOMES

Examine the benefits to partners and their communities that result from service-learning and community engagement. This includes examining how community engagement goals are set and how those match with the aspirations of partners. It also considers the return on investment for partners and communities as well.

- How do service-learning activities help the community on their long-term goals?
- How does an engaged curriculum lead to better outcomes for partners (research, industry, community organisations)?
- How can we minimise the time and financial commitment required of community partners to undertake community engaged research with universities, so that they get the most impact from the work (without it taking them away too much from their day-to-day

service provision in the community)? (Thinking about this from the perspective of also keeping the community partners as equal players alongside the university in the research activity).

- How does service-learning impact community awareness regarding public policy issues, and how do communities better engage with the process?

TRANSFORMATIONAL IMPACTS ON INSTITUTIONS

Measure the value of community engagement outcomes to the institutions involved and consider how involvement in community engagement partnerships has broader impacts on the institution's relationships with partners and other organisations. Questions under this category label highlight the ways in which community engagement can alter policy, practice, and reputation. This category also includes "return on investment" considerations – i.e. assessing the relationship between investment of resources and impact.

- How does service-learning contribute to advancing institution goals (for example: SDGs)?
- How can/how does community engagement deliver on a university's "social license"?
- What impact does service-learning/community engagement have on the willingness of government, NFP, corporates and other organisations to engage with universities, and how might it improve their perception of universities?
- How does service-learning shift community sentiment around universities?
- How can community-engaged learning programs address Australian national priorities (reconciliation with First Nations peoples, refugee support, etc.) whilst boosting public perceptions of alignment with university missions/values?

IMPACT ON TEACHING AND LEARNING

Examine how community engagement results in changes to teaching and learning in educational institutions, both in regard to professional practice and student experience.

- How does community engagement shift the idea of 'expertise' to models that allow for two-way learning?
- How can critical reflection be leveraged to promote transformational learning outcomes in service learning?

- How can the teaching and/or research experience of academic staff be improved by community engagement?
 - What pedagogical approaches best prepare community-engaged learning students to ethically and respectfully engage with vulnerable populations?
 - What models of service-learning delivery (e.g. embedded, co-curricular, intensive, virtual) are most effective across academic subjects and disciplines?
-

INCLUSIVE ASSESSMENT OF IMPACT

Include more partner voice in community engagement and service-learning research. Consider how multiple perspectives, including those of First Peoples, are part of our evaluation activities. Include assessments of how impact and the impact goals that are set at the start of a community partnership are defined.

- What is the impact of university-community engagement activities with First Nations peoples? What practices are effective in the Australian and New Zealand contexts?
 - How do we ensure that the interests of community partners and students are maintained in impact studies, including resource allocation to ensure equitable participation?
 - How is impact understood by the different participants involved in community engaged research and teaching practices.
 - How do community partners perceive their role and level of influence on service-learning outcomes?
 - How do community partners define "meaningful impact" from students undertaking community-engaged learning initiatives, and how does this differ from university-defined outcomes?
 - To what extent do students recognise and value the knowledge and expertise of community partners in comparison to academic knowledge?
 - Whose voice are heard and whose are unheard in the measurement of impact?
 - How does service-learning contribute to equity and inclusion outcomes for underserved student cohorts (e.g. First Nations, regional, neurodivergent)?
-

GRADUATE OUTCOMES

Examine the impact of community engagement and service-learning on students, and the skills and attributes that they take into their personal and professional lives following graduation. Focuses on how service-learning/community engagement influences students' values, civic identity, employability, cultural competency, and long-term transformation. Consider the effect of service-learning/community engagement on graduate profile and others' perception of graduates who have undertaken service-learning/community engagement.

- How do we ensure we are developing graduates who are committed to the actions and responsibilities of a professional and global citizen?
- How does service-learning lead to more culturally capable and connected students?
- How do service-learning activities impact civic responsibility of students who participate?
- How is transformational learning identified and measured in students participating in service-learning experiences?
- What impact does service-learning and community engagement have on the immediate, mid-term and longer-term employment types and outcomes for students?
- What is the longitudinal impact of community engagement on students in the longer term?
- How do we develop service-learning and community engagement opportunities that contribute to potential long-term employment for students?

IMPACT METRICS AND REPORTING OF OUTCOMES

Identify measures that can be used to assess impact, including the way/s impact emerges from the outcomes of community engagement and service-learning and how that may differ across contexts.

- How do we measure the 'quality' of community engagement and its correlation with impact?
- How can the longer-term engagement/impact of community engagement/service-learning on communities, stakeholders, students and staff be measured beyond publications?
- What conventions there for measuring impact?
- How can we best share the results of community engaged research studies with the broader community in accessible formats, to increase the impact of our work outside of academia, especially in contexts where academic publications are valued by university managements?

- How can the scholarly communication of engaged research and practice better support or make visible the goals of community-based partners?
 - How is transformational learning identified and measured in students participating in service-learning experiences?
 - What measures can be used to assess impact, including the way/s impact emerges from the outcomes of community engagement and service-learning and how that may differ across contexts?
-

SOCIETAL OUTCOMES

Examine the benefits and contributions of service-learning and community engagement to broader societal outcomes.

- How does service-learning contribute to the social and economic prosperity of communities in which a university operates?
- How does service-learning contribute to building trust with communities?
- What is the evidence of Social Returns on Investment from our university-community engagement?

II. IMPLEMENTATION

Implementation research focuses on examining the practices of service-learning and community engagement and the ways in which these practices are effective in achieving particular goals. Implementation studies seek to improve practice and provide guidance on best practices across a broad range of service-learning and community engagement programmatic approaches.

The research agenda identifies questions that centre on the process of delivering service-learning and community engagement across a broad range of community, cultural, geographic, disciplinary, and institutional contexts.

RECIPROCAL, ETHICAL, AND SUSTAINABLE COMMUNITY-ENGAGED PARTNERSHIPS

Conduct research that examines best practices for building community-engaged partnerships that are ethical, truly reciprocal, and consider the planning for, and commitment to sustainability and/or legacy where partnerships naturally conclude. The research should focus on two subthemes:

Building reciprocal and ethical community-engaged partnerships. Examine the practice of reciprocal partnerships from both pragmatic and ethical standpoints.

- What implementation approaches effectively transition community partnerships from transactional to transformational relationships over time?
- What is the "best practice" for co-design with multiple stakeholders, students, staff and communities to ensure sustainability, equity and equality?
- What kinds of approaches to often rigid university structures (around teaching, e.g.) work best to enable effective responses to community identified projects and needs (that may have very different timelines)?

Ensuring sustainability and legacy in community-engaged partnerships. Examine how community-engaged partnerships can be sustained over time and continue moving forward in response to further developments (i.e., not standing still). Sustainability planning should be wary of, and account for personnel and funding changes in the partnership. How can the partnership navigate change? It is acknowledged that partnerships naturally change, and in some cases conclude, so an intentional and ethical approach to legacy planning should be a part of community-engaged partnerships. There is a need to ensure the community is not left out cold when a project is over.

- What are best practices for ensuring the legacy of a partnership? How can a relationship be ongoing and open to future possibilities?
- What are best practices for sustaining the community partnerships and support from university on an ongoing basis for service-learning activities?

- How do we best prepare, mentor and continue to develop staff to create effective and impactful community engagement and service-learning programs?
 - What happens when service-learning projects conclude? How do we build workable structures to continue to engage with partners after the road show leaves town? And what are the implications for community partners if we do not?
 - What can (still) be done in university-community engagement when funding is gone from one/both sides, and staffing is reduced in one/both sides?
 - What is the 'natural history' of a university-community partnership? Borrowing from the natural history of diseases, this is a qualitative research question about what typically happens with a university-community partnership.
-

SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY-ENGAGED PEDAGOGY AND CURRICULUM DESIGN

Conduct research that examines the planning and implementation of service-learning and community engagement curricula, encompassing the subject level, the whole curriculum, and the whole university.

- What preparation and post-implementation activities are important for students and stakeholders to maximise the learning and outcomes?
 - How can community engagement be effectively scaffolded throughout an undergraduate program to prepare students for meaningful partnerships with community organisations in their final years of study?
 - How do we find commonality in service-learning/community engagement implementation when different regulatory bodies exert different power over the curriculum in service-learning/community engagement?
 - How can community-engaged learning be systematically embedded across the university within its structural bounds while maintaining flexibility for community responsiveness?
 - What program design strategies effectively support sustainable community engagement without overloading individual course coordinators?
-

CROSS-NATIONAL, INTERNATIONAL, AND INTER-INSTITUTIONAL COLLABORATION

Investigate the nature of collaboration across institutional, national, and international contexts to implement community-engagement and service-learning. What opportunities are there for universities and communities?

- What are effective strategies for furthering cross-institutional collaboration in the implementation of community engagement and service-learning?
 - What are best practices for international collaborators to work together to build the global implementation of community engagement and service-learning programs across countries?
-

UNIVERSITY-COMMUNITY ENGAGED PARTNERSHIPS AND CROSS-CULTURAL UNDERSTANDING

Advance the study of community engagement and service-learning as it relates to cultural diversity in Australia and New Zealand. In addition to exploring and understanding what best practice community engagement and service learning with indigenous communities is, conduct research that focuses on how community engagement and service-learning is best undertaken with the wide range of cultural communities in our nations.

- What is best practice university-community engagement with First Nations communities in Australia and New Zealand?
- How do varying cultural understandings of "service" and "reciprocity" shape the implementation of programs across diverse Australian communities?

III. INSTITUTIONALISATION

Institutionalization research focuses on examining the factors that promote the sustainability and institutionalization of service-learning and community engagement across institutional and community contexts.

Studies in this area seek to conceptualize the idea of institutionalization in light of the changing contexts of educational institutions and the varied approaches to service-learning and community engagement.

STRUCTURAL FACTORS

Conduct research on the structural factors that impact on the sustainable institutionalisation of service-learning and community engagement.

- What are the best practices in reward and recognition for all sides in university-community engagement?
- What workload allowance is given to university academic and professional staff (in US terminology = faculty and staff) for community engagement works? Is it sufficient? How can it be increased?
- What are best practices for creating support structures, such as research ethics committees, and resources for the (real and/or perceived) additional work around service-learning that often is not credited in academic workload and/or supported in other ways?
- What is the longer-term impact of institutionalization on the promotion and recognition of staff and students?
- How do we appropriately scale a university's community engagement activities to ensure they are being done with quality and ethics at the forefront? In many cases, universities struggle to find the right balance between having a large number (i.e., a diverse range) of activities (to show a broader impact) with appropriate resourcing of activities to ensure quality.

INSTITUTIONAL LEADERSHIP

Investigate strategies and mission for university leadership to ensure that community engagement and service-learning become and remain core institutional practices and are less susceptible to 'winds of change'.

- What are effective strategies for convincing 'people at the top' of the value that community engagement and service-learning work has for students and community partners, as well as for the university and its goals, such that they will take responsibility for considering ways to make the work in this space sustainable and 'put their money where their mouth

is', or at least take the time to find out more about what is working well in existing programs (especially as threats of funding cuts and program loss loom)?

- How can institutionalisation efforts be guarded against/become more resilient to internal leadership changes?
 - To what extent does Australian Higher Education leadership understand service-learning and community engagement 'competence'?
 - What are effective strategies for helping university leaders understand that community engagement with populations experiencing vulnerability is more time consuming in a range of ways, and that outcomes will take longer to achieve?
 - How do successful programs navigate leadership transitions in both university and community partner organisations?
-

BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLES AROUND THE WORLD

Study and draw from lessons learned from across the region and around the globe regarding best practices for institutionalising community engagement and service-learning?

- Where is institutionalisation of community engagement happening across Australia and New Zealand and what does it look like?
 - What are the best practices in shifting community engagement from individual-to-individual to institution-to-institution? This is crucial when staff turnover is high on either side.
 - What are the best practices of succession in community engagement leadership?
 - What is the best model of institutionalisation: a centralised approach (e.g. a specialist directorate leads and coordinates it all), a decentralised approach, a leadership model (Schools and Faculties determine their own way of meeting a centrally determined agenda), or a hybrid approach?
 - What are best practices for furthering the institutionalisation of community engagement and service-learning in heavily vocational, risk averse, large cohort and (in some instances) multi-campus universities?
-

COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT AND THE PURPOSES OF A UNIVERSITY

Following John Henry Newman's ideas around the purpose of a liberal university, future research should query the purpose(s) of a university and implications for community engagement and how community engagement is defined and operationalised.

- How are universities in Australia and New Zealand defining community engagement?
 - How do academics in Australia perceive their role in facilitating community engagement and service-learning?
 - How do external and internal stakeholders affect the institutionalisation of service-learning and community engagement?
 - What is the influence of universities' global identities in education or position in research on the institutionalisation process in Australian universities?
 - What is the 'true' level of institutional commitment to community engagement beyond what is formally written and said in public?
-

GOVERNMENT FACTORS THAT AFFECT INSTITUTIONALISATION

Explore local and national government priorities pertaining to community engagement.

- How does Australia's government funding structure and higher education affect institutionalised community engagement/service-learning?
 - What is the influence of governments both local and national on the institutionalisation process, especially for multi-campus universities?
 - What are effective strategies for linking the institutionalisation of community engagement and service-learning to government and university objectives (given that many Aussie universities are government funded)?
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IV. COVID/POST-COVID

Questions and issues that explore service-learning and community engagement practices during and beyond COVID.

The issues include, but are not limited to:

- new emerging practices for service-learning and community engagement results from the pandemic.
- changes regarding the conduct of service-learning and community engagement research due to COVID.
- impact of COVID on the quality of service-learning and community engagement; and
- advantages and disadvantages of conducting service-learning and community engagement during or after COVID.

SERVICE-LEARNING AND SUPPORT OF COMMUNITY DURING CRISIS

Examine how service-learning programs adapt to uncertain times.

- What role can service-learning play in supporting community needs during crisis situations, alongside or in place of traditional volunteer roles?
 - What role can service-learning play in preparing students for uncertain, disrupted, or post-pandemic work futures?
 - How did community organisations adapt to the loss of student volunteers and university resources? How did universities adapt to the loss of student placement opportunities in community partnerships?
-

TECHNOLOGICAL CAPACITY OF PARTNER

Examine the unequal distribution of technology resources between universities and community partners and ask how these inequities can be addressed to get the most out of partnerships.

- What are effective strategies to get universities to recognise and address the imbalance of power related to technological capacity of community partners?
 - How can universities partner with community groups to co-identify and co-resolve technological challenges in service delivery?
 - What support structures best address technological inequities among community organisations seeking to partner in online programs?
-

COLLABORATION AND CO-DESIGN FOR CRISIS

This is an exploratory theme that recommends conducting studies that consider the possibility of future disruption across the globe and how we can work with community partners to shield against this.

- How can universities and community partners collaboratively prepare for the next disruption to our world? What is the role of service-learning and community engagement in this effort?
-

VIRTUAL/HYBRID SERVICE-LEARNING DELIVERY

Investigate the opportunities and limitations in conducting hybrid service-learning experiences, including a documentation of how educational institutions adapted to an unexpected shift to online service-learning experiences.

- What are the ethical and practice concerns that arise from online and hybrid service-learning delivery? What elements of service-learning ought to remain in-person?
 - What are effective means of hybrid and online service-learning? What technological platforms and digital tools best facilitate authentic relationship-building between online students and community partners?
 - How did institutions adapt service-learning to virtual or socially distanced environments? And how effective are these hybrid models of service-learning?
-

VIRTUAL/HYBRID/NON-CONVENTIONAL SERVICE-LEARNING IMPACT

Examine the impact of hybrid service-learning on the learning outcomes of students.

- Do students undertaking online community engagement have similar outcomes in learning to those undertaking face to face (in-person in the community)?
 - What is the value and potential of 'online only' communities in university-community engagement and service-learning?
 - What was the impact of telehealth in community engagement/service-learning in building community and empathy in health professional students?
 - How do synchronous versus asynchronous community-engaged learning activities differ in their impact on both student learning and community benefit?
-

COVID LESSONS INSTITUTIONALISATION

Investigate the lessons learned during COVID and the effects, including financial, that this had on how institutions delivered service-learning and community engagement.

- What factors enabled universities to pivot and adapt their community engagement/service-learning programs in the face of COVID?
 - What can we learn from programs that have been able to 'weather storms' such as COVID?
 - How do financial costs compare between in-person community engagement/service-learning and online only community engagement/service-learning? What is the impact of this difference on the community partners, students, and the institution?
-

COVID INNOVATIONS

Investigate the lessons learned through COVID and how they may be applied to any future global disruptions.

- What innovations driven by COVID have remained valuable to partnerships post pandemic?
- What are the new and emerging community engagement formats since the COVID pandemic began? (This is suggested as a scoping review.)
- What is the impact of virtual engagement with community partners during or after COVID? Did it strengthen the relationship/engagement with them?
- During COVID, what community engagement/service-learning activities facilitate the development of sustainable online resources and databases of online resources/toolkits that could be shared, and how?

V. EQUITY AND SOCIAL ADVANCEMENT

Research in this area focuses on issues that explore the role of equity in service-learning and community engagement practices within and across cultures, populations, and regions. The issues include, but are not limited to, implications for conducting equity-focused research within and across different groups, populations, communities, and/or cultures.

CONCEPTUALISING EQUITY AND SOCIAL ADVANCEMENT IN SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

Explore the basic concepts of equity and social advancement, thus laying the foundation for all other research questions in this section.

- What does social advancement look like to universities versus the individual, the student, the community and the stakeholders?
- How do we measure social advancement and true equity in community engagement and service-learning?
- How can community engagement support/promote equity objectives in rural communities?
- What are the differences between the understanding of equity and social advancement concepts between rural and urban communities?
- What are the differences between the understanding of equity and social advancement concepts between students from rural and urban regions?

SERVICE-LEARNING/COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT EQUITY AND ITS IMPACTS ON STUDENTS

Investigate how service-learning is designed and executed as a pedagogy and how it impacts on students' equity.

- How do service-learning initiatives align with, or differ from, equity and social advancement?
- How can we leverage Open Education Resources to improve equity and contribute towards social advancement? <https://www.caul.edu.au/services-programs/OER-Collective>
- How should the service-learning curricula reflect an understanding and representation of equity "from within", recognising the participation and contribution of what are often considered "equity groups" in the learning spaces?

- What do students think about compulsory community engagement elements in their curriculum? Does that approach put them at a disadvantage?
- What community engagement/service-learning models are equitable, with the same level of learning, for students who experience placement poverty?
- What strategies can we adopt that service-learning does not reinforce the existing social hierarchy but empowers under-represented groups?
- How do community-engaged learning programs challenge deficit-based approaches when working with communities?

SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT IN THE FIRST NATIONS CONTEXT

Explore the principles and practical ways for ethical and strength-based service-learning and community engagement with First Nations peoples.

- How do community-engaged learning programs address the historical context of institutional harm by religious organisations toward Aboriginal communities?
- How can community-engaged learning partnerships with First Nations communities centre Indigenous knowledge systems and self-determination principles?
- How do we support growth in community engaged research with First Nations communities, through supporting, mentoring, training, etc. for First Nations students and academics to take leading roles?
- How can we best ensure that benefits for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander communities/organisations continue beyond the life of the project/agreement when they enter into partnerships with universities?

CULTURAL SAFETY

Examine cultural safety for both the students and the communities in which they are placed in service-learning and community engagement. Universities are often focused on training students (especially in the health and social care professions) to be culturally safe for their future clients or patients, but the cultural risks for the students during placements in the communities are often overlooked.

NOTE: In some Australian circles, the term 'cultural safety' is often discussed in relation to the First Nations context, to some extreme situations where cultural safety is only discussed in that way. We deliberately separate this theme of cultural safety from the other theme of service-learning/community engagement in the First Nations context to emphasise that cultural safety is crucially needed whenever two or more cultures meet, including encounters outside the First Nations context.

- How much work is done on cultural safe practices, inclusion, etc. before student placement?
 - What do community organisations need to do further on preparing students for cultural safe practices, inclusion etc. before community placements?
 - How do we balance between the community's and the students' cultural safety in community placements, ensuring both sides are safe in cross-cultural encounters?
-

EXPANDING THE SCOPE OF SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

Explore how equity and social advancement can be built into non-curricular service-learning and community engagement.

- How can universities, communities, stakeholders and students make an equitable contribution to social enhancement and not just via enrolment and completion of courses?
- How can universities' widening of participation and equity practices be truly community engaged and informed?

VI. CULTURAL/REGIONAL AND CROSS-CULTURAL/CROSS-REGIONAL

Issues that explore service-learning and community engagement practices within and across cultures and regions are to be embraced and discussed, with an eye toward identifying questions or action steps for the research agenda.

The research issues include, but is not limited to:

- conducting research within and across different cultural or geographic settings;
- examining service-learning and community engagement across the educational spectrum;
- community voice;
- multiple frames of service-learning and community engagement.

STUDENT PREPARATION FOR CULTURALLY DIVERSITY COMMUNITIES

Conduct research studies that explore the preparation of students for community-engaged learning/service-learning in environments involving culturally diverse communities, including the preparation for both domestic and international experiences and the development of cultural humility.

- How do we appropriately and effectively prepare students for the environments they will enter into, especially where there are different cultural norms, etc.?
- How do we develop cultural humility in students? By cultural humility, we mean entering a partnership with another person with the intention of honouring their beliefs, customs, and values, and being able to self-reflect and self-critique.
- What are the key elements of effective cross-cultural preparation for students participating in community-based global learning programs?

COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT, SERVICE-LEARNING, AND CULTURAL SAFETY

Examine students' cultural safety in community engagement and service-learning settings. Consider culture from the viewpoint of ethnicity, religion/spirituality, disability, sexual and gender identity, and other forms of social identity.

- What are the challenges in managing students from different cultures and/or home environments when participating in community engagement/service-learning?
- How can we best prepare communities to provide safe environments for students from minoritized groups (e.g., ethnic, religions/spirituality, LGBTQ+, disability, and other groups)?
- What are the challenges when working with different gender/affiliation and aged individuals and when working with individuals or communities with cross-cultural values?

- What are the barriers and facilitators for students with different additional needs when engaging in cross cultural and/or cross regional community engagement/service-learning?

BEST PRACTICE AND THE ETHICS OF CROSS-CULTURAL AND CROSS-REGIONAL COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT AND SERVICE-LEARNING

Conduct studies that help identify the best practices of cross-cultural and cross-regional community engagement and service-learning and how cross-cultural/cross-regional community engagement and service-learning can be enacted with due consideration of ethical challenges and opportunities.

- What are the commonalities of successful long-term cross-cultural and cross-regional community engagement and service-learning experiences/programs?
- What are the ways to inculcate the strengths-based paradigm rather than the deficit lens in cross-cultural and cross-regional community engagement?
- What is the potential for people, groups, communities with lived experience to enhance cross-cultural and cross-regional community engagement and service-learning?
- What are the best practices for conducting university-community engagement and service-learning with regional and remote communities? How do we consider and address barriers to engaging with remote communities?
- What precautions are needed to prevent extractive, 'Santa Claus', 'saviour's complex', utilitarian, or other negative models of international community engagement, especially from Global North universities to Global South countries?

BEST PRACTICE AND THE ETHICS OF CROSS-CULTURAL AND CROSS-REGIONAL COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT AND SERVICE-LEARNING

Conduct comparative research on community engagement and service-learning across cultures and regions with a focus on unpacking best practices and ethics considerations.

- What considerations/investigations/activities should a university undertake before engaging in cross-cultural research/international research to ensure the research is done carefully, ethically and without causing more harm?
- What are the commonalities and differences between K12-level (school-level) versus university-level community engagement/service-learning placement?

- How does the focus of community partners in regional areas differ from those in metropolitan areas in service-learning courses?
- How do students from metropolitan areas differ from students from rural areas in their motivations for service-learning activities?
- What are the shared foundations upon which to conduct comparative research into service-learning and community engagement in different contexts?

VII. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORKS AND THEORIES

The field of service-learning and community engagement has been criticized for being under-theorized and for lacking well-developed and well-tested conceptual frameworks.

Research in this area of work focuses on theory testing and building conceptual models and frameworks that explain various phenomena in the study and practice of service-learning and community engagement.

APPLYING EXISTING THEORIES TO COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT AND SERVICE-LEARNING

Investigate the applicability of conceptual frameworks and theories from other disciplines to the study of community engagement and service-learning.

- How do we best engage marginalised voices and develop critical pedagogy through collective case studies (long-term investment in ongoing relationships) and participatory action research?
 - How can service-learning be a vehicle for social justice through codesign?
 - What theoretical frameworks from business and economics might be useful lenses to consider the value and challenges of university-community engagement?
 - Which frameworks from Health Professional Education and specifically Medical Education may be applicable for service-learning and community engagement?
 - What theoretical frameworks from psychology, sociology, anthropology, etc. can inform and support community engagement and service-learning research?
 - What conceptual frameworks help navigate tensions between Catholic values (or other religiously-based values) and culturally specific community priorities?
 - What conceptual models effectively articulate the relationship between personal transformation and systemic change in service-learning contexts?
 - What conceptual frameworks help faculty and students recognise and navigate inherent power imbalances between universities and communities?
-

DEFINING COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT AND SERVICE-LEARNING

Investigates the parameters of community engagement/service-learning and what key concepts should be included in the frameworks and how those are defined.

- What are effective practices for incorporating each of the many different aspects of learning (personal, professional, cultural, technical, ethical/moral, civic) in service-learning and community engagement activities for students?
 - How do service-learning partnerships uphold or challenge principles of fairness and mutual benefit (reciprocity, anti-colonial, anti-extractive)?
-

THEORETICAL TOOLS AND APPROACHES TO COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT AND SERVICE-LEARNING

Explore, develop, and test the tools and approaches needed to address the service-learning and community engagement-focused research questions.

- How do diverse frameworks and theory fit in community engagement/service-learning transdisciplinary research?
 - What metaphors do people use in their service-learning and community engagement work? (These can be powerful tools for dialogue and bridge building.)
-

DISSEMINATION OF COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT AND SERVICE-LEARNING RESEARCH

Explore avenues to optimize the dissemination of new research studies in the field.

- What action steps should be taken to ensure that are cross-disciplinary journals or publication opportunities for new frames of community engagement/service-learning research to be published? Will IARSLCE journal provide this space? This is an example of a journal that accepts all forms of submission <https://herdsa.org.au/advancing-scholarship-and-research-higher-education-asrhe>.
- What are current journals that are prime for publishing new frames of service-learning/community engagement research? One option may be the *International Journal of Work-Integrated Learning* (IJWIL).

VIII. METHODOLOGICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The issues in this section focus on identifying the kinds of methods that are appropriate for the study of service-learning and community engagement. The items consider the research designs, methods, epistemologies and approaches that are needed and required in designing and operationalizing future research on service-learning and community engagement.

BEST PRACTICES IN SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

Explore and crystallise best practices of service-learning and community engagement research methodologies.

- What are the best practices in service-learning and community engagement research methodology?
- What are the best practices in sharing service-learning and community engagement research methodologies?
- What should be the common standards for evaluating outcomes and impacts of university-community engagement and service-learning?
- What minimal set of potential and actual confounders must be measured and controlled for in measuring community engagement impacts?
- How do we build sufficient flexibility into service-learning and community engagement research to embrace the local context of each community?
- What are the factors which determine the methodological choices in service-learning and community engagement research?
- What are the roles and importance of mixed-methods research in service-learning and community engagement research?

POTENTIAL METHODS FOR SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT RESEARCH

Explore diverse potential research methods for conducting research on service-learning and community engagement.

- What roles can Grounded Theory play in service-learning/community engagement research?
- What opportunities are there for ethnographic research in university-community engagement?

- What roles can AI play in future community engagement/service-learning research designs?
- How might explorations of Indigenous pedagogies in service-learning/community engagement models in higher education inform learning?
- What roles can simulation play in preparing students and staff for community engagement and service-learning and interactions with people and culture different to their own current experience?
- What are other ways of evaluating service-learning and community engagement student outcomes beyond self-reflection/assessment?
- Which Social Returns on Investment (SROI) method is the most appropriate for service learning and community engagement, especially since many SROI methods are very expensive?

RIGOUR IN SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT RESEARCH

Explore more fully how rigour can and should be established, given that service-learning and community engagement research may be seen as 'soft' or as 'nontraditional' research.

- How do we establish and strengthen transparency and rigour in service-learning and community engagement research?
- How can we assert within institutions with expectations around rigour that difference in method or epistemology is not the same as deficient?

ETHICAL SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT RESEARCH

Explore the avenues that can ensure that service-learning and community engagement research is ethically designed and conducted.

- How do we partner with community organisations to design mutually beneficial and contextually-considered research projects?
- How can we appropriately mentor community partners to feel supported as equal partners as they engage in research activities with universities?
- How do we maintain the power balance while training community partners in research methodologies, where our biases are likely to seep in?

- What are the ethical aspects pertinent to researching issues abroad in international service-learning/community engagement, which is sometimes done from afar?
- How can we ensure international service-learning/community engagement research is done safely, with reciprocal partnerships with communities and organisations in the country abroad?
- What protocols can be developed to ensure Indigenous communities are at the forefront of consideration in planning implementation and to ensure that there are appropriate disaggregating analyses of data?
- How can Indigenous research methodologies feature, and appropriate resourcing be secured and made available for, Indigenous community members and hosts?
- How can we decolonise methodologies in order to respect community timeframes and cultural protocols rather than academic calendars and institutional requirements?

IX. INSTRUMENTS AND MEASURES

Securing quality research requires valid and appropriate instruments and measures that can secure the best data and provide opportunities for thorough, systematic analyses. Many of the instruments that have been developed for the study of service-learning and community engagement are home grown instruments that are often applied to single studies and are not cultivated further for potential use in other studies. In addition, there are many instruments that are available for studies of service-learning and community engagement, but it is sometimes unclear regarding the suitability of such instruments for programs or populations for which they were not initially designed.

The research agenda identifies issues for improving the instrumentation and measurement of service-learning and community engagement across the many contexts in which the work takes place.

SUITABILITY OF EXISTING INSTRUMENTS

Advance the application of instruments and measures developed outside the community engagement/service-learning field to measure the impact of community engagement/service-learning activities.

- What instruments and measures can be used for research on community engagement/service-learning?
- What considerations need to be taken into account to ensure that global frameworks do not overshadow local priorities and context?
- How do we use the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) Impact Assessment Tool in SL/CE?
- How can the Furco Service-Learning Institutionalisation Rubric be used in the Australian context?
- What tools are available to support the evaluation of student learning in community engagement? What is the quality of these tools?

CONTEXT-APPROPRIATE INSTRUMENTS AND MEASURES

Conduct an assessment of what kinds of instruments/measures are needed for conducting research in specific contexts (e.g. faith-based, alumni groups, particular countries). Develop a strategy for deepening understanding of how definitions of impact may be adjusted or developed to fit specific contexts and how the definition(s) of impact affect the instruments/measures we need and use.

- What context frameworks, measures, and instruments can be designed specifically for issues relevant to conducting service-learning and community engagement in the Australian region (e.g., "closing the gap" indicators, etc.)?
- What is the definition of service-learning success? What strategies can be used to measure that success, perhaps through the co-designing of evaluation tools with students and/or community partners?
- How can we use Kolb's learning journals, Kiely's transformational learning Rubric, Campus Compact Service-Learning Assessment Matrix, and narrative interviews in various Australian service-learning and community engagement contexts?
- What measures and instruments are able to assess the impact of campus ministry or ministry counselling during and after community engagement/service-learning placements?
- What instruments or measures can further the understanding of the enduring impact of community engagement/service-learning on alumni?
- How do we collaboratively evaluate service-learning/community engagement projects/programs from student and community/other perspectives?

DEVELOP VALID INSTRUMENTS AND MEASURES

Examine how and what kinds of instruments and measures could be developed and identify the sorts of available resources/data that can be drawn on to develop them.

- How can we best use public data as measures from government websites, artificial intelligence (AI), and other under-utilized resources to conduct deep data dives in service-learning and community engagement research?
- How do we establish and strengthened the validity of university-run debrief/focus groups sessions for staff and students during and at the end of each semester of community engagement/service-learning placements for capturing impact?
- What is best practice for impact evaluation frameworks that measure the system-wide impacts of university community engagement activity?
- What are valid instruments for measuring transformational learning of students who participate in service-learning and community engagement experiences?
- How can we measure the benefit to community organisations of the community engagement work we do?

X. REPLICATION

No one study provides all the evidence, understanding, or knowledge that is needed to draw firm conclusions about service-learning or community engagement. Replication is a critical feature of scientific inquiry and research.

Only a handful of service-learning and community engagement studies have been replicated. Replicating high quality studies is a way to strengthen evidence and secure more conclusive findings about the strengths and limitations of service-learning and community engagement practices, outcomes, and approaches.

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO REPLICATION RESEARCH

Gather already existing methodologies for replication studies from other fields, in order to encourage these sorts of studies in community engagement and service-learning. Such studies, however, may not fully capture cultural or contextual issues.

- How can we advance the rigor (qualitative, quantitative, or mixed methods) of community engagement and service-learning studies to encourage and/or enable meta-analytic and meta-synthesis approaches?
- What are the conceptual, cultural and methodological considerations of utilising an approach such as ‘replication’ which stems from a positivist scientific paradigm?
- What opportunities are there for qualitative meta-synthesis to drive forward knowledge in the field? How do we structure our qualitative work to support meta-synthesis?
- What are the alternatives or complementary approaches to meta-analysis or traditional research studies in community engagement and service-learning?
- What language and cultural practices do we need so that replication better reflects the values and principles of community engagement?

METHODOLOGICAL ALTERNATIVES TO CONVENTIONAL REPLICATION RESEARCH

Advance non-scientific but equally valid methodologies for undertaking replication research.

- Weave First Peoples’ knowledge into a university course | The Australian Journal of Indigenous Education | Cambridge Core.
- Apply learnings from the article “Practical Aspects of Service Learning Make Work-Integrated Learning Wise Practice for Inclusive Education in Australia”, International Journal of Work-Integrated Learning, 2019. ERIC - EJ1206987 -

- Create a fourth space for social impact collaborations across boundaries (e.g., active project-based learning and internships for GC education).
-

PURPOSE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF REPLICATION RESEARCH

Establish a clear rationale, sense of purpose, and understanding of contextual and cultural considerations in order to see more replication studies in service-learning research and community-engaged scholarship.

- How can the field encourage strategic replication of studies where it makes sense? (and not, where it does not make sense)?
- How do longitudinal studies contribute to replication research in service-learning and community engagement?
- In some disciplines, the reporting of experiments that did not achieve the results anticipated or hoped for is encouraged to deepen understanding of processes, particularly complex ones. What is the best place for that approach in community engagement?

CONTRIBUTORS

Forum Participants

VIRTUAL MEETING (May 14, 2025)

Hosted by the Engagement Australia

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**GLOBAL RESEARCH AGENDA FOR
SERVICE-LEARNING AND
COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT**

EUROPE REGION

Global Research Agenda for Service-Learning and Community Engagement

EUROPE Region

The content contained in this part of the global research agenda is based on an analysis of 508 research questions and items submitted by 65 individuals who participated in five forums held in Europe between September 2019 and September 2023. While these forums were held in Europe, two of them included individuals from other regions. The questions and items were categorized and prioritized by 24 service-learning and community engagement scholars, researchers, and practitioners from across Europe who participated in a two-day data analysis meeting held in Antwerp, Belgium, November 21-22, 2024. The results of their analyses and discussions are presented here.

I. IMPACTS

Impact research focuses on assessing the impacts of service-learning and community engagement on participants, including students, faculty, staff, educational institutions, and the community partners and organisations. They cross a broad range of short-term and long-term outcomes. This section of the agenda presents broad areas of impact to be investigated along with a particular set of themes within each impact area.

IMPACT OF THE ORGANIZATION AND INSTITUTION

Investigate the impact that institutional policies, organizations, and practices have on the advancement and institutionalisation of high-quality service-learning and community engagement.

Flexibility of the Curriculum

- Does today's service-learning impact how the study programme(s) will be (re)designed for the future generation(s) of students?
- What is the "added value" of using 'University Modules' that include service-learning to complement learning in higher education? There may be an appetite/interest now (e.g., student interest in supporting/contributing to community, service-learning filling a gap

exposed by limited 'face to face' learning going forward.)

- How can faculties and schools become more connected to real-life learning and teach real life skills through service-learning?

Measurement

- What can we learn about the long-term effects of service-learning and community engagement participation?
- What are best practices for building long-term alliances with community partners?
- How do community-engaged learning and service-learning enable the delivery of the education strategy and other key institutional strategies?

Mission Oriented Leaders

- What are indicators of interconnectedness between partners?
- What can systematic, larger scale, and integrated studies that go beyond particular experiences tell us about the role of mission-oriented leaders and the ways such leaders support/do not support service-learning and community engagement?

Strategic Institutional Development

- What are the non-profit, private, non-governmental organizations, and government sectors that are most influential and important in furthering the impact of service-learning and community engagement?
- How can an institution engage its staff in service-learning and community engagement and what is the impact on their professional development?

IMPACT ON COMMUNITY

Investigate the short-term and long-term impact of service-learning and community engagement on communities and how to sustain service-learning and community engagement to optimize positive community impact.

Inequalities and Subjective Perceptions of Inequality

- Does service-learning and community engagement have any impact on reducing the gender pay gap in the community??
- What is the ripple effect of service-learning on unemployment and in developing socially and environmentally committed entrepreneurship?

Immediate, Short, Medium and Long-term Impact

- What long-term changes are notable within partner organisations?
- What is the long-term impact of service-learning on community partners in the context of organisational professionalization? Is service-learning a driving force of organizational professionalisation for community partners?

Community Organizational Sustainability and Mission Alignment

- How do service-learning and community engagement enable communities to further their mission and goals?

IMPACT ON ACADEMIC AND EDUCATIONAL STAFF

Investigate the ways in which involvement in service-learning and community engagement impact the skills, knowledge, and professional trajectories of academic staff.

Transformative Professional Development

- What is the impact on teachers/professors and/or researchers who initiative service-learning or community engagement projects?
- Does service-learning increase the satisfaction of primary and secondary school educators with their profession?
- How can an institution engage its staff in this kind of projects?
- What is the impact on staff members' professional development?

Inclusive Learning Experience Design (Knowledge and Skills)

- How does an interdisciplinary setting of service-learning and community engagement impact actors/participants?
- Does service-learning make the curriculum more relevant, contemporary, and pertinent to the issues of today?
- What are the similarities and differences in impact from participation in traditional in-person service-learning courses and hybrid e-Service-learning courses?

Subjective Well-Being

- Service-learning is risky - it can and does fail. It is also very demanding, requiring a lot of emotional labour. What impact does service-learning have on teaching staff who participate in it?
- To what extent does participation in service-learning experiences contribute to the development of solidarity-based subjectivity and agency (e.g., the capacity to be subjects in research)?
- What is the impact of service-learning on facilitators' (faculty, staff) mental health or well-being?

IMPACT ON STUDENTS

Investigate the ways in which participation in service-learning and community engagement impact students' academic, personal, civic, professional, and social skills and attitudes.

Academic Engagement

- How can service-learning and community engagement projects provide a more transformative learning experience?
- What is the tangible legacy of service-learning and community engagement experiences on students in the context of the behavioural domain?
- What are the long-term behaviour changes on students who participate in service-learning and community engagement?

Transversal Skills and Values

- What is the impact of Service-Learning in primary and secondary school democratic competences of students (using the European Union Reference Framework for Competences for Democratic Culture model)?
- How can service-learning help students to broaden their horizons to boost their soft skills and interpersonal competencies?
- On the long-term, how do service-learning and community engagement participation influence the likelihood of former students to engage in politics/civil society?
- Does participation in service-learning and community engagement influence students' values?

- What is the influence of service-learning and community engagement on “how to live your life”? Does service-learning and community engagement participation have an impact on students’ life philosophy?

Professional Profile

- How can service-learning and community engagement develop students’ graduate identity?
- In regard to balancing future practice, do service-learning and community engagement activities in higher education (and social sciences in particular) enhance the practice of graduates when they take up employment in voluntary/public sector jobs working with disadvantaged communities? Do these service-learning and community engagement opportunities lead to more inclusive and reflective practitioners?
- What is the impact of service-learning and community engagement on students’ employability and their employment and transversal skills?
- Are there gender differences in the development of students’ employability and transversal skills?

Inequalities and Subjective Perceptions

- Instead of asking students (especially students from disadvantaged backgrounds) to volunteer or engage in service-learning, how does bringing service-learning and community engagement into the curriculum affect students’ interest in participating and in their overall experience and development from the experience? from disadvantaged backgrounds?

II. IMPLEMENTATION

Implementation research focuses on examining the practices of service-learning and community engagement and the ways in which these practices are effective in achieving particular goals. Implementation studies seek to improve practice and provide guidance on best practices across a broad range of service-learning and community engagement programmatic approaches.

The research agenda identifies questions that centre on the process of delivering service-learning and community engagement across a broad range of community, cultural, geographic, disciplinary, and institutional contexts.

FRAMEWORK FOR IMPLEMENTATION (PRACTICES, MODELS, ROLES, AND GUIDELINES)

Investigate the best practices and models for structuring, implementing and assessing service-learning and community engagement that optimize stakeholder impact.

- What is the lifecycle of service-learning implementation?
- Research different ways to design service-learning projects and compare the impact of these different designs.
- Conduct studies that map the stakeholders, resources, specific roles and tasks that are needed to implement high quality service-learning and community engagement.
- What are the necessary training, design, and implementation components to ensure high quality service-learning and community engagement? Are these components interconnected and how do they impact the efficiency of the service-learning practices?
- What is good training for service-learning and community engagement?

ETHICS IN IMPLEMENTATION

Conduct research on the often-hidden ethical issues that undergird service-learning and community engagement practices and experiences.

- In partnerships, 'reciprocity' may simply be seen as a buzzword. What are the elements for establishing truly reciprocal collaborations in practice for all parties involved?
 - Should teaching staff work additional hours (or expend other opportunity costs) to implement service-learning or community engagement?
-

DISCIPLINARY APPROACHES/PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT ASPECTS FOR ENGAGEMENT IMPACT

Investigate the opportunities and challenges to adopting and advancing service-learning and community engagement as an instructional pedagogy.

- What is the relationship between particular types of service-learning courses (e.g., large size, particular disciplines, etc.) and different strategies for implementing service-learning in the curriculum.
 - Is embedding service-learning realistic in subject-based curriculums? If the agenda is to institutionalise service-learning across universities or other types of educational institutions, how does one achieve this within the curriculum when the curriculum remains subject/discipline-based? Would there be more success if a different approach was taken?
-

CO-PRODUCTION

Investigate the nature and approaches to relationship building among the various stakeholders that participate in service-learning and community engagement.

- It is important that service-learning and community engagement reflect the needs of the community and that research findings are shared with the community. What are the best strategies to not only monitor impact but also the process of service-learning/community engagement so that learning and research findings can be truly shared effectively?
 - What are the ways to effectively incorporate citizen science principles into service-learning research?
 - Examine the different models at play in different institutions of how practitioners and researchers in service-learning work together.
-

IDENTIFICATION OF NEEDS (SOCIETY, STUDENTS, INSTITUTIONS, STAKEHOLDERS, ETC.)

Investigate the ways in which higher education priorities can align more fully to addressing public purposes through student engagement in service-learning and community engagement.

- How do we shift the focus of higher education from employability to enhancing students' ability to apply learning to real social problems, both as a graduate skill and as a way to best manage their roles as members of the community?
-

RISKS, CHALLENGES, OPPORTUNITIES, LIMITATIONS OF SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT IMPLEMENTATION

Investigate the conditions under which service-learning and community engagement experiences fail in order to better understand practices to avoid.

- Where do most problems in implementation of service-learning and community engagement to occur? How can they be avoided and what contingencies must be addressed?
 - How can we minimize the negative side effects of service-learning/community engagement implementation? What are appropriate implementation strategies to minimise the negative side-effects (e.g., negative biases of hierarchy)?
-

PROFESSIONALISATION OF ENGAGEMENT

Examine the relationship between service-learning/community engagement training practices and quality implementation.

- How does training on implementation affect the implementation process of service learning and community engagement?
 - How does training on implementation affect the level of engagement of students in service-learning/community engagement practices?
-

DIGITALISATION AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN IMPLEMENTATION

Investigate the role of artificial intelligence, technology, and digitalization in advancing quality practice of service-learning and community engagement.

- What are the best practices for conducting high quality hybrid service-learning?
- What are potential benefits and drawbacks of Artificial Intelligence in service-learning and community engagement?
- How can digital tools be implemented for reflection in service-learning and community engagement.
- Service-learning is revealing in its various forms/platforms (e.g., as a course, a project, an extracurricular activity in schools, etc.). How do particular forms/platforms shape and limit possibilities/opportunities for participants' experiences?

III. INSTITUTIONALISATION

Institutionalisation research focuses on examining the factors that promote the sustainability and institutionalisation of service-learning and community engagement across institutional and community contexts.

Studies in this area seek to conceptualize the idea of institutionalisation in light of the changing contexts of educational institutions and the varied approaches to service-learning and community engagement.

CONCEPTUALIZATION OF INSTITUTIONALISATION

Conduct investigations that build greater clarity on the concept of institutionalisation, what its aims are, and why institutionalisation should be achieved.

- "What" is it exactly that you want to institutionalize, considering the multiple interpretations, levels, and applications of community engagement and service-learning?
 - What is the goal of institutionalisation? (Whereas it is often phrased as a goal, it seems more as an end)
 - What impact does the institutionalisation of service-learning and community engagement have on the institution and the community?
-

FACILITATORS AND BARRIERS OF INSTITUTIONALISATION

Investigate the challenges to and facilitators of institutionalizing service-learning and community engagement in educational institutions.

- What are the barriers of service-learning and community engagement institutionalisation?
 - What are the motivations of staff members to engage in service-learning and/or community engagement? What motivates teachers to adopt these practices in their work.
 - What support and incentives do teachers need to enhance their involvement in service-learning and community engagement?
-

PROCESS AND STRATEGIES OF SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT INSTITUTIONALISATION

Investigate the various stages of service-learning and community engagement institutionalisation and the different ways that the institutionalisation process can be approached.

- What do longitudinal studies say about the institutionalisation progress and process over time? What are the key markers of institutionalization at different stages of institutionalization development?
 - Which strategies for institutionalizing service-learning and community engagement are more successful?
 - What are the advantages and disadvantages of employing bottom-up approaches to service-learning and community engagement institutionalisation?
-

POLICIES AND MODELS FOR SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT INSTITUTIONALISATION

Identify institutional models and structures for service-learning and community engagement institutionalisation.

- What are different, successful models of service-learning and community engagement institutionalisation at different types of educational institutions?
 - What types of institutional structures are associated with long-term service-learning and community engagement institutionalisation at institutions that are constantly changing and evolving?
-

RESOURCES AND FUNDING

Investigate best practices for securing financial and other resources that support the institutionalisation of service-learning and community engagement in educational institutions and partner organizations.

- How can service-learning and community engagement be better resourced to be effectively institutionalized?

IV. COVID/POST-COVID

Questions and issues that explore service-learning and community engagement practices during and beyond COVID.

The issues include, but are not limited to:

- new emerging practices for service-learning and community engagement resulting from the pandemic.
- changes regarding the conduct of service-learning and community engagement research due to COVID.
- impact of COVID on the quality of service-learning and community engagement; and
- advantages and disadvantages of conducting service-learning and community engagement during or after COVID.

LESSONS FROM COVID (INSTITUTIONS, COMMUNITY, AND STUDENTS)

Investigate the ways that COVID has impacted service-learning and community engagement practices and participants' approaches to and motivations for their involvement in the practices.

- What challenges did the pandemic bring to service-learning and community engagement programs?
- What new best practice strategies did the pandemic bring to service-learning and community engagement programs?
- What are the long-term effects of the pandemic on students' motivation and attitudes towards service-learning and community engagement in the context of digital citizenship, and how can these be effectively addressed?

NEW PRACTICES IN DIGITAL ENGAGEMENT

Investigate the ways in which COVID has shaped how digital approaches are being applied to service-learning and community engagement practices.

- How have service-learning programs adapted to the challenges posed by the pandemic, and what innovative strategies have emerged during this time that promote digital citizenship?
-

CHANGES IN IMPLEMENTATION AFTER COVID

Conduct comparisons of how post-COVID practices of service-learning and community engagement practices are similar to or different from the practices used before and during COVID.

- How is e-Service-Learning post-COVID different from e-Service-Learning during COVID?
-

ETHICS IN DIGITAL ENGAGEMENT

Investigate the various ethical issues and challenges that may arise as service-learning and community engagement practice become more digitalized.

- What mechanisms, policies, structures, and practices need to be put in place in order that the implementation of service-learning and community engagement in the post-COVID era account for responsible online behaviour, digital literacy, and ethical use of technology?
-

IMPACT OF COVID

Investigate whether COVID has changed views and approaches to service-learning and community engagement.

- What are the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on service-learning initiatives in terms of student engagement, community partnerships, and learning outcomes, considering the dimensions of digital citizenship?
- What new skills in post-COVID era are enhanced by service-learning and community engagement participation?

V. EQUITY AND SOCIAL ADVANCEMENT

Research in this area focuses on issues that explore the role of equity in service-learning and community engagement practices within and across cultures, populations, and regions. The issues include, but are not limited to, implications for conducting equity-focused research within and across different groups, populations, communities, and/or cultures.

EQUITY PRINCIPLES IN CURRICULUM/COURSE DESIGN

Explore the program elements in service-learning and community engagement that promote participants' understanding of equity and social advancement.

- What program (curriculum) elements impact the development of critical (justice-oriented) social change understanding?
- Do different program aspects impact students from diverse demographic backgrounds differently?

CRITICAL AND DECOLONIAL RESEARCH APPROACH

Conduct investigations that have a critical, decolonial approach and have epistemic integrity.

- What are effective research approaches that embody a critical, decolonial perspective with epistemic integrity that can be applied to studies of service-learning and community engagement?

EQUITY IN COLLABORATION

Investigate how service-learning/community engagement relationships—between students, faculty, and community—can be made more equitable, reciprocal, and inclusive.

- How do we collaborate in a manner that values the contributions of all parties included in an equal manner?

STUDENT DIVERSITY (STUDENT-ASSET)

Examine how educational institutions adopt community-centred practices while addressing power imbalances, historical harm, and equity through justice-centred engagement, equitable co-production, and a commitment to collective thriving.

- How does resource disparity among students influence the creativity, adaptability, and flexibility of service-learning projects?

- What are the outcomes for different student demographics, especially those traditionally marginalised in education (e.g., socio-economic status, first-generation)?
-

EQUITY ISSUES IN SOCIETY

Explore how service-learning and community engagement initiatives are intentionally structured to promote equity, including the design of partnerships, curricula, and pedagogies that prioritize co-creation, cultural relevance, asset-based approaches, accessibility, and the dismantling of exclusionary practices to ensure inclusive participation and equitable outcomes.

- How and to what extent could service-learning and community engagement contribute to addressing inequity issues?

VI. CULTURAL/REGIONAL AND CROSS-CULTURAL/CROSS-REGIONAL

Issues that explore service-learning and community engagement practices within and across cultures and regions are to be embraced and discussed, with an eye toward identifying questions or action steps for the research agenda.

The research issues include, but is not limited to:

- conducting research within and across different cultural or geographic settings;
- examining service-learning and community engagement across the educational spectrum;
- community voice;
- multiple frames of service-learning and community engagement.

CULTURAL SENSITIVITY IN SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT IMPLEMENTATION IN CONCRETE PROJECTS

Investigate strategies for building greater cultural sensitivity and understanding in service-learning and community engagement projects.

- What are successful strategies in cross-cultural collaboration, according to students and community partners?
- How do cultural differences facilitate the capacity of community members to co-create research agendas?
- What are best practices for taking into account the cultural diversity of values/rules/norms of the recipients?

CONTRIBUTIONS TO CROSS-CULTURAL AWARENESS

Investigate the ways in which service-learning and community engagement contribute to the advancement of participants' cultural awareness.

- To what extent and in what ways do community engagement and service-learning experiences contribute to culture awareness?
 - What impact do cross-cultural service-learning and community engagement projects through glocalization promote participants' cultural awareness?
-

CROSS-COUNTRY AND CROSS-REGIONAL DIFFERENCES IN COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT AND SERVICE-LEARNING IMPLEMENTATION

Examine the similarities and differences in service-learning and community engagement implementation and institutionalization across national, regional, and cultural contexts.

- What are the differences between the regions in regard to how service-learning and community engagement are defined, implemented, and institutionalized?
 - What are the qualitative differences among implementing models of service-learning and community engagement across cultures and contexts?
-

DIVERSITY IN POLITICAL CONTEXT OF COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT AND SERVICE-LEARNING DEVELOPMENT

Investigate how the different political environments across the region impact the ways in which service-learning and community engagement are practiced and institutionalized.

- How do cultural/historical/governmental/institutional contexts shape strategies for keeping and strengthening service-learning courses and students' engagement?
-

LINGUISTIC DIMENSIONS IN COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT AND SERVICE-LEARNING

Explore how the different languages and linguistic cultures in the region shape the ways in which service-learning and community engagement are defined, practiced, and advanced.

- To what extent is the current movement to give visibility to the linguistic diversity in the region affecting the ways in which service-learning and community engagement are being advanced and operationalised?
- Does the use of English as a primary language in the region perpetuate a sense of colonialism, and if so, does it have an effect on the ways service-learning and community engagement are perceived by students, teachers, and community members?

VII. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORKS AND THEORIES

The field of service-learning and community engagement has been criticized for being under-theorized and for lacking well-developed and well-tested conceptual frameworks.

Research in this area of work focuses on theory testing and building conceptual models and frameworks that explain various phenomena in the study and practice of service-learning and community engagement.

THEORETICAL LENS

Build a deeper and expanded theoretical base for research on service-learning and community engagement.

- What are the conceptual frameworks and theories from other fields and disciplines that can be used in research on service-learning and community engagement. Some examples might include:
 - Transformative learning theory
 - Community organizing theories and frameworks. There are some examples developed where higher education works with local community organizing partners. This can be helpful for re-conceptualising service-learning and community engagement as more overtly political.
 - Critical pedagogy — critical consciousness core to our hopes.
 - Social pedagogy. This might be a useful theory as it focuses on cultural agility and inclusive practice - seeing academic/practitioners/communities and individuals as all sharing the same life space.
 - Complex systems theory to analyse success of service-learning (one study exists, it can be interesting to replicate it)
 - Digital participation theory
 - Theory of experiential learning and its influence on students' learning.
 - Theoretical models of social empathy development - could help reflection.
 - Ecological models applied to institutional learning.

OPERATIONAL FRAMEWORK

Establish conceptual frameworks that provide guidance on how to best operate and deliver service-learning and community engagement programs and practices.

- How can the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) be leveraged as a taxonomy framework for service-learning activities. The (SDGs) have proven to be a useful framework for service-learning activities.
- What are the best digital literacy frameworks to understand and enhance service-learning and community engagement practices?
- What concept models explain the relationship between service-learning/community engagement participation and democratic and/or global competencies?

Systematising Research on Service-Learning and Community Engagement

Develop a research plan that articulates a systematic approach to advancing key areas of research on service-learning and community engagement in Europe.

- Which are the model protocols from previous research in broader field service-learning and community engagement that can be used as guides for conducting research on service-learning and community engagement in Europe?
- Conduct a systematic review of existing research on service-learning and community engagement in Europe beginning with pulling together a systematic review of the literature that has attempted to theorise service-learning/community-engaged learning. This will provide a picture of the state of play and the kinds of theories/models that have been used to date.
- Conduct an overview on the different theoretical models and conceptual frameworks used in service-learning and community engagement studies.
- Conduct a comprehensive review of the specific competencies to evaluate and measure in service-learning and community engagement.

Theory Development and Service-learning Conceptualisation

Bring greater clarity to the definition of service-learning, taking into account the diverse knowledge systems and social contexts that influence how service-learning is operationalised and practiced.

- In order to have a robust conceptual framework, we need to build an understanding of what is meant by ‘service-learning’. One of the questions that comes up time and again is ‘what do we mean by service-learning’? It has numerous definitions and as many practices, which creates challenges when trying to use existing frameworks or create new ones for service-learning research.
- What are effective strategies to learn from the indigenous knowledge systems, cultures, and practices? How can communities’ knowledge actually inform current and new theories?

VIII. METHODOLOGICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The issues in this section focus on identifying the kinds of methods that are appropriate for the study of service-learning and community engagement. The items consider the research designs, methods, epistemologies and approaches that are needed and required in designing and operationalizing future research on service-learning and community engagement.

A broad range of research designs, methods, and approaches are needed in order to gain a full understanding of the nature of the field. A broad range of epistemologies are required in designing and operationalizing today's research on service-learning and community engagement.

ENSURING QUALITY

Explore the possibility of establishing a set of common expectations and research standards that can guide service-learning and community engagement researchers in conducting and producing high quality research.

- How do we best deal with small samples and sometimes biased conclusions?
- Could a detailed explanation of methodology be required for publications, including expected outcomes?
- Should we agree on guidelines for methodology?

MIXED METHODS

Examine the potential and role of mixed methods in studies of service-learning and community engagement.

- Is a combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches possible/desired to produce high quality service-learning and community engagement studies?
- Are quantitative and qualitative approaches equally effective in the study of service-learning and community engagement?

COMMUNITY FOCUSED

Explore effective strategies for conducting community-engaged research that is co-created with partners through participatory methods that prioritize community voice.

- Aim for more studies that utilize participatory action research (PAR).

- Establish a set of elements to be included to measure the community voice.
-

LONGITUDINAL

Identify best practices and effective strategies for conducting longitudinal studies of service-learning and community engagement.

- How do we deal with the practical challenges of getting longitudinal data?

IX. INSTRUMENTS AND MEASURES

Securing quality research requires valid and appropriate instruments and measures that can secure the best data and provide opportunities for thorough, systematic analyses. Many of the instruments that have been developed for the study of service-learning and community engagement are home grown instruments that are often applied to single studies and are not cultivated further for potential use in other studies. In addition, there are many instruments that are available for studies of service-learning and community engagement, but it is sometimes unclear regarding the suitability of such instruments for programs or populations for which they were not initially designed.

The research agenda identifies issues for improving the instrumentation and measurement of service-learning and community engagement across the many contexts in which the work takes place.

APPROPRIATENESS

Conduct more testing of instruments and measures used in community engagement and service-learning research to ensure that the instruments are valid, reliable, and appropriate for the particular conditions and contexts in which the studies take place.

- Validate more instruments for community engagement and service-learning research.
- What are the best instruments for research on service-learning and community engagement that can be applied across diverse and national contexts?
- What is the best way to plan experiments? Should templates be developed to help plan service-learning and community engagement studies?

COLLABORATIVE RESOURCES

Enhance the capacity for community engagement and service-learning researchers to access and exchange research-related opportunities, instruments, datasets, and other resources.

- Establish an up-to-date repository/online platform that provides various resources (e.g., recent studies, instruments, data sets, etc.) to service-learning and community engagement researchers.
 - Develop a mechanism for community engagement and service-learning researchers to share and exchange research tools and methods more easily and more widely.
-

PARTICIPATORY ENGAGEMENT

Expand opportunities for all participants and stakeholders to have a voice and role in community engagement and service-learning research activities.

- What are best practices and effective strategies for giving voice to and involving various stakeholders in service-learning and community engagement research studies?
 - How do we include the perspectives and voices of community partners?
-

QUALITATIVE/NARRATIVE INSTRUMENTS

Develop greater clarity as a field as to which research methods and instruments are valid and appropriate (and not appropriate) for the study of service-learning and community engagement.

- Are all qualitative approaches (data from questionnaires, focus groups, observations in nature, etc.) valid for conducting research on service-learning and community engagement?
 - What are the standards of rigour that should be met when using qualitative narrative instruments in service-learning and community engagement research?
-

QUANTITATIVE INSTRUMENTS

Develop a database of quantitative instruments that are applicable to and valid for research on service-learning and community engagement.

- Quantitative measures in service-learning and community engagement research are scant. More instruments are needed. What are effective mechanisms for developing them?

X. REPLICATION

No one study provides all the evidence, understanding, or knowledge that is needed to draw firm conclusions about service-learning or community engagement. Replication is a critical feature of scientific inquiry and research.

Only a handful of service-learning and community engagement studies have been replicated. Replicating high quality studies is a way to strengthen evidence and secure more conclusive findings about the strengths and limitations of service-learning and community engagement practices, outcomes, and approaches.

CROSS-REGIONAL/CROSS-CULTURAL REPLICATION

Replicate service-learning and community engagement studies in new and different local and global contexts.

- Conduct further research in various local and global contexts, focusing on immigration studies (as both a topic and sample) and its connection to service-learning and community engagement.
- Conduct further research in various local and global contexts, focusing on community needs and their connection to service-learning and community engagement (as both a topic and sample).
- Conduct further research in various local and global contexts, focusing on populations with similar characteristics across different contexts, and populations with diverse characteristics in similar contexts (as a sample), while investigating various variables of interest.
- Conduct further research in various local and global contexts, focusing on (as a topic) how service-learning and community engagement studies can address universal needs.

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ANTWERP, BELGIUM (September 21, 2019)

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NOTTINGHAM, ENGLAND [Virtual] (May 18, 2020)

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MUNICH, GERMANY [Virtual] (June 21, 2023)

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Analysis Meeting: Antwerp, Belgium (November 20-21, 2024)

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**GLOBAL RESEARCH AGENDA FOR
SERVICE-LEARNING AND
COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT**

NORTH AMERICA REGION

Global Research Agenda for Service-learning and Community Engagement

NORTH AMERICA REGION

The content contained in this part of the global research agenda is based on an analysis of 2,541 research questions and items submitted by 235 individuals who participated in 11 forums held in the United States between October 2019 and February 2025. While these forums were held in the United States, four of them had multinational participation. The questions and items were categorized and prioritized by 44 individuals from the United States who participated in a set of data analysis meetings held in Atlanta (March 2025), Durham, North Carolina (April 2025), and San Diego (May 2025). The results of their analyses and discussions are presented here.

I. IMPACTS

Impact research focuses on assessing the impacts of service-learning and community engagement on participants, including students, faculty, staff, institutions and the community. They cross a broad range of short-term and long-term outcomes. This section of the agenda presents broad areas of impact to be investigated along with a particular set of themes within each impact area.

STUDENT RETENTION, MATRICULATION, AND PATHWAYS

Investigate how civic and community engagement influence student success across a broad range of participants and stakeholders.

- Do high schools with service-learning programs have better attendance and graduation rates? Are students who participate in service-learning courses in high school more likely to apply to/complete college? How does a service-learning curriculum impact the student college selection process, as they decide where to apply and what school to attend?
- What impact does community-engaged learning have on students' career outcomes and participation in their communities?

- What is the impact of interdisciplinary service-learning courses on --employability of students? --career pathways of former students?
- What is the role of service-learning and community engagement on increasing student enrollment of majors and/or resilience of precariously political disciplines (e.g. arts and humanities programs), contemporaneously “controversial” programs etc. (e.g. critical race theory. - CRT)?

CIVIC AND POLITICAL PARTICIPATION

Assess the link between higher education’s civic initiatives and students’ lifelong civic and political behaviors.

- Impact on students: Examining the impact of community engagement and service-learning in/on social justice movements. Have they (students) learned solidarity or virtue signaling?
- Does participation in service-learning and community engagement contribute to existing socio-political divides in education settings? (e.g. CRT debates at school board meetings).
- What is the impact of service-learning/community engagement on students from the community in which the engagement occurs (e.g. students with disability in education courses serving with school for disability)? Understanding of concepts: affective change development.
- Does participation in service-learning or community engagement lead to long-term engagement in activism and other forms of service-learning?
- How does a place-based approach to service-learning impact students’ ability to think, work, and explore global issues and challenges?
- What role does international service-learning play in fostering public/citizen diplomacy between countries?

SPECIAL POPULATIONS AND SERVICE-LEARNING/COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT IMPACT

Examine how service-learning and civic engagement (SLCE) initiatives differentially impact specific groups, including ESL/ELL students, international students, and marginalized communities, with attention to how context, proximity, and locale influence these experiences and outcomes.

- Are there heterogenous effects for various subgroups (ethnicity, first gen, community of origin, disability, language, gender, intersectionalities, students of color, international

students) in civic or academic outcomes from participation in service-learning and community engagement?

- What is the impact of course-based service-learning and community engagement on student learning outcomes (SLOs) for students engaged in experiences in their own hometowns?
- What are the short-term impacts of sense of belonging for first gen students who engage in community engagement?
- What role do institutions play in providing equitable resources for communities? (e.g., translation, American Sign Language (ASL), ADA materials beforehand, brail)?
- What is the impact of SL/CE on the plight of rural communities that are affected by poverty and high unemployment history, from previously disadvantaged and apartheid history?
- Are there differential impacts of SLCE between students of color from privileged backgrounds (i.e., high socio-economic backgrounds, homes with two parents, etc.) and white students from underprivileged backgrounds (i.e., low socio-economic status, abusive homes, single parent homes, etc.)?

MENTAL HEALTH, SOCIAL-EMOTIONAL LEARNING (SEL), AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

Investigate how engagement experiences impact student well-being, resilience, and SEL development.

- How does student participation in service-learning and community engagement use and build social-emotional competencies?
 - How does service-learning and community engagement impact students' empathy development, cross-cultural competence, mental health, assumptions, self-awareness, systems thinking.
 - What is the impact of service-learning and community engagement participation on mental health and suicide prevention for students, educators, community?
 - What are the short-term impacts of sense of belonging for first-generation student populations who engage in service-learning and community engagement?
 - How does engaging in community engagement change perspectives of the world around them?
-

STUDENT CIVIC IDENTITY FORMATION

Build understanding how community engagement shapes students' personal, academic, and professional identities over time.

- Do students see a connection between their service-learning and civic-mindedness?
- Long-term impact on engaged students considered to be of minority backgrounds on/of their self-understanding with respect to being: -agents of change, -assimilated vs. separate-ethical identity.
- Does participation in service-learning lead to increased civic skills, knowledge, and dispositions, and other civic health indicators? Does it lead to increased social capital, social trust, trust in institutions, etc.)?
- What is the impact of service-learning and community engagement courses/co-curricular experiences on the personal and identity development of college students?
- Do students who've been involved with service-learning report higher levels of understanding re: civic participation skills like consensus-building and conflict resolution than those who haven't had such involvement?

FACULTY ENGAGEMENT, IDENTITY, AND INSTITUTIONAL INCENTIVES

Investigating how faculty engagement in community-engaged scholarship and community-based learning influences their professional identity, development, and career progression, including the role of tenure and promotion (P&T) processes in shaping these behaviors.

- How is this approach transforming the way faculty across disciplines conceptualize their teaching—shifting from viewing community engagement as a service-learning 'add-on' to embracing it as a foundational pedagogy, and scholar identity? In what ways is this lens reshaping their attitudes, course design, and overall approach to student learning?
 - How does service-learning impact faculty perceptions of how well a course has gone? Does that align with student course evaluations? If not, why?
 - What are the short- and long-term impacts of BIPOC faculty and professionals who lead community engagement efforts?
 - What impact does service-learning and community engagement have on faculty teaching and learning in regard to pedagogy, resource development, and course development?
 - Faculty/staff - does service-learning and community engagement impact faculty and staff's mental health, sense of community belonging, retention?
 - How does faculty mentorship impact community-engaged faculty development?
-

COMMUNITY AND CIVIC HEALTH

Examine how partnerships enhance various dimensions of community health, including but not limited to social, economic, environmental, and civic well-being, as indicators of overall community quality and resilience.

- What is the impact of service-learning and community engagement on community resilience/sociological resilience?
- What is the impact of service-learning and community engagement on the communities' overall civic and environmental health? How does proximity to an institution affect the outcomes?
- Does the presence of engaged institutions of higher education lead to improved community outcomes such as social capital or youth outcomes as a result of service-learning and community engagement?
- What is the impact of service-learning and community engagement on the social determinants of health within a campus community and/or the community in a certain proximity to an institution?
- What is the impact of service-learning on a community's perception of the value/power of young people?

PARTNERSHIPS

Investigate how broad partnerships shape community outcomes and the qualities and impact of service-learning and community engagement initiatives.

- What is the impact of service-learning on the integration/strengthening of school, community, family, and university partnerships?
- Community - how does service-learning and community engagement impact: institution/community relationships, assumptions/biases, mental health, non-profit capacity?
- To what extent do community partners see themselves as co-educators as a result of engaging service-learning?
- How do collaborative and adaptive approaches to leadership influence community engagement partnership outcomes?

II. IMPLEMENTATION

Implementation research focuses on examining the practices of service-learning and community engagement and the ways in which these practices are effective in achieving particular goals. Implementation studies seek to improve practice and provide guidance on best practices across a broad range of service-learning and community engagement programmatic approaches.

The research agenda identifies questions that center on the process of delivering service-learning and community engagement across a broad range of community, cultural, geographic, disciplinary, and institutional contexts.

EFFECTIVE SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT MODELS AND STRUCTURES

Investigate the best practices and models for structuring, implementing and assessing service-learning and community engagement that optimize stakeholder impact.

- What length of time is ideal for different types of service-learning and community engagement? (e.g., direct service, indirect service, advocacy, virtual).
- What are the similarities and differences between various modalities of service-learning and community engagement (e.g., online/virtual, curricular/co-curricular, individual/group)?
- What are the best practices in service-learning and community engagement and how are they assessed over time (reflection, stakeholder feedback)?
- What is the impact of how the service-learning and community engagement experience is structured (e.g., elective/requirement, long-term/short-term, transactional/transformational)?
- What are the longitudinal markers of best practice in community-higher ed partnerships among institutional type (e.g., Catholic institutions versus R1 institutions, versus private institutions)? Does it differ from other institutions?

INSTITUTIONAL PROCESSES, PROCEDURES, AND SUPPORT

Conduct research to build a better understanding of the institutional and infrastructure supports—faculty professional development, networking, incentives for participation, tenure/promotion, dedicated centers, community engagement professional role, memoranda of understanding, policies, Carnegie Classification for Community Engagement process—that deepen the implementation of service-learning and community engagement.

- Does the match between what institutional leaders say and what they do (i.e., trust in leadership) influence the quality of service-learning/community engagement at an institution? How do the priorities of institutions and community partners differ and have

an effect on the implementation of service-learning and community engagement?

- What do faculty need to implement this work across disciplines? What is the best strategy for faculty to implement this work across disciplines?
- What are effective strategies to gain institutional support?
- How can we best mobilize funders for community engagement and service-learning?

CENTERING COMMUNITIES, COMMUNITY VOICE, AND COMMUNITY PARTNER EXPERIENCE

Investigate the role and best practices pertaining to communication, co-creation, ensuring the development of reciprocal partnerships, types of partnerships, and ways to engage.

- How can we best engage community partners in reflective practices before, during, and after service-learning projects to measure ways service has positively or negatively impacted community members to better understand ways to scaffold partnerships that minimize harm?
- What is the role of the community in knowledge creation? How to create processes of validation that undermine current power structures? What does it mean for a partnership to be reciprocal?
- Does offering financial support (or other resources) to community partners, students, and faculty make a difference in the quality and/or meaningfulness of the experience?
- Examine the different approaches higher education uses to engage community partners - which approach is most effective? Hyperlocal - fewer partners with more concentrated effort? Many partners - very dispersed? Local, regional, state, and international partners?
- What are best practices for tying institutional community engagement agenda to needs of the local region (e.g., literacy, food insecurity, etc.)?

STUDENT EXPERIENCE

Investigate the role and best practices for reflection, ensuring equity in access to service-learning and community engagement, and student leadership in the engagement experience.

- What are the most effective ways to encourage students to be involved with community engagement or advocacy after a course is over?
- Given how important and useful Bloom's Taxonomy is in helping us think more deeply about levels of learning and teaching, can we establish a taxonomy of "service-learning/community-engaged learning" which identifies developmental levels of ethical

community engagement and critical consciousness?

- The majority of research on civically-engaged students is very white-centered. How do we implement studies or experiences for students who do not come from white or privileged backgrounds?
- What kinds of training and prep of students are needed when they are and are not representative of the community where service takes place? How do we best prepare students to enter communities, especially when interacting with people who may be different from them?

INCLUSIONARY PRACTICES AND DIVERSITY, EQUITY, AND JUSTICE

Investigate the role and best practices for ensuring and supporting diverse perspectives, cultural approach, and states of being in service-learning and community engagement and how such practices are channeled in the service-learning and community engagement process.

- How can community engagement practices reflect a pedagogy of liberation rather than reinforce dominant cultural norms?
- What strategies help faculty and staff navigate identity-based tensions in intercultural student and partner spaces (e.g., pronoun use, cultural norms)?
- What models from Minority Serving Institutions can inform more equitable community engagement practices at Predominantly White Institutions?
- How can universities engage a broader range of community institutions to collaboratively meet regional equity and access needs?

SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT IN K-12 EDUCATION

Investigate ways to incorporate best practices of service-learning and community engagement within K-12 education systems.

- Study the implementation of service-learning in university schools of Education and their service-learning courses for pre-service and in-service K-12 teachers and administrators on the basics of service-learning and community engagement.
 - To what degree do K-12 teachers connect service to academic context standards?
 - What did it take for a district charter or state to strongly accept and use service-learning research to improve what happens with students?
 - At what age should students first engage in service-learning and what are the potential outcomes across the grade spans?
-

PRACTITIONER STAFF EXPERIENCE

Investigate the professional pathways of staff who coordinate and lead service-learning and community engagement.

- What is the career pathway of a service-learning/community engagement practitioner/teacher?
 - How do we support professional development for practitioners/staff?
-

FACULTY EXPERIENCE

Investigate the professional development of focus to expand their horizons regarding the different approaches to and purposes of service-learning and community engagement.

- In terms of service-learning and community engagement best practices - how do we effectively scaffold faculty development, particularly from charity-oriented approaches to more social-change orientations.
- What mechanisms, tools, support systems foster faculty development of service-learning and community engagement?

III. INSTITUTIONALIZATION

Institutionalization research focuses on examining the factors that promote the sustainability and institutionalization of service-learning and community engagement across institutional and community contexts.

Studies in this area seek to conceptualize the idea of institutionalization in light of the changing contexts of educational institutions and the varied approaches to service-learning and community engagement.

MISSION AND CULTURAL SUPPORT

Investigate how, in what ways, and to what effect service-learning and community engagement are being institutionalized.

- In what ways do efforts connect to mission, curriculum and strategic planning?
 - How, in what ways, and to what effect is service-learning and community engagement integrated into university goals and priorities?
 - What types of investments and commitments are being made to institutionalize community engagement into the mission of research, teaching, and service?
 - What are the barriers and bolsters of institutionalizing service-learning and community engagement?
-

FACULTY AND STAFF SUPPORT

Investigate how, in what ways, and to what effect faculty are being recognized, rewarded, and supported for their community engagement work and scholarship.

- How are universities moving to shift how faculty think about research/teaching to better allow or embrace community engagement?
 - What is the role of faculty rewards, promotion, and tenure criteria and other measures of faculty success on institutionalization of service-learning and community engagement?
 - How do we address the realities that these classes are often taught by BIPOC, untenured/pre-tenured and women faculty without compensation or recognition?
 - How can educational institutions incorporate the concept of service and service-learning while onboarding new faculty in a way that is mission-aligned and focused on long term investment, while maintaining a focus on community needs/desires?
-

COMMUNITY PARTNER SUPPORT

Investigate how, in what ways, and to what effect community partners are being recognized, rewarded, and supported for their community engagement work and scholarship.

- How do community partners value long-term, sustainable partnerships?
 - To what extent are community partnerships reciprocal and mutually beneficial?
 - What are best practices for building university - community networks?
-

STUDENT SUPPORT

Investigate how, in what ways, and to what effect students are motivated to engage and are supported in service-learning and community engagement activities.

- What are the benefits and drawbacks of mandating service (attaching it to graduation requirements etc.)?
 - What are the long-term impacts of service-learning and community engagement on student outcomes?
 - What impact does positioning service-learning and community engagement with other high impact practices in a center or office have on student and faculty engagement at institutions?
-

MATURITY AND PROFESSIONALISM IN THE FIELD

Investigate how, in what ways, and to what effect the service-learning and community engagement field is growing, is being sustained, and is connected with or is influencing the current political climate and societal issues.

- How has the Carnegie Designation process promoted or hindered institutionalization of community engagement (especially at minority service institutions and community colleges)?
 - What are the unintended/negative consequences of institutionalizing/professionalizing/disciplining the service-learning and community engagement field?
 - Did federal service-learning policy (Learn and Serve America) have its intended impacts on civic skills of students and solving community problems? Were the \$10-2- million federal investments producing outside impacts relative to the size of the investments?
 - How do we share information and knowledge of the field and continue to develop the knowledge base?
-

IV. COVID/POST-COVID

Questions and issues that explore service-learning and community engagement practices during and beyond COVID.

The issues include, but are not limited to:

- new emerging practices for service-learning and community engagement results from the pandemic;
- changes regarding the conduct of service-learning and community engagement research due to COVID;
- impact of COVID on the quality of service-learning and community engagement; and
- advantages and disadvantages of conducting service-learning and community engagement during or after COVID.

IMPACT OF PEDAGOGY, TEACHING, AND LEARNING

Examine if, how, and in what ways pedagogy, teaching, and learning of service-learning and community engagement have been impacted or changed because of COVID.

- What are the lessons we learned from doing service-learning in a virtual space that we can take with us, learn from and weave into service-learning experiences?
- What is the impact of technology on service-learning and community engagement? Do virtual platforms facilitate more equitable community engagement opportunities? Are there ways it is less equitable?
- What are the impacts from shifting from direct to indirect service?
- What are the best practices in risk management for virtual experiences? What are the ethical implications of virtual engagement?

IMPACT ON COMMUNITY PARTNERS

Examine if, how, and in ways have community partners and partnerships been impacted and changed because of COVID?

- How has COVID elevated our understanding of the ways in which service-learning and community engagement does or does not support increasing resilience in communities?
- What are the financial strains on nonprofit /partner capacity to support service-learning? How do we continue to fund/stipend/resource community-based organizations?
- Who was benefited by online service actions (e.g., training and service provision)? What was disadvantaged by the online service actions? Should they be continued?

- How can what we learned about public meetings and inclusivity benefit the way service-learning partners work together?
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LINK BETWEEN COVID AND RACIAL JUSTICE AND HEALTH DISPARITIES

Investigate whether COVID has changed views and approaches to service-learning and community engagement, especially in regard to addressing issues of racial justice and health disparities.

- How has the impact of the racial tension coupled with COVID changed the desire and level of engagement of educators, students, and/or communities?
- How has COVID increased awareness of systemic issues such as lack of access to quality health care?
- How did COVID affect the interpretation of the work "service" in regard to more vulnerable communities?
- How and in what ways does service-learning and community engagement impact students' mental health?

V. EQUITY AND SOCIAL ADVANCEMENT

Research in this area focuses on issues that explore the role of equity in service-learning and community engagement practices within and across cultures, populations, and regions. The issues include, but are not limited to, implications for conducting equity-focused research within and across different groups, populations, communities, and/or cultures.

SOCIAL SYSTEMS OF POWER

Examine how service-learning and community engagement can confront systemic power imbalances, promote equity through co-production, and shift from service to justice by centering marginalized voices and fostering belonging.

- How do we attend to power imbalances between the university and the community?
- How does co-production in service-learning lead to more equitable partnerships, and what shifts when marginalized communities are meaningfully involved in shaping projects aimed at advancing equity and social justice?
- How can we move from service to justice in our framing of service-learning and community engagement?
- How does service-learning and community engagement impact today's polarized climate?
- To what extent do service-learning experiments/projects help decrease or promote the sense of othering and increased belonging across different groups of communities?

PRACTICES, PEDAGOGIES, AND METHODS

Explore how service-learning and community engagement practices, pedagogies, and methods can incorporate diverse cultural perspectives, ensure inclusive participation, and challenge dominant norms to create increasingly just, representative models of the populations it serves.

- Conduct research to develop a new set of service-learning prevalence data (like Learn and Serve America used to do) with full demographic breakdowns by geography (rural, suburban, urban), race/ethnicity, socioeconomic status, gender, youth with disabilities, English-language learners, etc.
- Just like the education field does with graduation rates, establish a means to measure the gaps in students having access to service-learning and community engagement opportunities, to assess rates of participation in the opportunities.
- What are ways to increase rates in under-represented communities and populations to bring parity to rates of opportunity and participation?

- Develop mechanisms to capture good data on how much service-learning is actually happening and who service-learning programs are engaging.
- How can we create a new pedagogy of service-learning that is not grounded in whiteness? Or test/evaluate the models that have recently emerged?
- How are differentiated instructional strategies being implemented to ensure all students have the opportunity to participate?
- What practices in service-learning and community engagement create more equitable access for resources for social change?

EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS' ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

Examine how educational institutions adopt community-centered practices while addressing power imbalances, historical harm, and equity through justice-centered engagement, equitable co-production, and a commitment to collective thriving.

- How are power/privilege differentials attended to in community/university relationships? What processes, procedures, ways of engaging, etc. acknowledge this effectively?
 - How do we repair harm done by our universities on communities we now propose to "serve"? What frameworks, conversations, practices and Catholic Social Teaching (CST) principles can we contribute?
 - What is the impact of institutions and universities actively pursuing and creating reparation for Black and Indigenous communities?
 - How can we move from service to justice in our framing of service-learning and community engagement? How can we examine the role of service-learning on polarization in the current moment?
 - What are the promising (institutional) practices for equity-focused service-learning and community engagement?
 - How (much) do we compensate community partners?
 - How do we ensure scholarship service hours are equitable?
-

INTERPERSONAL RELATIONSHIPS

Investigate how service-learning/community engagement relationships—between students, faculty, and community—can be made more equitable, reciprocal, and inclusive.

- Does service-learning and community engagement create a sense of belonging among students? Is there a connection between equity and belonging?
 - How to develop the relational and interpersonal skills for faculty and students to engage discussions addressing equity issues?
 - How are power/privilege differentials attended to in community/university relationships? What processes, procedures, ways of engaging, etc. acknowledge this effectively?
 - What is the harm we are doing to partners, students, and other participants?
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DIVERSITY, CULTURAL AWARENESS, AND RESPONSIVENESS

Investigate how service-learning and community engagement practices recognize, respect, and respond to diverse cultural identities, experiences, and worldviews by fostering intercultural understanding, affirming marginalized perspectives, and cultivating culturally responsive approaches that enhance inclusion and mutual respect across differences.

- What role does/should intercultural responsiveness competence play in community engagement?
 - How do we increase cross cultural competence/awareness? How to measure this?
 - What needs to happen with service-learning and community engagement participants around diversity, equity, and inclusion prior to engaging in these experiences?
-

DESIGN

Explore how service-learning and community engagement initiatives are intentionally structured to promote equity, including the design of partnerships, curricula, and pedagogies that prioritize co-creation, cultural relevance, asset-based approaches, accessibility, and the dismantling of exclusionary practices to ensure inclusive participation and equitable outcomes.

- How do we center BIPOC students in community-engaged learning?
- How do we know for sure that service-learning does not simply reinforce stereotypes that some communities are "deficits" and some are assets? How can service-learning be implemented to frame the community from an assets lens? How do we know for sure that service-learning does not simply reinforce stereotypes that some communities are

"deficits" and some are assets?

- How do projects include the view from different cultures/groups in their design?
- How to develop skills for faculty/students to engage in discussion/address equity issues?
- How can equity questions be scaffolded in the classroom curriculum in order to facilitate more equitable service-learning?
- Case studies of equity-focused service-learning. How might co-production (as a research approach) promote equity among all partners involved in service-learning?
- How can we move from service to justice in our framing of service-learning? How can we examine the role of service-learning on polarization in the current moment?

STUDENT ACCESS

Examine how students have equitable access to service-learning and community engagement.

- Service is often more accessible to students with the most resources - those who do not have to work while attending school, do not have to support family, are traditional college students, and so forth. How can we structure service opportunities that are accessible to all students, particularly those with fewer resources, time, and transportation, and how can we best support those students who are participating to ensure their relationships with community partners are steeped in reciprocity?
 - Are stipends/fellowships successful at involving more students from diverse backgrounds in service-learning and community engagement? What are the trade-offs students on Pell grant/federal aid and/or with other summer offers making when they select to participate in summer research opportunities? How do we mitigate those?
 - What is the appropriate balance between the accessibility of virtual service-learning and community engagement versus the in-depth impact of person-to-person experiences?
 - What are best practices for making service-learning and community engagement programs accessible for physically challenged students and partners?
 - How are differentiated instructional strategies being implemented to ensure all students have the opportunity to participate?
 - What cultural responsibilities prevent students from engaging in service-learning and community engagement? |
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SOCIAL IDENTITY

Investigate how service-learning and community engagement are designed equitably to incorporate diverse backgrounds and experiences.

- Taking into account assumptions and stereotypes, how does one measure growth and change? What are best practices for challenging these assumptions?
- What are attitudes toward service-learning by different cultural groups?
- How can service-learning be implemented to frame community from an assets lens?
- What are effective ways for using service-learning projects with the LGBTIQ+ community as a tool to address discrimination (including homophobia).
- How does intergenerational service-learning and community engagement working with elderly populations increase connections to elderly, empathy for elderly and engagement with the elderly?

THEORY/CONCEPTUAL

Conduct research that advances theories or concepts to further understanding of the relationships between service-learning/community engagement and equity/social advancement.

- What are the specific theoretical lenses that are most useful for service learning?
- What are the different definitions of equity by different service-learning groups. Might a typology be created?
- How are the differences between equality and equity addressed in service-learning?

INSTITUTIONAL ISSUES

Investigate issues institutions can address to increase engagement and equity in service-learning and community engagement programs.

- What are the promising practices for equity-focused engagement?
- What is the responsibility of Catholic universities to acknowledge their own complicity in institutional racism? And then through reparations and reconciliation repair these relationships? Can community-engaged learning at Catholic colleges and universities aid in the reconciliation efforts between the Catholic church and native/indigenous communities (in light of the Indian Boarding Schools)?

- How are professional associations and publication outlets/journals uplifting diverse service-learning and community engagement scholars?
- What is the return on investment for community partners who partner in service-learning and community engagement? How do service-learning and community engagement programs add value to their community? What is the economic impact of service-learning and community engagement programs?
- How to develop skills for faculty/students to engage in discussion/address equity issues?
- Where is service-learning part of diversity, inclusion, and equity education, and where is it the vehicle for such education?

VI. CULTURAL/REGIONAL AND CROSS-CULTURAL/CROSS-REGIONAL

Issues that explore service-learning and community engagement practices within and across cultures and regions are to be embraced and discussed, with an eye toward identifying questions or action steps for the research agenda.

The research issues include, but is not limited to:

- conducting research within and across different cultural or geographic settings;
- examining service-learning and community engagement across the educational spectrum;
- community voice;
- multiple frames of service-learning and community engagement.

PLACE

Explore how geographic location and cultural context shape the meanings, practices, and perceptions of service-learning and community engagement.

- Rural vs Urban: Institutions in rural settings present unique challenges for service-learning (especially focused on local issues). How does institutional size versus institutional footprint (area of influence) impact relationship between campus and community?
- Does the research include the perspective of the region/culture? Is it implied in the project? How?
- Can a cross-cultural typology of service-learning and community engagement be defined that incorporates different ways of knowing and doing service-learning/community engagement to apply across contexts or geographies?
- What are the similarities/differences in the community attitude about youth who conduct service-learning? Rural, suburban, urban, in different countries? Are any places more positive about their youth from service-learning than others?
- To inquire the notions of service and service-learning in different cultures and regions (e.g., what does "serve other" mean in a given culture or population)?
- What does service-learning and community engagement look like in different geographical settings? Should it look different in different geographical settings?

POWER AND PRIVILEGE

Investigate how whiteness and dominant cultural norms shape service-learning and community engagement, whose knowledge is valued, and how students—especially those from marginalized communities—experience these practices.

- Service-learning has been criticized as being a pedagogy of whiteness. Have moves been made to change that? Has that criticism been taken seriously?

- How can we make service-learning and community engagement more inclusive, especially for students who may be coming from the communities in which their engagement experiences take place?
- How does community engagement impact understanding of epistemic justice?
- What issues around epistemic justice need to be part of a partnership? Whose knowledge counts? How is it honored and recognized?
- What happens when service-learning/community engagement exacerbates conflict in diverse communities?
- How are power imbalances attended to between university and community?

INSTITUTION, CULTURAL, AND CONTEXTUAL DIFFERENCES

Examine how institutional type, mission, and cultural context shape the rationale, implementation, and impact of service-learning and community engagement.

- What are the rationales of service-learning and community engagement by institution type (community college, public, private, private-religious, etc.)?
- What are the impacts of the similarities and differences among service-learning/community engagement between public and faith-based institutions? Do the impacts change across regions and cultures?
- Implement studies that renew the focus on community colleges, especially in regard to transfer students and adult learners.
- How do we facilitate developing and supporting multi-institutional and multi-national collaborations?
- How can we (maybe IARSLCE) remove barriers to cross-institutional research, which would help encourage more robustness in service-learning/community engagement research and practice.

BARRIERS TO QUALITY/ACCESS

Investigate how language, culture, and hidden norms can limit ethical, effective, and inclusive participation in service-learning and community engagement.

- How do we avoid having dialogue “lost in translation”? Can one do service-learning/community engagement ethically/safely/effectively around massive language barriers? What are the language barriers, if any, that contribute to ineffective experiences?

- Is the burden of cross-cultural communication placed on service-learning partners, or are there examples of a third party facilitating this aspect of service-learning and community engagement work?
- How do we make sure cultural appropriateness/protocol is met before students are sent out to the community? What are best practices in cultivating cultural competency regarding insider and outsider perspective?
- Conduct research in native languages (honor the translation and ways of speaking about subjects and topics).
- How do service-learning/community engagement programs /activities attend to the hidden curriculum—the unspoken or implicit lessons that participants learn on campus and in the community?
- Conduct comparative studies about the language of community engagement, such as different meanings and connotations of words in different languages/contexts (e.g., service, solidarity, social responsibility, social justice, etc.).
- How does the language of engagement affect experiences and outcomes?

PARTICIPATORY AND COMMUNITY-LED PARTNERSHIPS

Explore how service-learning/community engagement and research can center community-defined priorities, honor diverse ways of knowing, and build ethical, culturally humble, and reciprocal partnerships.

- How can researchers collaborate with community partners to ensure full participation, amplify representative voices, and prioritize community-defined needs over academic or Western-imposed perspectives?
- What are best practices for ensuring that community-engaged research is ethical and is not dehumanizing communities. What are best practices for recognizing power differentials when conducting community engagement/service-learning. What harm reduction and sustainability strategies need to be in place?
- What is the role of cultural humility in service-learning and community engagement?
- Why is the academy resistant to community voice and community-led research being thought of as "counting" as valid ways of knowing?
- What are effective strategies for responding to local cultural practices that may be contradictory to research outcomes/goals/ethical practices?
- How is service-learning and community engagement used to address community-identified needs across cultural contexts? How does one build effective partnerships across

cultural difference?

- Is community voice heard more in certain cultures in the service-learning context than in others? Why? For example, How do we ensure a "nothing for us - without us" understanding when entering tribal nations?

CULTURALLY RESPONSIVE STUDENT ENGAGEMENT

Examine how service-learning/community engagement programs recognize and adapt to the diverse cultural, linguistic, racial, and age-related backgrounds of students.

- What value does the community organization place on the partnership or individual facilitating the student experience?
- How do we mitigate the burden of service-learning/community engagement on students of color/underrepresented/marginalized in navigating service-learning? Do students from different racial and cultural backgrounds experience service-learning programs and courses differently?
- Exploring cultural understanding and responsiveness across participants. The acceptability of student voice within certain cultural contexts - Are all voices valued and do all students have agency or empowered to speak, and, contribute?
- Which impact does service-learning/community engagement have on students when they work together with students from other countries who do not speak the same language?
- How can service-learning practice/pedagogy adapt to teaching and learning with non-traditional age students across different cultural and geographic settings?
- In human development terms, the 'culture' of middle schoolers differs greatly from high schoolers and from college-level. How do these differing age-cohort "cultures" shift the needed focus and practices for effective service-learning and community engagement?

TECHNOLOGY FOR CROSS-CULTURAL ENGAGEMENT

Examine how technology and online learning can facilitate deeper understanding and collaboration across diverse cultures.

- What are effective strategies for doing more through online learning and harnessing technology in service-learning/community engagement to gain deeper understandings across cultures?
- Develop cross cultural algorithms that can translate findings from service-learning and community engagement experiences (e.g., artificial intelligence modules).

VII. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORKS AND THEORIES

The field of service-learning and community engagement has been criticized for being under-theorized and for lacking well-developed and well-tested conceptual frameworks.

Research in this area of work focuses on theory testing and building conceptual models and frameworks that explain various phenomena in the study and practice of service-learning and community engagement.

SERVICE-LEARNING/COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT AND THEORIES OF DEVELOPMENT AND IDENTITY

Explore the incorporation of theories of individual, interpersonal, and community development in the study of service-learning and community engagement. This includes advancing questions relating to psychosocial and civic/political development of students, faculty motivational development and identity formation and community partnership development. Research in this area might include the following areas of focus:

- Civic/Political -- Community/Institutional/Societal
 - Psychosocial/Identity -- Individual/Interpersonal
 - Pedagogy/Learning -- Interpersonal/Individual
- What development theories related to faculty, students, and community have informed or been integrated into service-learning/community engagement?
 - How does SLCE affect the identities of service-learning/community engagement participants, if at all?

THEORIES AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORKS DRAWN FROM OTHER DISCIPLINES OR FIELDS

Many theories and conceptual frameworks used in service-learning and community engagement draw from different disciplines and diverse epistemic communities.

- What fields does service-learning/community engagement research draw from? Some examples include:
 - Anthropology
 - Arts and Humanities
 - Black Studies
 - Indigenous Studies
 - Cognitive Development and Cognitive Science
 - Communications
 - Community Development
 - Education & Learning Sciences
 - Ethnic Studies
 - Human Development

- Indigenous Studies
 - Philosophy, Theology, and other relevant disciplines
 - Political Science & Civic Development
 - Professional & Applied Fields: Business, Peace Studies, Architecture, Urban Studies
 - Psychology
 - Public Health
 - Sociology
 - STEM
 - Women's Studies, and others
- What is the current state of the literature in terms of types of theoretical frameworks used and fields from which they are drawn?
 - What is the potential for future cross-disciplinary/cross-theoretical research? How do we critically examine the use of these fields in the context of service-learning and community engagement?
 - To what extent is there convergence around different theories frequently used in the service-learning/community engagement field to substantiate the theory unique to service-learning/community engagement? Where are there gaps?
 - In terms of theory development, what phenomena in the field of service-learning/community engagement are most in need of "explaining?" For example, should service-learning/community engagement connect itself to:
 - theories of human development
 - theories of cognitive processing
 - theories of social change
 - theories of self-efficacy, self-esteem, self-regulation
 - theories of community development
 - theories of learning
 - theories of pedagogy
 - theories of civic development
 - scholarship of teaching and learning
 - epistemology theories of what knowledge counts
 - others?
 - How can service-learning/community engagement locate itself within the various disciplines and areas of study in ways that lend credibility?

THE PRAXIS OF SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

Explore the dialectical nature and interrelationship between theory and practice within the field. It addresses steps and processes of developing theory.

- How are scholars, practitioners, and community members in dialogue during theoretical formation? How do we best approach the development of service-learning/community theory/theories?
- As a dialectical process, what role does practice play to test, validate, and build service-learning/community theories? How is practice valued and recorded?
- What kinds of theories are appropriate for both "doing the work" and "preparing people to do the work"?
- What can be learned from international service-learning/community engagement in terms of practice, theoretical development, and praxis?

POWER, JUSTICE, AND SOCIAL TRANSFORMATION

Examine the ways in which service-learning/community engagement can inform, support, and participate in community change. It considers the ethics of practice and epistemic equity and examines the potential for service-learning and community engagement to move toward greater equity, culturally centered and sustaining practices.

- To what extent is knowledge co-produced between community and university? What is the valuation, possibilities, and limits of disciplinary knowledge versus community-driven knowledge?
 - What are the conceptual frameworks to guide university and community relations that address issues of reciprocity, the role of language, co-creation, and mutual benefit? How does the field address power relations and community change?
 - What theories does service-learning/community engagement apply to understanding community and civic engagement? What and how are the theories being used? What can we learn from the application of these theories to service-learning/community engagement (e.g., democracy/public life, ethics, critical theories, civic participation and awareness, human rights, restorative justice, funds of knowledge, liberation theology, indigenous knowledge, decolonization, social capital)?
 - How can the philosophical framework of epistemic in/justice shape service-learning and community engagement practices at an interpersonal and institutional level?
 - Are current conceptual models of service-learning/community engagement “doing enough” to examine how service-learning/community engagement itself can be a part of a “colonial project” to otherize others?
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EXPERIENTIAL LEARNING AND PEDAGOGIES OF ENGAGEMENT

Examine the scholarship of teaching and pedagogy and inclusive ways to enhance educational experiences and strategies to document, assess, and improve learning experiences. This encompasses different approaches including service-learning, community-engaged learning, community-based curricular and co-curricular learning, and other experiential approaches. It broadly asks, “What theories and approaches to pedagogy inform teaching objectives and learning outcomes?”

- What theories and approaches to pedagogy inform teaching objectives and learning outcomes?
- In what ways does service-learning/community engagement represent a High Impact Practice (HIP) that addresses professional development, career, and/or lifelong learning skills, including public service and civic leadership, collaboration, and cross-cultural communication, among other skills?
- How do instructors frame their pedagogical approach, including the relationship between learning, reflection, and action?
- Does community-engaged learning engage and develop different cognitive and/or affective/emotional capacities than does traditional learning?
- How are service-learning/community engagement learning outcomes similar or different when rooted in diverse fields, such as peace education, experiential education, outdoor education, global education, or learning science?
- How are service-learning/community engagement learning outcomes similar or different when taught using diverse pedagogies such as Ignatian pedagogy, reflection, community-engaged learning, authentic learning, constructivism, problem-solving/project-based learning, liberation, or restorative justice pedagogy?

VIII. METHODOLOGICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The issues in this section focus on identifying the kinds of methods that are appropriate for the study of service-learning and community engagement. The items consider the research designs, methods, epistemologies and approaches that are needed and required in designing and operationalizing future research on service-learning and community engagement.

THE NEED FOR BROADER AND DEEPER RESEARCH METHODOLOGIES

Explore how diverse, hybrid, and interdisciplinary research methodologies—including emerging technologies and culturally responsive approaches—can better capture the complexity of service-learning and community engagement. This area of research calls for innovation, transparency, and collaboration across paradigms to advance more rigorous, inclusive, and scalable service-learning and community engagement scholarship.

- Integrate multiple research paradigms and expand epistemologies in research on service-learning and community engagement. Possible options to consider:
 - system thinking
 - design thinking
 - appreciative inquiry
 - mixed methods
 - biomedical-focused "hard measures" (e.g., blood pressure, quality of life)
 - ripple effect mapping
 - learning analytics
 - multi-level qualitative comparative analysis
 - self-reflexivity
 - participatory writing
 - multi-institutional studies
 - photo voice
 - meta-analyses
 - RICA model rubrics
 - photovoice + photo elicitation,
 - participatory action research (PAR)
 - youth participatory action research (YPAR)
 - case studies
 - literary or textual analysis
 - oral history
 - philosophy
 - archive analysis
 - historical analysis
 - self-reporting
 - auto-ethnographies
 - comidualisms
 - social change methodologies
 - Vygotsky scaffolding theory (zone of proximate development)

- communities of practice
 - grounded theory
 - ethnography,
 - application of AI machine-learning
 - testimony
- Do new technological advances warrant changing our methods of service-learning and community engagement?
 - Optimize technology tools to assess impacts of community-based research.
 - Develop common metrics that are applied across institutions for multi-institutional studies.
 - Conduct studies that make more use of larger-scale institutional data with nuance beyond just groupings of “service-learning” or “not service-learning”.
 - Provide transparency around data collection processes and gaps/limitations in ways that ensure open source.

CRITICAL AND DECOLONIZING METHODOLOGIES

Conduct research on service-learning/community engagement that centers culturally relevant, community-rooted, and justice-oriented approaches that challenge dominant epistemologies, value multiple ways of knowing, and promote equitable, decolonized.

- Approaches that value participants in the field as whole human beings.
 - How can research of scholarship in community engagement be broadened to embrace other ways of knowing, multiple epistemologies, wisdom in the community, etc.? There is a discrepancy between an unexposed desire to develop a more critical social-justice approach in community engagement with equitable mutually beneficial relationships in the community, on the one hand, and the current dominant mechanisms for knowledge sharing (journals, books, conferences, etc.), on the other hand.
 - What epistemologies are being privileged? Who is the audience for our work? How should that change our research lens?
 - What methodologies help us address epistemological injustice?
 - Employ more decolonizing methodologies. Begin with discussions on methods used with communities and methods that are culturally relevant.
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LONGITUDINAL AND SUSTAINABLE IMPACT-FOCUSED RESEARCH

Develop inclusive, long-term strategies to assess the sustained impact of service-learning and community engagement on students, community partners, and institutions, while ensuring findings are shared accessibly and meaningfully with all stakeholders.

- Develop strategies for assessing impact on the long-term in relation to student development, community impact on capacity building, and faculty development.
- Conduct more program impact studies that include comparisons pre/post implementation.
- Survey community partners in follow-up surveys to assess the long-term impact of service-learning experiences on communities and partners.
- Conduct longitudinal studies to see long term effects on students (e.g., longitudinal studies with graduates)? Include a control group of students who were not engaged.
- How can we involve community members and/or partners in framing and give meaning to the direction of the "right" impacts?
- How do we share results of impact studies beyond traditional academic means (e.g., accessible to community partners, students, admin, faculty, and other stakeholders)?
- Optimize program evaluations should as they are often more valuable to partners than research.

COMMUNITY CO-RESEARCH, RECIPROCITY, AND EMPOWERMENT

Explore effective strategies for conducting community-engaged research that is co-created with partners through participatory, culturally grounded methods that prioritize reciprocal relationships, empower local knowledge, and ensure shared ownership of impact, analysis, and communication.

- Co-producing knowledge with the community is the key.
- Involve community members and/or partners in framing and give meaning to the direction of the "right" impacts.
- Work in tandem with community partners to create assessments that show the program's efficacy and long-term impact on clients/participants.
- Be adoptive to local knowledge creation methods and infuse.
- Examine the perception of community members on the institution's community involvement and impact.

- Be attentive to partner contributions (e.g., strengths, asset-based approaches).
 - Explore models or practices that have been successful in creating a balance between asking about community needs and leveraging community capacity.
 - How can research be presented so that practitioners and non-research people will understand the method and analysis?
 - Use participatory action research that is community-led to allow for more community impact.
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STUDENT-FOCUSED STUDIES

Investigate how students—including youth—engage in and are impacted by service-learning/community engagement. Explore research models, long-term outcomes, and new tools for assessing reflection, competencies, and academic or civic development across educational stages.

- How are/could secondary students be engaged in service-learning research? K-12 students love doing the investigation and subsequent action, etc., but often resist or do not understand the need for more formal research on what and how they are doing and what they are doing.
- Measure the development of democratic and intercultural competencies of the people who work for the service sites using the RICA model, adjusted for this purpose.
- Link community engagement/service-learning metrics to students' analytics work.
- Develop better mechanisms and strategies that facilitate the use of student reflections to assess student outcomes. What are effective strategies for students to share what they learned and to describe their partnership with community members/organizations.
- Explore opportunities for colleges, community organizations, and companies to offer case studies and data about how their employees'/personnel's experience with service-learning during K-12 or higher education has impacted performance?

IX. INSTRUMENTS AND MEASURES

Securing quality research requires valid and appropriate instruments and measures that can secure the best data and provide opportunities for thorough, systematic analyses. Many of the instruments that have been developed for the study of service-learning and community engagement are home grown instruments that are often applied to single studies and are not cultivated further for potential use in other studies. In addition, there are many instruments that are available for studies of service-learning and community engagement, but it is sometimes unclear regarding the suitability of such instruments for programs or populations for which they were not initially designed.

The research agenda identifies issues for improving the instrumentation and measurement of service-learning and community engagement across the many contexts in which the work takes place.

INSTRUMENT QUALITY

Develop instruments that have greater fidelity, reliability, and validity of implementation and measurement.

- Which instruments have been most effective in measuring outcomes and impact of service-learning and community engagement?
- Develop a strategy for building knowledge of which instruments and measures are used most frequently in service-learning and community engagement.
- Instruments should be accompanied with details on who developed them and how they were developed.
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CULTURAL APPROPRIATENESS

Strike a balance between standardized and contextualized instruments in the conduct of research on service-learning and community engagement, especially when the investigations are community-centered.

- What adaptations of instruments have been used effectively to address certain communities' cultural practices?
- How can service-learning and community engagement integrate what community partners want to measure about the impact of partnerships?
- What types of instruments and measures do K-12 teachers prefer to utilize in studies of K-12 service-learning? Which are the most effective?

- Which types of instruments and methods do students prefer to be evaluated and to show their progress? Likert Scales, journals, quizzes, etc.?
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ACCESS TO PROMISING PRACTICES, INSTRUMENTS, AND DATABASES

Expand access to a broad range of instruments and measures that can be used to advance research on service-learning and community engagement.

- Create a repository and taxonomy of tools and instruments that includes lists and inventories of validated instruments as well as unique and diverse types of instruments and measures, such as:
 - trauma-informed measures
 - tools for scholarly personal narratives
 - global engagement surveys
 - attitude and affective change thermometers
 - Develop effective ways for researchers and constituents to access promising practices, instruments, and databases.
-

RESEARCH, ORGANIZATIONAL, INSTITUTIONAL, CROSS-SECTOR, AND INTERDISCIPLINARY COLLABORATIONS

Establish stronger networks across platforms and organizations to coordinate information sharing.

- Develop partnership with leading service-learning and community engagement organizations (e.g., Campus Compact, Carnegie, National Youth Leadership Council, others) to strategically collect data from across sites and programs that could then be used by researchers.
- Explore ways to collect standardized data that allows for more longitudinal studies.
- Adapt and incorporate instruments from related fields. For example, explore ways that the Youth Program Quality Assessment (YPQA), which is used by community youth programs, might be applied to studies of K-12 service-learning.

X. REPLICATION

No one study provides all the evidence, understanding, or knowledge that is needed to draw firm conclusions about service-learning or community engagement. Replication is a critical feature of scientific inquiry and research.

Only a handful of service-learning and community engagement studies have been replicated. Replicating high quality studies is a way to strengthen evidence and secure more conclusive findings about the strengths and limitations of service-learning and community engagement practices, outcomes, and approaches.

REPLICATION PROCESS

Develop processes for replicating different kinds of studies on service-learning and community engagement.

- What are key considerations and standards for replication for the different types of studies.
- What data sets, methods, and procedures should be used in study replications? What are contextual considerations?
- What standards and incentives need to be in place for replications to occur?
- Focus on localized contexts. Service-learning and community engagement are not the same across contexts.
- Replicate localized studies in global contexts.
- Share instruments to compare generalizability of data collected

REPLICATION PHILOSOPHY

Establish a clear justification and rationale of why research studies should be replicated.

- Replication is important so long as conforming variables are not perpetuated. Critical peer reviews need to be accounted for.
 - Need to incorporate more of a critical lens of inclusion when it comes to replicating studies.
 - Service-learning and community engagement populations and contexts are so unique. Can studies really be fully replicated in their totality? What are the considerations for replicating a study in a different context?
 - Explore meta-analyses instead of replications.
-

UNDER-STUDIED AREAS FOR STUDY REPLICATION

Replicate studies on topics and issues for which there is limited information.

- Replicate studies focused on the effects of service-learning on students with disabilities. For example, studies by Brill (1994) and Burns (1999).
- Replicate studies focusing more on subgroups than on generalized groups.
- Conduct replication of studies in fields that examine Catholic focused themes.

REPLICATION OF SPECIFIC STUDIES AND TESTING OF INSTRUMENTS AND SCALES

Replicate high quality studies and further test instruments and scales that have provided useful information on key issues in service-learning and community engagement.

- Develop a list of the studies that have had the greatest impact (the most used/cited) and replicate those.
- Replicate evidence gathered in the 1990s. How have the student body, community needs (local and global) changed over the past 30 years? Repeat studies with more diverse student, faculty, institution types.
- Conduct replications of published studies that have shown positive impacts and outcomes of service-learning and community engagement, such as:
 - UCLA Higher Education Research Institute (HERI) study (Astin et al.)
 - Eyler and Giles study from *Where's the Learning in Service-Learning?*
 - Kiely study on the Chameleon Complex
 - Furco et al. study on impact of service-learning and community engagement on underrepresented students' retention
 - Holland study on how service-learning has spread across institutions
 - Bringle et al. study on empathetic justice
 - Restinger and Clifford study on transformative learning
 - Matthews, Dorfman, & Wu study that looks at salary and employment outcomes from undergraduates who participated in service-learning
- Further test service-learning and community instruments and measures that show promise. For example:
 - Civic-Minded Graduate/Professional Scale (Steinberg)
 - K-12 Service-Learning Standards (National Youth Leadership Council)
 - American Association of Colleges and Universities Scoring Collaborative
 - DEAL Model (Clayton and Ash)

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ALBUQUERQUE, NEW MEXICO (October 21, 2019)

Hosted by the International Association for Research on Service-Learning and Community Engagement (IARSLCE) and the University of New Mexico

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VIRTUAL (March 27, 2020)

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MINNEAPOLIS, MINNESOTA (April 21, 2022)

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HONOLULU, HAWAII (March 16, 2023)

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NEW ORLEANS, LOUISIANA (October 24, 2023)

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Hosted by Northeastern University

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Analysis Meeting #3: San Diego, California (May 30, 2025)

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This work has been considered by the University of Minnesota Human Research Protection Program (United States) and deemed as “not human research”, per record STUDY00025524.

**AGENDA GLOBAL DE INVESTIGACIÓN
PARA EL APRENDIZAJE-SERVICIO Y
COMPROMISO COMUNITARIO**

**REGIÓN
AMÉRICA LATINA/
AMÉRICA DEL SUR
(VERSIÓN EN ESPAÑOL)**

Agenda Global de Investigación para el Aprendizaje-Servicio y Compromiso Comunitario

REGIÓN AMÉRICA LATINA/ AMÉRICA DEL SUR

Esta parte de la agenda global de investigación se basa en el análisis de 924 preguntas y temas de investigación presentados por 111 personas de varios países latinoamericanos y más allá que participaron en cuatro foros en español celebrados en Argentina, Chile y México entre agosto de 2019 y agosto de 2023. Las preguntas y temas fueron categorizados y priorizados en junio de 2025 por 43 personas de Argentina, Brasil, Chile, Ecuador y México.

I. INCIDENCIA/IMPACTO

La investigación de impacto se centra en evaluar el impacto del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario (y otras formas del compromiso social) en los participantes, incluyendo estudiantes, profesorado, personal, instituciones y la comunidad. Aborda una amplia gama de resultados a corto y largo plazo.

ESTUDIANTES

La categoría estudiantes aborda el impacto del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario en el desarrollo integral de los estudiantes. Se exploran las competencias adquiridas —tanto genéricas como profesionales, éticas y ciudadanas—, su relación con el rendimiento académico, la apropiación de saberes teóricos y el sentido de pertenencia institucional, tanto a corto como a largo plazo. Además, se consideran dimensiones como la autoeficacia, los valores y el proyecto de vida, particularmente en estudiantes de primera generación y de la Generación Z.

- ¿Qué competencias adquieren los estudiantes que participan en aprendizaje-servicio y las prácticas del compromiso comunitario?

- ¿Qué relación existe entre la participación en actividades de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario y el desarrollo de habilidades de aprendizaje, la apropiación de contenidos teóricos y el rendimiento académico de los estudiantes?
- ¿Cómo perciben los estudiantes el impacto del aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario en su desarrollo integral, considerando competencias, emociones, valores, autoeficacia y proyecto de vida?
- ¿Qué efectos tiene el aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario en las competencias de los estudiantes, incluyendo su formación ética, ciudadana y profesional?
- ¿Cómo se comparan las experiencias de aprendizaje-servicio y otras formas de servicio estudiantil en su impacto sobre los valores, el sentido de pertenencia y la trayectoria universitaria de estudiantes de primera generación y de la Generación Z?
- ¿Cómo incide la participación en experiencias de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario en el desarrollo y la transferencia de competencias genéricas hacia nuevos contextos profesionales, y qué impacto tiene en la formación ética, ciudadana y el proyecto de vida de los estudiantes universitarios a lo largo del tiempo?
- ¿Cómo perciben los estudiantes el impacto social que tienen en la comunidad con los proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio en los que participan?

DOCENTES

La categoría Docentes analiza el impacto del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario en las prácticas, trayectorias y condiciones de su trabajo. Se consideran las barreras institucionales y pedagógicas que enfrentan, así como las transformaciones en su rol, competencias profesionales, identidad docente y sentido de pertenencia. Además, se exploran formas de colaboración y reflexión crítica que fortalecen su desarrollo profesional y el compromiso con la comunidad educativa.

- ¿Cuáles son las principales dificultades institucionales, pedagógicas y contextuales que enfrentan las/os docentes al integrar el aprendizaje-servicio o el compromiso comunitario en sus prácticas de enseñanza?
- ¿De qué manera el aprendizaje-servicio transforma el rol docente y promueve nuevas formas de colaboración pedagógica e institucional en el ámbito universitario?
- ¿Cómo incide la participación en proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio en el desarrollo profesional del cuerpo docente universitario, considerando la construcción colaborativa de conocimiento, la práctica reflexiva, la adquisición de competencias y el fortalecimiento de su identidad, sentido de pertenencia institucional y compromiso educativo?
- ¿Cómo contribuye el AS o el compromiso comunitario en el desarrollo de la conciencia y responsabilidad social de los docentes?

COMUNIDAD

Estos elementos se centran en cuestiones relacionadas con el análisis cualitativo y cuantitativo de los impactos en la comunidad, los cambios producidos en términos positivos y negativos, la participación de estudiantes y de socios comunitarios y en la sostenibilidad de las acciones.

- ¿De qué forma promover la construcción de conocimiento socialmente relevante con los espacios comunitarios considerando: los cambios concretos provocados, las características de los socios comunitarios, los efectos a largo plazo?
- ¿De qué forma medir cuantitativamente el impacto del aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario en la comunidad? Construcción de indicadores que permitan evidenciar resultados e impacto social en la comunidad por la intervención de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario.
- ¿Cómo se construye la figura de la organización comunitaria como co-formadora de los estudiantes y qué relaciones se establecen luego de las experiencias de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario? ¿Cómo impacta en la formación ciudadana?
- ¿Cómo evaluar la sostenibilidad de los cambios con posterioridad a la implementación de los proyectos, contemplando estrategias para la continuidad, procesos a largo plazo y el papel de la comunidad en la resolución de las problemáticas?
- ¿Cuál es el impacto social en la comunidad, de las alianzas intersectoriales de los proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
- ¿Cómo identificar los riesgos y daños que puedan provocar nuestras intervenciones comunitarias?

INSTITUCIONAL

Estas preguntas de investigación abordan cómo la institucionalización del aprendizaje-servicio solidario y compromiso comunitario transforma la gestión y cultura institucional. Indagan los cambios en las propuestas pedagógicas, en la construcción de redes y los procesos de internacionalización para el fortalecimiento del compromiso social.

- ¿Cómo impacta el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario en la gestión y cultura institucional, considerando a los distintos actores, los enfoques metodológicos utilizados, los marcos normativos, las perspectivas epistemológicas sobre lo social y los desafíos que influyen en su sostenibilidad y expansión?

- ¿Cómo se construyen relaciones de transversalidad entre espacios curriculares que abordan o no problemáticas comunitarias?
- ¿Cómo influye el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario y a través de espacios de intercambio y socialización entre países, a la construcción de la identidad profesional y en los procesos de internacionalización de las instituciones educativas?
- ¿Cómo impacta el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario y en las modificaciones curriculares y en las prácticas pedagógicas?
- ¿Cómo contribuyen las redes colaborativas entre la universidad y otras entidades al proceso de institucionalización del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario?
- ¿Cómo influye el AS y el compromiso comunitario en posicionar a la universidad como actor relevante en la resolución de problemas sociales en el territorio donde opera?

INVESTIGACIÓN

Las preguntas de investigación propuestas integran distintos niveles de análisis del impacto en el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario, vinculando la evaluación de impacto y calidad educativa, los enfoques metodológicos, las consideraciones conceptuales y la reflexión ontológica.

- ¿Cómo considerar los indicadores de calidad educativa en las experiencias de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario y en su impacto a largo plazo, teniendo en cuenta los efectos colaterales y no deseados?
- ¿Cómo inciden los enfoques metodológicos en la relación entre investigador y quienes son objeto de investigación -con su realidad y su cultura- y en la validación de resultados a lo largo del tiempo?
- ¿Cómo influyen los enfoques epistemológicos y metodológicos en la manera en que distintos actores educativos perciben, definen y diferencian el impacto y la contribución en su comunidad?
- ¿Cuáles son los factores determinantes que influyen en el impacto de las experiencias de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario en los distintos actores (estudiantes, docentes y comunidad), y cómo los enfoques interdisciplinarios y los diversos métodos pueden potenciar dicho impacto?
- ¿Cómo influyen las perspectivas sobre "el otro" y lo social en la construcción del impacto y los resultados de las experiencias de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario, y qué modelo de mundo subyace a dichas representaciones?

II. IMPLEMENTACIÓN

La investigación sobre implementación se centra en examinar las prácticas de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario, así como su eficacia para alcanzar objetivos específicos. Los estudios de implementación buscan mejorar la práctica y brindar orientación sobre las mejores prácticas en una amplia gama de enfoques programáticos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario.

La agenda de investigación identifica preguntas centradas en el proceso de impartir aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario en una amplia gama de contextos comunitarios, culturales, geográficos, disciplinarios e institucionales.

DIAGNÓSTICO

Estas preguntas se centran en los diagnósticos.

- ¿Cómo asegurar diagnósticos participativos para generar proyectos con sentido?
- ¿Cómo puede efectuarse de forma efectiva la detección de:
 - a) necesidades y capacidades del entorno;
 - b) Capacidades y necesidades de la universidad y
 - c) el match entre estas?
- ¿Cómo se sabe si el servicio que estoy proporcionando es realmente beneficioso para determinada comunidad? ¿Qué estudios previos puedo hacer?
- ¿Qué aspectos éticos y de seguridad deben tenerse en cuenta e implementarlos? ¿Cómo se consideran en los distintos contextos/países?
- ¿Qué estrategias y herramientas son útiles para conocer los objetivos y necesidades de la comunidad?
- ¿Cuál es el mejor modelo para trabajar con el socio comunitario (pasos, objetivos, logros) para obtener mejores resultados?

COMUNIDAD

Estas preguntas se centran en el vínculo con la comunidad.

- ¿Cómo involucrar a la comunidad en procesos co-construidos?
- ¿Cómo vincularse con la comunidad de forma sistemática?
- ¿Qué es comunidad o realidad, dónde está el límite?

- ¿Cómo generar espacios de intercambio que favorezcan el trabajo en red entre organizaciones de la comunidad?
 - ¿Cuáles son las mejores prácticas para la participación de los beneficiarios finales en el proyecto de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
 - ¿Cómo podemos evitar el asistencialismo?
-

MOTIVACIÓN

Estas preguntas se centran en cómo motivar a los estudiantes, al profesorado y a la comunidad.

- ¿Cómo motivar a los maestros a que se involucren en aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
 - ¿Cómo poder lograr que los estudiantes se comprometan con el proyecto de servicio?
 - ¿Cómo motivar a los miembros de la comunidad a compartir problemas personales u otros aspectos delicados que pueden ser útiles para la implementación del proyecto, pero los miembros no están dispuestas a hablar sobre esos temas? ¿Cómo no herir sus sentimientos y no invadir su esfera personal ni intimidarlos?
 - ¿Cómo atraer a los líderes de la comunidad para lograr el efecto del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario?
-

ROL DOCENTE

Preguntas orientadas a identificar habilidades y herramientas necesarias para el docente.

- ¿Cuáles son los conocimientos y habilidades de docentes que deben ser profundizados/modificados para acompañar las experiencias y avanzar la colaboración entre organizaciones?
 - ¿Qué habilidades deben formarse en los docentes?
 - ¿Cómo se forma a los docentes para fomentar la práctica reflexiva?
 - ¿Cuánto influye la capacitación docente en una buena experiencia de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
-

SOLIDARIDAD

Examinar el rol y la importancia del concepto de solidaridad en aprendizaje-servicio.

- ¿Como incorporar la dimensión de la solidaridad (y su significado según el contexto) en el diseño y la ejecución de un proyecto.
 - ¿Cómo se interpreta la concepto de “solidaridad” según cada contexto?
-

MULTI /INTERDISCIPLINA

Preguntas relativas a el enfoque que debe darse en los proyectos interdisciplinarios, y cómo evaluarlos.

- ¿Cómo encontrar los puntos de encuentro entre disciplinas?
 - ¿Cómo se le da seguimiento al servicio si hay muchas disciplinas involucradas?
 - ¿En qué medida los estudiantes que participan en una experiencia de aprendizaje-servicio o compromiso comunitario con un enfoque interdisciplinario tienen que involucrarse en el aprendizaje de contenidos o métodos de una carrera que no es la suya?
-

NUEVAS TECNOLOGÍAS

Examinar el uso de nuevas tecnologías en la implementación de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario.

- ¿La incorporación de nuevas tecnologías en la implementación de distintas etapas de los proyectos, por ejemplo el uso de la IA, mejora el impacto de los mismos?
 - ¿El uso de nuevas herramientas tecnológicas mejora significativamente todas o algunas de las distintas etapas de un proyecto de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario? (¿Cuáles herramientas?/¿Cuáles etapas? ¿En todos los casos?).
-

TIEMPOS

Preguntas orientadas a identificar los momentos y la duración necesaria para implementar.

- ¿Cuál es el mejor momento del curso para involucrar a los estudiantes en el aprendizaje-servicio o compromiso comunitario? ¿Desde el primer año o más adelante?
- ¿Cuáles son los tiempos ideales para el diagnóstico, desarrollo y conclusiones de los proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio o compromiso comunitario?

- ¿Cuánto tiempo durante el semestre se debe dedicar al aprendizaje de la teoría para preparar a los estudiantes para prestar un servicio de alta calidad?
-

REFLEXIÓN

Examen del desarrollo de la reflexión en los proyectos.

- ¿Cómo lograr reflexión profundas y críticas en los estudiantes?
-

COMUNICACIÓN

Preguntas vinculadas a la comunicación al interior y hacia fuera de la institución.

- Generar líneas directos entre las autoridades educativas y las escuelas y comunidades.
 - Escuche atentamente a los estudiantes.
 - ¿Cómo implementar el social, familiar y los puntos de encuentro entre disciplinas?
-

APRENDIZAJES

Explorar la importancia del aprendizaje-servicio y la participación comunitaria en el currículo.

- ¿Cuál es la mejor manera de integrar el aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario en el currículo escolar?
-

RECURSOS

Examen de la importancia de los recursos.

- ¿De dónde provienen los fondos de financiamiento para apoyar las actividades y el desarrollo del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario?

III. INSTITUCIONALIZACIÓN

La investigación sobre institucionalización se centra en examinar los factores que promueven la sostenibilidad y la institucionalización del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario en contextos institucionales y comunitarios.

Los estudios en esta área buscan conceptualizar la idea de institucionalización a la luz de los contextos cambiantes de las instituciones educativas y los diversos enfoques del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario.

INSTITUCIONALIZACIÓN Y SUS MODELOS

Esta categoría explora los modelos de institucionalización del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario en instituciones de diferentes niveles de los sistemas educativos. La pregunta de investigación “¿Cómo institucionalizar el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario en distintos contextos?” se centra en identificar metodologías, estrategias y procesos para integrarlo de manera formal dentro de diversas instituciones y comunidades. El tema refiere a la comprensión de los factores que promueven que esta práctica educativa se mantenga a lo largo del tiempo, adaptándose a las particularidades culturales y estructurales de cada lugar.

Se busca explorar los elementos clave que deben considerarse para lograr la institucionalización del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario, como el marco normativo y legal, y cómo este puede influir en el proceso. Además, refiere a investigar sobre la calidad de los planes, programas y proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario, así como los desafíos y dificultades que surgen durante la institucionalización. La investigación también se orienta a recopilar experiencias de institucionalización en diferentes países (exitosas o no exitosas), reconociendo que cada contexto presenta sus particularidades. En síntesis, este tema busca proporcionar una guía práctica y conceptual sobre cómo consolidar el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario para que no dependa de iniciativas individuales, sino que se convierta en parte integral de la cultura y la estructura de las instituciones educativas y las comunidades.

- ¿Cómo institucionalizamos el aprendizaje-servicio solidario y el compromiso comunitario en distintos contextos?
- ¿Qué estrategias deben implementarse para lograr la institucionalización?
- ¿Cuáles son las estrategias que aumentan la participación docente?
- ¿Qué estructura organizacional es la ideal para coordinar la estrategia a nivel universidad?
- ¿Qué relación hay entre la institucionalización y el marco normativo/legal que promueve esa institucionalización?
- ¿Cómo evitar la mercantilización de la "solidaridad" desde la lectura institucional?

- ¿Qué elementos o aspectos debemos considerar para decir que se ha logrado institucionalizar la propuesta de aprendizaje-servicio solidario y compromiso comunitario?
- ¿Cuáles son los elementos que debe analizar para establecer la institucionalización?
¿Cómo se rastrea?
- ¿Las normativas o aspectos legales mejoran la institucionalización de la propuesta de aprendizaje-servicio solidario y compromiso comunitario?
- Recopilar experiencias de institucionalización en cada país (ahondar en la cultura de cada lugar tiene sus propias dificultades). Considero que la institucionalización tiene sus pormenores en la coyuntura cultural de cada lugar. Creo que amerita hacer mayor cantidad de investigaciones acerca de los procesos de institucionalización.
- ¿Qué procesos (qué pasos) son efectivos en la institucionalización en cada región?
- ¿Cómo problematizar el concepto de institucionalización para encontrar sus elementos más apropiados?

SOSTENIBILIDAD Y BARRERAS

Esta categoría explora cómo sostener en el tiempo los procesos de institucionalización del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario; analizando, por ejemplo, recursos y decisiones. Este tema de investigación explora la capacidad de las instituciones educativas para mantener y consolidar los *cambios y las reformas* que implementan a lo largo del tiempo. No se trata solo de introducir nuevas políticas o programas, sino de asegurar que estas innovaciones se integren de manera permanente en la estructura, la cultura y el funcionamiento diario de la institución. El foco está puesto en cómo las instituciones logran que estos procesos no sean iniciativas aisladas o temporales, sino que se conviertan en *prácticas arraigadas y sostenibles*.

Esto implica analizar diversos factores, tales como:

- ⇒ *Liderazgo y gobernanza*: Cómo el liderazgo institucional facilita o dificulta la continuidad de los cambios.
- ⇒ *Cultura organizacional*: El papel de los valores, creencias y normas compartidas en la aceptación y permanencia de las nuevas prácticas.
- ⇒ *Recursos y capacidades*: La disponibilidad y gestión de los recursos humanos, financieros y tecnológicos para sostener los procesos institucionalizados.
- ⇒ *Participación y compromiso*: La implicación de la comunidad educativa (docentes, estudiantes, personal administrativo, familias) en la apropiación y el mantenimiento de las reformas.
- ⇒ *Marcos normativos y políticas*: La influencia de las regulaciones internas y externas en la estabilidad de los procesos.
- ⇒ *Evaluación y adaptación*: La capacidad de la institución para monitorear el progreso, identificar desafíos y ajustar las estrategias para asegurar la sostenibilidad.

En síntesis, la investigación busca entender qué hace que una institución educativa pueda *capitalizar sus esfuerzos de cambio* y evitar que las innovaciones se diluyan o desaparezcan con el tiempo, garantizando así un impacto duradero en la calidad y pertinencia de la educación que ofrece.

- ¿Cómo se construye el compromiso docente para generar sostenibilidad?
- ¿Cuál es el rol de los profesores, estudiantes, administrativos, decanos, coordinadores, rector, en la institución para avanzar en la institucionalización del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario?
- ¿Quiénes deben liderar las estrategias?
- ¿Qué incentivos o mecanismos de promoción existen para docentes para promover las estrategia?
- ¿Hay incentivos económicos u otros reconocimientos para los/las docentes líderes del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario? ¿Cómo se selecciona y cómo se vinculan con los socios comunitarios?
- ¿Qué apoyo se brinda a los maestros para la aplicación de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
- ¿Cómo implementar un programa de dedicación especial para ayudar a docentes y profesores a aumentar su interés en el aprendizaje y servicio y el compromiso comunitario?
- ¿Qué apoyos a docentes favorecen buenas prácticas institucionales?
- ¿Cómo puede la dirección universitaria potenciar los proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario en un contexto con limitaciones económicas?
- ¿Cuáles son las estrategias que aumentan la participación docente?
- ¿Cómo entendemos y honramos (compensamos) la labor invisible del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario (docentes, socios comunitarios, estudiantes)?
- ¿Cuáles son los dificultades y retos para la institucionalización?
- ¿Qué "peligros" están latentes en la institucionalización?
- Definición de retos para la institucionalización dentro de las organizaciones.
- ¿Es la existencia de diferentes facultades con diferentes subculturas un obstáculo para institucionalizar el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario? ¿Qué ocurre con una misma universidad dispersa por todo el país?

- ¿Cómo se pueden reducir las barreras institucionales a la recompensa del personal docente para incentivar un mayor uso del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario?
- ¿Cuáles son los riesgos de institucionalizar el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario en la universidad?
- ¿Qué limitaciones trae consigo la institucionalización del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario para estudiante, docente, y comunidad?
- ¿Cómo la institución puede proveer recursos económicos para el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario y asignarlos de una manera equitativa?
- ¿Cuáles son los incentivos que deben institucionalizarse para asegurar que suceda de manera intermitente?
- ¿Los mecanismos de financiación no contemplan la participación comunitaria y el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario a largo plazo.
- ¿Cómo cambiamos el sistema de recompensas a largo plazo, de reconocimiento a socios y de personal académico (profesional) con agendas muy ocupadas?
- ¿Cómo se construyen demandas intra institucionales para dar al aprendizaje-servicio y al compromiso comunitario sostenibilidad?
- ¿Qué elementos deben ser considerados para mantener la sostenibilidad del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario?
- ¿Cómo deben prepararse y entrenarse a los profesores para una adecuada implementación sustentable?
- ¿Cuáles son las prácticas docentes que permiten mantener en el tiempo proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio solidario y el compromiso comunitario?
- ¿Cuáles son las dimensiones críticas para la sostenibilidad del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario en un departamento o carrera? ¿En diferentes áreas?
- ¿Cómo hicieron las instituciones educativas para mantener vivo el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario?
- ¿Cuáles son los elementos que definen que el aprendizaje-servicio o el compromiso comunitario ha sido institucionalizado?
- ¿Qué estudios se pueden realizar para conocer si el impacto en el servicio se va a sustentar a largo plazo?
- ¿Cómo quitar tanta burocracia para tener apoyo económico de la institución?
- ¿Cómo detectar las materias factibles?

INSTITUCIONALIZACIÓN Y SOCIOS COMUNITARIOS, Y PROTAGONISMO DE LOS ESTUDIANTES EN LA INSTITUCIONALIZACIÓN

La categoría en cuestión se refiere a aspectos que, aunque no siempre son el foco principal en las preguntas analizadas, son fundamentales para el desarrollo completo y sostenible de los procesos de institucionalización del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario en las instituciones educativas y sus socios comunitarios.

Socios Comunitarios: Analiza la naturaleza y el impacto de las relaciones colaborativas y recíprocas entre las instituciones educativas y las organizaciones o comunidades externas. La investigación en esta área explora cómo se establecen, mantienen y evalúan estas alianzas para que sean equitativas, beneficiosas para ambas partes y contribuyan a la calidad del aprendizaje y del servicio ofrecido. Se busca entender cómo la voz y las necesidades de la comunidad se integran genuinamente en el diseño y desarrollo de los proyectos de compromiso comunitario y aprendizaje-servicio.

Protagonismo Estudiantil: Examina el rol activo y significativo de los estudiantes en todas las fases de los proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario. Esto implica investigar cómo se fomenta su agencia, liderazgo y responsabilidad en la identificación de necesidades comunitarias, el diseño de soluciones, la implementación de acciones y la reflexión sobre su aprendizaje y el impacto social. El foco está en cómo los estudiantes se convierten en agentes de cambio y en cómo la experiencia de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario potencia su desarrollo personal, académico y cívico.

En resumen, esta categoría de investigación busca comprender cómo las instituciones educativas pueden sostener y escalar el aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario de forma que promueva una auténtica colaboración con la comunidad y un empoderamiento real de los estudiantes, transformando así la práctica educativa y el compromiso social de la institución.

- ¿Hay institucionalización del aprendizaje-servicio o el compromiso comunitario en los socios comunitarios (OSC)?
- ¿Qué modelos de alianzas con la comunidad favorecen la institucionalización?
- ¿Cuáles son las mejores maneras de facilitar la participación de los estudiantes en aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
- ¿Qué características están presentes en las universidades que exigen que todo estudiante participe en el aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
- ¿Cuánto tiempo será el indicado para realizar la capacitación en la comunidad para que estos hagan suyo el proyecto?
- ¿Cómo institucionalizar el aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario en las distintas escuelas?

- ¿Cómo documentar las evidencias de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario desarrolladas en la comunidad a nivel institucional?
- ¿Es posible articular el desarrollo del aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario en las universidades con su desarrollo en los niveles educativos anteriores?
- ¿Puede haber institucionalización en el nivel de comunitaria? ¿Podemos tener institucionalización entre el socio comunitario o puede el socio comunitario institucionalizarse después de varios compromisos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
- ¿Cómo institucionalizar en la comunidad?
- ¿Cómo se refleja la institucionalización del aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario en nuestras universidades en la forma como los profesores evalúan el proceso de aprendizaje?
- Socialización a la comunidad y participación democrática.

IV. COVID/POST-COVID

Preguntas y problemas que exploran las prácticas de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario durante y después de la COVID-19.

Los problemas pueden incluir, entre otros:

- nuevas prácticas emergentes para el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario derivadas de la pandemia;
- cambios en la realización de investigaciones sobre el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario debido a la COVID-19;
- Impacto de la COVID-19 en la calidad del aprendizaje-servicio y del compromiso comunitario; y
- Ventajas y desventajas de implementar el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario durante o después de la COVID-19.

TECNOLOGÍAS EN LOS PROYECTOS DE APRENDIZAJE-SERVICIO SOLIDARIO

Los elementos priorizados se enfocan en el uso de las tecnologías y el papel de la virtualidad en el desarrollo de proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario, partiendo del escenario abierto por la pandemia de COVID-19. Las preguntas que integran esta categoría refieren a cómo aprovechar herramientas digitales para implementar o evaluar el aprendizaje-servicio solidario y compromiso comunitario, y los beneficios y límites de la virtualidad en experiencias de aprendizaje-servicio solidario.

- ¿Qué poblaciones se benefician más del servicio online? ¿Existen poblaciones que solo pueden beneficiarse del aprendizaje-servicio o compromiso comunitario en línea?
- ¿Las actividades virtuales proporcionan un mayor número de socios comunitarios?
- ¿Cómo aprovechar las facilidades que la tecnología ofrece para mejorar las experiencias de aprendizaje y servicio?
- ¿Cuál es el aporte del trabajo virtual en los proyectos/actividades de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario de los estudiantes?
- ¿Cuál es la eficacia del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario online para sustentar su continuidad en relación con los resultados de aprendizaje institucional esperados y los atributos de los graduados?
- ¿Cómo hacer vinculación con el medio en un territorio “virtual”?
- ¿Qué aprendimos de la modalidad remota (COVID) para los proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?

PRESENCIAL/VIRTUAL

Estos elementos se centran en la comparación y articulación entre modalidades presenciales y virtuales en proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario; y en cómo varía el diseño metodológico según la modalidad (presencial, virtual o híbrida).

- ¿Cómo decidir qué prácticas son las más adecuadas (presencial/online) para obtener la mejor experiencia de aprendizaje?
- ¿Cuáles son los posibles resultados del aprendizaje de los estudiantes en relación con el desarrollo de un servicio presencial y con el virtual?
- ¿Tiene el contacto cara a cara efectos diferenciales sobre los resultados de los aprendizajes de los estudiantes y la comunidad?

IMPACTO DEL COVID EN LOS APRENDIZAJES Y LAS PRÁCTICAS DEL APRENDIZAJE-SERVICIO SOLIDARIO Y COMPROMISO COMUNITARIO

Estos elementos se centran en comprender cómo la pandemia de COVID-19 afectó los modos de enseñar, aprender y vincularse solidariamente con la comunidad en el marco de proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario.

- ¿Qué prácticas de aprendizaje-servicio solidarios y compromiso comunitario surgidas durante la COVID perduran y benefician las prácticas actuales?
- ¿Qué prácticas surgieron durante la COVID que ampliaron la capacidad institucional y estudiantil para participar en aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
- ¿Cuáles son los nuevos procesos de intervención comunitaria tras el COVID?
- ¿Cómo la experiencia del COVID ayudó a realizar cambios en la política de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario de la institución?
- ¿Cómo se han profundizado las necesidades de la comunidad a través del impacto del COVID (educación, interacción social, economía, salud)?
- ¿Cuáles fueron los resultados inesperados del aprendizaje-servicio durante la COVID? ¿Fueron positivos? ¿Hubo más autorreflexión?

- ¿Cuáles son las ventajas y desventajas del aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario en situaciones de emergencia. Límites y posibilidades.
 - ¿Cuál fue el impacto del aislamiento en la implementación de proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
 - ¿Cómo puede el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario ayudar a recibir a estudiantes cuya educación primaria o secundaria fue afectada por la crisis COVID?
-

SALUD MENTAL Y HABILIDADES SOCIOEMOCIONALES

Estos elementos se centran en el reconocimiento, evaluación y fortalecimiento de aspectos vinculados al bienestar psicológico, la empatía, la autorregulación emocional y las habilidades relacionales en experiencias de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario.

- ¿En qué medida el aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario ha contribuido a la salud mental de estudiantes y docentes durante la COVID?
- ¿El aprendizaje-servicio ha ayudado a superar las habilidades sociales que no se desarrollaron durante la COVID?
- ¿Puede el aprendizaje-servicio ayudar a estudiantes con problemas de salud mental derivados del COVID (o en la etapa post COVID)?
- ¿Qué función tiene la salud mental en el proceso de enseñanza-aprendizaje en materias de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?

V. EQUIDAD Y AVANCES SOCIALES

La investigación en esta área se centra en cuestiones que exploran el papel de la equidad en las prácticas del aprendizaje-servicio y del compromiso comunitario dentro y entre culturas, poblaciones y regiones. Estas cuestiones pueden incluir, entre otras, las implicaciones para la realización de investigaciones centradas en la equidad dentro y entre diferentes grupos, poblaciones, comunidades y/o culturas.

ESTADO DEL ARTE EN TORNO A LA EQUIDAD Y AVANCE SOCIAL

Esta categoría se centra en conocer el estado de arte en torno a avance o fortalecimiento de la equidad y avance social que el aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario permite en Latinoamérica y el caribe.

- ¿Se han desarrollado y abordado en LATAM temáticas de equidad y justicia en aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?

SENSIBILIDAD PARA LA EQUIDAD Y AVANCE SOCIAL

Esta categoría se centra en investigar y abordar temáticas de trabajo hacia el desarrollo de la sensibilidad de estudiantes, docencia y socios comunitarios en torno a la equidad y avance social.

- ¿Cuáles son los riesgos (estereotipos) de no incluir estos temas (equidad y avances sociales) en los proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
- ¿El aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario —fomenta la equidad e integración o genera prejuicios y/o rechazos?
- ¿Qué ayuda a los estudiantes a cultivar una mayor sensibilidad hacia las realidades sociales, económicas, culturales y religiosas?
- ¿Cómo perciben los estudiantes de grupos minoritarios y los de mayoría los proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio y y compromiso comunitario en los que participan, cuando estos proyectos involucran a miembros de su mismo grupo minoritario; hay diferencias?
- ¿Podemos incluir el análisis de estereotipos (en textos literarios y discursos sociales) en experiencias de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario, como una forma de reconocer cuestiones de equidad en una comunidad?
- ¿Cómo se puede realizar el aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario en comunidades de élite y adineradas?

CONSIDERACIONES METODOLÓGICAS PARA EL DESARROLLO DE LA EQUIDAD Y AVANCE SOCIAL EN APRENDIZAJE-SERVICIO Y COMPROMISO COMUNITARIO

Los elementos de esta categoría se centran en consideraciones relevantes para asegurar la equidad y apuntar al avance social al momento de desarrollar experiencias de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario.

- ¿Cómo el aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario tiene en cuenta las necesidades y las cualidades personales específicas de las minorías/poblaciones marginadas?
- ¿Cómo se incluye la equidad en los proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario en general para prevenir daños (no incluirlos puede ser peligroso)?
- ¿Qué se debe tener en cuenta en una experiencia con aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario para no continuar reproduciendo inequidades o una postura centrada en el poder?
- ¿Cuáles son los puntos a tener en cuenta para asegurar la equidad al involucrar a los estudiantes en el aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario global en un país diferente con una cultura y prácticas diferentes?
- ¿Cuál es la mejor manera de abordar las cuestiones de equidad y avance social en clase y en la reflexión?
- ¿Cómo la multidisciplina en los docentes y alumnos ayuda a un mejor resultado del aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?

SOCIO COMUNITARIO

Esta categoría se enfoca en poder conocer e investigar como se ha desarrollado y potenciado la equidad y avance social en los socios comunitarios de las diversas experiencias del aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario.

- ¿Cómo pueden los socios comunitarios desempeñar un papel más integral en la configuración del proyecto para que todas las partes tengan un papel equitativo?
 - ¿Cómo pueden los proyectos de participación comunitaria ayudar a empoderar a los miembros de la comunidad?
 - ¿Cuál es el proceso para asegurar la equidad en la selección de un socio comunitario?
 - ¿Cuál es el proceso para constituirse en socio comunitario? ¿Cómo se asegura la institución de acceder a la mayor cantidad de "elegibles"?
-

RESPONSABILIDADES INSTITUCIONALES EN LA EQUIDAD Y AVANCE SOCIAL

Enfocarse en las responsabilidades que tienen las instituciones educativas para asegurar, fortalecer y promover el desarrollo de la equidad y avance social en las experiencias aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario en América Latina (LATAM).

- ¿Cuál es el rol de las universidades en sus entornos en temas de equidad y desarrollo social y regional? ¿Cuál es la relevancia de la vinculación con el medio? ¿Es posible?
 - ¿Como construir experiencias interdisciplinarias de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario que sean útiles como instrumentos para abordar las diferencias entre estudiantes y otros actores?
-

BENEFICIOS DE FORTALECER LA EQUIDAD Y AVANCE SOCIAL

Enfocarse en los resultados, impactos y/o beneficios potenciales de abordar y desarrollar la equidad y avance social en las distintas experiencias de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario.

- ¿Cómo incide el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario en el rendimiento académico de los estudiantes vulnerables y en su integración social? ¿Favorece la equidad?
- ¿Los futuros trabajadores que ahora participan en el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario desarrollarán formas de relacionarse con sus compañeros y subordinados de una manera más igualitaria en cuanto a, entre otros aspectos, edad, género, nacionalidad y religión?
- ¿Cómo se percibe la justicia social en contextos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario y en diferentes religiones?
- ¿Cómo inciden las asimetrías sociales en los resultados?
- ¿Cuáles son los indicadores que expresan el abordaje del tema de la equidad en el proyecto?

VI. CULTURAL/REGIONAL/TRANSCULTURAL

Se deben abordar y debatir temas que exploren las prácticas del aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario y del compromiso comunitario dentro y entre culturas y regiones para identificar preguntas o acciones para la agenda de investigación.

Los temas de investigación incluyen, entre otros:

- realizar investigaciones dentro y entre diferentes entornos culturales o geográficos;
- examinar el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario en todo el espectro educativo;
- la voz de la comunidad;
- múltiples marcos para el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario.

DESCOLONIZACIÓN Y PODER EN EL APRENDIZAJE-SERVICIO Y COMPROMISO COMUNITARIO

Esta categoría aborda enfoques críticos sobre el aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario desde una perspectiva de descolonización, cuestionando las estructuras de poder y hegemonía, las desigualdades existentes y las epistemologías dominantes. Busca repensar los marcos teóricos y prácticos para promover un trabajo más justo, inclusivo y respetuoso con las comunidades, evitando replicar patrones coloniales.

- ¿Cómo dialogar con otros que hacen aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario sin imponerles nuestra visión o sin encasillarlos según nuestros propios marcos conceptuales?
- ¿Por qué deberíamos repensar los marcos hegemónicos del conocimiento si queremos trabajar en el sur? (De lo contrario domesticamos conciencias).
- ¿Puede el aprendizaje-servicio solidario y compromiso comunitario contribuir a la resistencia de modelos hegemónicos desde una perspectiva de descolonización? ¿De qué manera?
- ¿Cómo puede el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario garantizar una reciprocidad genuina entre los estudiantes y las comunidades a las que sirven y, al mismo tiempo, abordar los desequilibrios de poder?
- ¿Cómo se puede afrontar la diferente valoración de la acción universitaria en un contexto intercultural de amplia presencia del “extractivismo académico”?

INTERCULTURALIDAD Y DIVERSIDAD

Esta categoría reúne preguntas que exploran cómo entender, respetar y trabajar con la interculturalidad y la diversidad en proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario. Se enfoca en la importancia de reconocer las diferencias culturales, religiosas, étnicas, entre otras, promover el diálogo diverso e intercultural y desarrollar competencias para interactuar de manera horizontal y respetuosa con comunidades diversas.

- ¿Cómo relacionarse con comunidades con distintas culturas e idiomas para desarrollar proyectos en conjunto?
- Se toman en cuenta la cultura y sus limitaciones en diferentes ámbitos a la hora de llevar a cabo la implementación de los proyectos?
- ¿Qué tanto impactan las diferencias culturales en la implementación del servicio?
- ¿Cómo cambia el método de evaluación de necesidades en las diferentes culturas?
- ¿Cuáles son los elementos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario en las comunidades religiosas que ejecutan proyectos sociales?
- ¿Cuáles son los valores comunes (por ejemplo, católicos e islámicos) que pueden desarrollarse en las prácticas de participación comunitaria y aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
- ¿Existen rasgos que distinguen los fundamentos y prácticas del aprendizaje-servicio solidario y el compromiso comunitario de acuerdo a culturas, regiones y creencias diferentes? ¿cuales?

RELACIÓN Y PARTICIPACIÓN COMUNITARIA

Esta categoría reúne preguntas que se centran en la interacción activa y colaborativa con las comunidades involucradas en proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario. Explora cómo integrar a la comunidad de manera genuina dentro de los proyectos, asegurando que su voz y necesidades sean parte fundamental del proceso.

- ¿Qué aspectos se deben de preguntar a la comunidad en el aspecto cultural?
 - ¿Pueden los proyectos artísticos con un enfoque de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario ayudar a proporcionar un reflejo confiable de la voz de la comunidad, particularmente en una región multilingüe?
-

METODOLOGÍAS Y DIDÁCTICAS EN EL APRENDIZAJE-SERVICIO Y COMPROMISO COMUNITARIO

Identificar las herramientas y habilidades necesarias para que estudiantes y docentes realicen proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario en contextos interculturales.

- ¿Qué herramientas y habilidades son con los que debe contar un estudiante y docente para trabajar en comunidades con culturas diferentes?
 - ¿Qué elementos tienen los proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario interculturales?
 - ¿Cómo puede un enfoque interdisciplinario del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario enriquecer la comprensión cultural?
-

EVALUACIÓN, DIAGNÓSTICO Y SENSIBILIZACIÓN

Preguntas que buscan comprender la importancia de la dimensión cultural en los procesos de evaluación, diagnóstico y sensibilización de los proyectos.

- ¿Cómo agregar el "factor cultural" en el diagnóstico y en la evaluación?
 - ¿En qué medida la sensibilización es relevante para la contextualización del estudiante?
 - ¿Cómo cambia el método de evaluación de necesidades en las diferentes culturas?
 - ¿Cómo se puede utilizar una metodología de “No hacer daño” para abordar la intervención comunitaria en un contexto determinado?
-

IMPACTO Y RESULTADOS

Preguntas vinculadas a los impactos en proyectos interculturales.

- ¿Cuáles son los espacios de encuentro/diálogo intercultural y su impacto más allá de la comunidad/institución?
 - ¿Cómo generar un impacto en los participantes donde sean reconocidos por el enriquecimiento cultural y mutuo?
-

COMPETENCIAS

Preguntas que se orientan a identificar las competencias necesarias para la implementación de un proyecto en un ámbito intercultural.

- ¿Qué herramientas y habilidades son con los que debe contar un estudiante y docente para trabajar en comunidades con culturas diferentes?
- ¿Qué tiene que considerar el profesor para analizar el entorno cultural en el que va a trabajar?
- ¿Qué ventajas se desarrollan cuando los estudiantes tienen competencia intercultural antes de participar en el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario con una comunidad?

VII. ACUERDOS CONCEPTUALES Y TEORÍAS

El campo del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario ha sido criticado por su escasa teorización y la falta de marcos conceptuales bien desarrollados y probados.

La investigación en esta área de trabajo se centra en la comprobación teórica y la construcción de modelos y marcos conceptuales que expliquen diversos fenómenos en el estudio y la práctica del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario.

EPISTEMOLOGÍA, ENFOQUES CRÍTICOS Y ALTERNATIVOS DEL APRENDIZAJE-SERVICIO Y EL COMPROMISO COMUNITARIO

El conjunto de preguntas se centra en el ámbito de la Filosofía de la Educación y la Epistemología propia del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario. Se ve una perspectiva crítica que emerge desde el aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario que cuestiona al currículo y su diseño y, a la larga, al mismo sistema educativo.

- ¿Cuál es el posicionamiento epistemológico del aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
- ¿Cómo desanclar el aprendizaje-servicio de los paradigmas dominantes de la ciencia de la educación, para que deje de subordinarse a dichos cánones?
- ¿Qué lugar ocupan las teorías críticas en el aprendizaje-servicio solidario y compromiso comunitario?
- Paradigma sociocrítico (transformador, crítico, político).
- ¿Qué lugar tienen las epistemologías del sur, los saberes otros, lo indisciplinado en el aprendizaje-servicio solidario y compromiso comunitario?
- Considerar/crear desde el “sur” nuevos paradigmas Americanos y Caribe.
- ¿Existen teorías que vienen explicando los proceso de aprendizaje para otro lado en de vínculo e interacción con la comunidad?
- ¿Cómo desarrollar estudios teóricos que cuestionan y confirmen herramientas conceptuales?
- Estudios críticos.
- Teoría crítica.
- Historias críticas.

- ¿Cómo recoger las perspectivas críticas respecto del marco teórico predominantes?
 - Teorías pedagógicas (fundamento).
 - ¿Existen posturas de aprendizaje-servicio solidario o compromiso comunitario desde alternativos al desarrollo a los modelos desarrollistas?
-

ACLARACIÓN DE CONCEPTOS

Muy cercana a la categoría de Epistemología, representa un paso sustancial para definir un marco robusto que sustente la práctica.

- ¿Desde qué marcos / campos se ha abordado la VCM? ¿Cómo pueden dialogar / potenciar / colaborar?
 - ¿Desde qué marcos se fundamenta el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario y la VCM?
 - ¿Qué modelos de marco conceptual son adecuados para diferentes tipos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
 - A propósito de las diferentes construcciones conceptuales que están presentes en Chile y Latinoamérica ¿cuáles son las consideraciones epistemológicas que conlleva hablar de vinculación con el medio o de extensionismo en las Instituciones de Educación Superior chilenas?
 - ¿Qué conceptos evaluar la concepción en la aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
 - Desarrollar una instancia de diálogo y encuentro que permita elaborar un "marco conceptual". Esto posibilita cohesionar equipos y definir una postura para abordar, crear, desarrollar la vinculación.
 - Trabajar en el desarrollo de un marco conceptual que defina estrategias participativas y vinculantes para la VCM.
 - ¿Cómo aborda la institución el significado y uso flexible de los conceptos de la extensión? ¿O es un ámbito esencialmente de términos vaciados de significados?
-

INTEGRACIÓN TEORÍA-PRÁCTICA

Esta dinámica entre teoría y práctica hace más evidente la construcción del conocimiento.

- ¿Cómo se relacionan la teoría y la praxis en experiencias de aprendizaje y servicio? Debe haber un equilibrio, y alguna de las dos debe prevalecer?
- ¿Qué acciones realizar para promover la integración de los aprendizaje-servicio y los adquiridos en el aprendizaje-servicio?
- ¿Antes de desarrollar el servicio, cómo se si se requiere un al introducción teórica previa? ¿Cómo es mejor? Primero teoría y luego práctica, o llévalas a cabo a la pas, o primero práctica y luego el aprendizaje teórica?
- ¿Cómo establecer una metodología para asegurarnos que los conocimientos son adquiridos?
- ¿Cómo a través de nuestras aplicaciones se puede generar conocimiento para aportar a la teoría?
- ¿Cómo a través de nuestras aplicaciones se puede generar conocimiento para aportar a la teoría?

DIÁLOGO CON OTRAS TEORÍAS

Esta categoría representa explorar y ubicar el estatuto epistemológico del aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario con relación a otras teorías. Las preguntas y elementos de esta categoría enfatizan al ejercicio de distinción y construcción crítica y comparativa de la pedagogía que sustenta al aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario.

- ¿Cómo avanzar la fundamentación en las diversas teorías que vienen de otros campos?
- ¿Cómo integrar el aprendizaje-servicio a los paradigmas y teorías dominantes?
- ¿Qué referentes de la teoría motivación pueden contribuir a robustecer el enfoque?
- Teoría de la discapacidad.
- Teoría feminista.
- Desarrollo moral en aprendizaje-servicio.
- ¿Cómo se puede utilizar la teoría de Freud/Maclain sobre la autorrealización en el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario? El aprendizaje-servicio o el compromiso comunitario ayuda a identificar el propósito?

- Uso de diferentes modos de aprendizaje experiencial: ¿Cuál será más apropiado para el aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario y por qué?
 - Aprendizaje situado.
 - Aprendizaje experiencial/Modelos experienciales de aprendizaje.
 - ¿Un marco de derechos humanos mejora la ciudadanía global y la conciencia cívica en los estudiantes que participan en el aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
-

SOCIOLOGÍA DE LA EDUCACIÓN SUPERIOR

La sociología de la Educación representa todo un contexto de la incidencia de la institución en la sociedad y su diálogo con otras instituciones y contextos.

- ¿Qué rol o expectativas tienen las comunidades sobre las universidades de Chile post estallido?
 - ¿Qué explica el reflote de la vinculación con el medio y la extensión en Chile? (más allá de la CNA).
 - Identidades institucionales en vinculación con el medio. ¿Las definiciones dependen de trayectorias institucionales o normativa nacional?
-

EVALUACIÓN DEL APRENDIZAJE-SERVICIO Y EL COMPROMISO COMUNITARIO

La evaluación del aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario representa un esfuerzo sustancial que permite comprender mejor los términos de incidencia en los procesos de aprendizaje.

- Marcos conceptuales acerca de la evaluación, las tareas auténticas y las demandas cognitivas asociado con un tipo de proyecto de aprendizaje-servicio solidario y compromiso comunitario.
- ¿Cómo profundizar en aspectos éticos y políticos en aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
- ¿Qué consideraciones de calidad hay que considerar en aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?

- ¿Qué herramientas o qué variables se deben tomar en cuenta al valorar si el servicio comunitario está bien fundamentado?
- ¿En qué fases se puede dividir el proyecto de servicio social con el fin de encontrar los marcos teóricos más adecuados?
- ¿Cómo evaluar el aprendizaje teóricamente?
- ¿Qué estrategias podemos utilizar para sustentar un proyecto?
- ¿Cuáles son los marcos conceptuales para institucionalizar el aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario en contextos diversos?

RELACIÓN ENTRE LO INDIVIDUAL Y LO COLECTIVO - COMUNIDAD Y ACADEMIA

Esta categoría es importante puesto que revela la construcción del aprendizaje en contacto con la realidad. Realidad entendida como condición sustancial y cambiante -líquida- que muchas veces quiebra cualquier planificación, además de imponer su propio tiempo y dinámica a las iniciativas de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario.

- Relación entre lo "individual y lo colectivo" en los proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario.
- ¿Cómo se articula el conocimiento de la comunidad con la academia?
- ¿De qué manera debe ser el involucramiento del área de servicio social y la academia?

VIII. CONSIDERACIONES METODOLÓGICAS

A lo largo de los años, se ha debatido mucho sobre los métodos adecuados para el estudio del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario.

Se requiere una amplia gama de diseños, métodos y enfoques de investigación para comprender plenamente la naturaleza de este campo. Se requiere una amplia gama de epistemologías para diseñar y poner en práctica la investigación actual sobre el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario.

PUNTOS DE PARTIDA

Consideraciones epistemológicas, enfoque de investigación, perspectiva

- ¿Cómo superar la cercanía entre la propia experiencia y el estudio así como las asimetrías epistemológicas y metodológicas en la investigación para alcanzar mayor objetividad en las investigaciones y el proceso de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
- ¿Cómo dialoga el aprendizaje-servicio con diferentes propuestas metodológicas y epistémicas, qué métodos han sido eficaces? ¿Hay paradigmas metodológicos más alineados que otros con el aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
-

TIPOS

Ofrece una muestra de algunos tipos posibles de estudios a incluir en las investigaciones de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario.

- Estudios longitudinales.
 - Estudios de caso de "buenas prácticas".
 - Estudios comparativos.
 - Estudios etnográficos.
 - Enfoques mixtos.
 - Investigación cualitativa.
 - Casos testigos.
 - Otros temas sugeridos
-

PARTICIPACIÓN COMUNITARIA

Busca reflexionar sobre el rol de la comunidad en el marco de los proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario, así como sobre las maneras de tomar en cuenta la voz y la mirada de la comunidad en la investigación y por qué resulta clave dichas voces.

- Investigación-acción participativa basada en la comunidad.
 - ¿Cómo integrar la sistematización de una manera "amigable" (sencilla-eficaz) para quienes implementan aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario? |
 - ¿Qué dinámicas de poder podría esconder la elección de metodología a utilizar?
-

EVALUACIÓN E IMPACTO

Abarca la evaluación desde distintos focos que recorren la evaluación y el impacto: aspectos metodológicos, conceptuales, institucionales / sistémicos, de calidad.

- ¿Cómo validar los resultados y medir el éxito de un proyecto de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario, sin dejar de poner en cuestión el concepto de impacto?
- ¿A quién evaluamos? (Sujeto de evaluación)
- Adecuación – pertinencia
- Rigurosidad
- ¿Cómo se relaciona el sistema de recompensas para la investigación a corto plazo con la generación de impacto a largo plazo, y cómo podemos evaluar el compromiso sostenido del liderazgo en el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario frente a la provisión de recursos?

IX. INSTRUMENTOS Y MEDIDAS

Para garantizar una investigación de calidad se requieren instrumentos y medidas válidos y adecuados que permitan obtener los mejores datos y brindar oportunidades para análisis exhaustivos y sistemáticos. Muchos de los instrumentos desarrollados para el estudio del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario son instrumentos locales que suelen aplicarse a estudios individuales y no se perfeccionan para su posible uso en otros estudios. Además, existen numerosos instrumentos disponibles para estudios de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario, pero a veces no está claro si son adecuados para programas o poblaciones para las que no fueron diseñados inicialmente.

La agenda de investigación identifica cuestiones y problemas para mejorar la instrumentación y la medición del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario en los diversos contextos en los que se desarrolla el trabajo.

DISEÑO DE INSTRUMENTOS DE INVESTIGACIÓN EN APRENDIZAJE-SERVICIO Y EL COMPROMISO COMUNITARIO

Estos elementos se centran en cómo diseñar, seleccionar, adaptar y aplicar instrumentos que permitan recoger datos confiables y pertinentes para investigar el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario.

- ¿Cómo desarrollar instrumentos que incorporen elementos universales y, al mismo tiempo, se adapten de manera efectiva a contextos específicos del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario?
 - ¿Cómo diseñar instrumentos de medición que permitan un análisis a largo plazo del impacto de proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
 - ¿Qué instrumentos ya sistematizados pueden ser utilizados en el contexto de la investigación del aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
 - ¿Qué instrumentos de investigación ya validados pueden servir para medir el impacto y/o la institucionalización del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario?
 - ¿Qué instrumentos se utilizan ya para medir la utilidad del proyecto a largo plazo?
 - ¿Es posible crear una guía de instrumentos de investigación validados en América Latina?
 - Investigar las medidas utilizadas actualmente en diferentes países.
-

TIPOS DE INSTRUMENTOS

Estos elementos se centran en la consideración de distintos recursos metodológicos que permiten recolectar, registrar y sistematizar información relevante para responder preguntas de investigación.

- Encuestas: Medición de participación.
- Evaluación de todos los involucrados mediante encuestas con preguntas puntuales.
- Diseñar instrumentos que midan: cumplimiento de expectativas de alumnos; aplicación de la profesión en el aprendizaje-servicio; si satisficieron las necesidades de la comunidad; el impacto de la actividad de servicio en el aprendizaje en el alumno; y desarrollo de habilidades y actitudes en los estudiantes.
- Desarrollo de un instrumento sobre autoeficacia para los diferentes elementos de la metodología: autoeficacia para identificar necesidades; planificar un proyecto; reflexionar; interactuar con personas en situación de vulnerabilidad.

VARIABLES, INDICADORES, Y MEDIDAS

Estos elementos se centran en la identificación, definición y operacionalización de los aspectos que se quieren observar, analizar o evaluar en una investigación sobre aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario.

- ¿Qué categorías e indicadores sería fundamental considerar para la construcción de un instrumento de evaluación/investigación?
 - ¿Cómo definir mejores variables que permitan evaluar? ¿Son aplicables a diferentes realidades?
 - Identificar indicadores que puedan medir el aprendizaje-servicio en su totalidad en diferentes contextos.
 - Determinar las variables y en qué unidad se puede medir? (número de personas, duración de beneficiarios).
 - ¿Cómo determinar cuáles son las variables que serán medidas?
 - ¿Cómo desarrollar variables para permitir evaluar mejor? ¿Son todos aplicables a diferentes realidades?
-

ENFOQUES CUALI-CUANTI

Estos elementos se centran, no tanto en los instrumentos, sino en los enfoques de la investigación, ya sea desde la medición objetiva de variables (cuantitativo), la comprensión de significados y experiencias (cualitativo) o la combinación de ambos enfoques (mixto). Las preguntas están vinculadas con la utilidad, límites y complementariedad de los enfoques cualitativo y cuantitativo y en cómo superar dicotomías tradicionales entre ambos enfoques y avanzar hacia perspectivas integradoras.

- ¿Cómo superar la división cuantitativa-cualitativa en el diseño de instrumentos para investigar proyectos de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
- Necesidad de diseñar instrumentos (que responden a una lógica) cuantitativa y cualitativa, con diferentes enfoques según los diversos grupos, situaciones culturales y regiones para asegurar la validez y confiabilidad de los resultados.
- ¿Cómo superar la división entre lo cualitativo y lo cuantitativo, que ya ha sido cuestionada en la academia?
- Más allá de lo cualitativo, ¿qué instrumentos cuantitativos se han utilizado para investigar el aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario, o evaluar proyectos?
- ¿Es obligatorio elaborar un instrumento cualitativo y cuantitativo, o solo alguno es suficiente?
- Estructuración rigurosa de la investigación cualitativa para facilitar la transferibilidad.
- Problema de ubicar o cuestionar la metodología (cuantitativa o cualitativa).

REALIDADES ESPECÍFICAS

Estos elementos se centran en reconocer cómo las características sociales, culturales, geográficas o institucionales particulares de los contextos; y la focalización en algunos actores clave influyen en el diseño de los instrumentos de la investigación en aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario.

- ¿Qué instrumentos podemos utilizar para resolver problemas de inequidad en una experiencia de aprendizaje-servicio o compromiso comunitario con niños y niñas? (En particular, respecto a la diferencia entre niños/niñas y adultos).
- Desarrollar instrumentos y técnicas para evaluar el impacto social.
- Instrumentos para medir responsabilidad social en profesores.
- ¿Cómo medir el compromiso de los estudiantes? ¿Es necesario medirlos?

- La percepción de los actores se puede medir de manera cualitativa. ¿Existen instrumentos que pueden tomarse como base?
 - ¿Existen instrumentos que puedan dar cuenta de cómo la salud mental y la educación artística de la comunidad impactan en los resultados?
 - ¿Qué instrumentos o métodos son pertinentes para medir el impacto de la VcM-Extensión?
-

METODOLOGÍAS QUE ORIENTAN EL DISEÑO DE INSTRUMENTOS

Estos elementos se centran, no en los instrumentos, sino en los enfoques metodológicos que guían una investigación, atendiendo al tipo de conocimiento que se busca construir. Las preguntas se centran en las metodologías más adecuadas o coherentes con los principios del aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario.

- ¿Pueden las reflexiones valorativas funcionar como instrumentos idóneos en el aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
- ¿Puede el método de Filosofía para Niños ser un instrumento para la investigación en aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
- ¿El involucramiento de los beneficiarios de los proyectos como parte del proceso metodológico de recopilación de la información?
- ¿Puede el Método Socrático ser un instrumento para el aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?
- ¿Puede el Método de Aprendizaje en Acción ser un instrumento para el aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario?

X. REPLICACIÓN

Ningún estudio proporciona toda la evidencia, la comprensión ni el conocimiento necesarios para extraer conclusiones firmes sobre el aprendizaje-servicio o el compromiso comunitario. La replicación es un aspecto fundamental de la investigación científica.

Solo se han replicado unos pocos estudios sobre aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario. Replicar estudios de alta calidad permite fortalecer la evidencia y obtener hallazgos más concluyentes sobre las fortalezas y limitaciones de las prácticas, resultados y enfoques del aprendizaje-servicio y el compromiso comunitario.

EL PROCESO DE REPLICACIÓN

Estos artículos se centran en cómo replicar investigaciones de aprendizaje-servicio y compromiso comunitario.

- ¿Podemos replicar un estudio de investigación que ha sido validado en un determinado contexto cultural en otros contextos?
- Contexto: Replicar estudios de alta calidad en diferentes contextos para evaluar cómo el aprendizaje-servicio funciona de forma diferente o similar en diferentes entornos culturales.
- ¿Se puede replicar metodologías e instrumentos o herramientas pero se debe desarrollar la capacitación para diagnosticar la situación de cada institución?
- ¿Qué condiciones se requieren para fomentar/facilitar los estudios comparados? ¿Qué función cumplen estos estudios?

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Buenos Aires, Argentina

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**GLOBAL RESEARCH AGENDA FOR
SERVICE-LEARNING AND
COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT**

**SOUTH AMERICA/LATIN
AMERICA REGION
(*ENGLISH VERSION*)**

Global Research Agenda for Service-Learning and Community Engagement

SOUTH AMERICA/LATIN AMERICA REGION

The content contained in this part of the global research agenda is based on an analysis of 924 research questions and items submitted by 111 individuals from various countries in Latin American and beyond who participated in 4 Spanish-language forums held in Argentina, Chile y México between August 2019 and August 2023. The questions and items submitted during these forums were categorized and prioritized in June 2025 by 43 individuals from Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Ecuador y México.

I. IMPACT

Impact research focuses on assessing the impacts of service-learning and community engagement on participants, including students, faculty, staff, institutions and the community. They cross a broad range of short-term and long-term outcomes. This section of the agenda presents broad areas of impact to be investigated along with a particular set of themes within each impact area.

STUDENTS

The student category addresses the impact of service-learning and community engagement on students' comprehensive development. It explores the acquired competencies—both generic and professional, ethical, and civic—and their relationship to academic performance, the acquisition of theoretical knowledge, and the sense of institutional belonging, both short and long term. Additionally, dimensions such as self-efficacy, values, and life plans are considered, particularly among first-generation and Generation Z students.

- What competencies do students acquire who participate in service-learning and community engagement practices?

- What is the relationship between participation in service-learning and community engagement activities and the development of learning skills, the appropriation of theoretical content, and students' academic performance?
 - How do students perceive the impact of service-learning and community engagement on their overall development, considering competencies, emotions, values, self-efficacy, and life plans?
 - What effects do service-learning and community engagement have on students' competencies, including their ethical, civic, and professional development?
 - How do service-learning experiences and other forms of student service compare in their impact on the values, sense of belonging, and college careers of first-generation and Generation Z students?
 - How does participation in service-learning and community engagement experiences impact the development and transfer of generic competencies to new professional contexts, and what impact does it have on university students' ethical and civic development and life plans over time?
 - How do students perceive the social impact they have on the community through the service-learning projects in which they participate?
-

TEACHERS

The Teachers category analyzes the impact of service-learning and community engagement on the practices, trajectories, and conditions of their work. It considers the institutional and pedagogical barriers they face, as well as the transformations in their role, professional competencies, teacher identity, and sense of belonging. It also explores forms of collaboration and critical reflection that strengthen their professional development and commitment to the educational community.

- What are the main institutional, pedagogical, and contextual challenges that faculty face when integrating service-learning or community engagement into their teaching practices?
 - How does service-learning transform the teaching role and promote new forms of pedagogical and institutional collaboration in the university setting?
 - How does participation in service-learning projects impact the professional development of university faculty, considering the collaborative construction of knowledge, reflective practice, the acquisition of competencies, and the strengthening of their identity, sense of institutional belonging, and educational commitment?
 - How does service-learning or community engagement contribute to the development of faculty awareness and social responsibility?
-

COMMUNITY

These items focus on issues related to the qualitative and quantitative analysis of community impacts, positive and negative changes, student and community partner engagement, and the sustainability of the actions.

- How can we promote the construction of socially relevant knowledge through community spaces, considering the specific changes brought about, the characteristics of community partners, and the long-term effects?
 - How do we quantitatively measure the impact of service-learning and community engagement in the community? Develop indicators that demonstrate the outcomes and social impact of service-learning and community engagement interventions in the community.
 - How is the community partner constructed as a co-educator of students, and what relationships are established after service-learning and community engagement experiences? How does this impact civic development?
 - How can the sustainability after project implementation be assessed, considering strategies for continuity, long-term processes, and the community's role in problem resolution?
 - What is the social impact on the community of cross-sector partnerships of service-learning and community engagement projects?
 - How can we identify the risks and harm that our community interventions can cause?
-

INSTITUTIONAL

These research questions address how the institutionalization of solidarity-based service-learning and community engagement transforms institutional management and culture. They explore changes in pedagogical approaches, networking, and internationalization processes to strengthen social engagement.

- How do service-learning and community engagement impact institutional management and culture, considering the different actors, the methodological approaches used, the regulatory frameworks, the epistemological perspectives on the social, and the challenges that influence their sustainability and expansion?
- How are transversal relationships built between curricular spaces that address or do not address community issues?
- How do service-learning and community engagement influence, through spaces for exchange and socialization between countries, the construction of professional identity

and the internationalization processes of educational institutions?

- How do service-learning and community engagement impact curricular modifications and pedagogical practices?
 - How do collaborative networks between universities and other entities contribute to the institutionalization of service-learning and community engagement?
 - How does service-learning and community engagement influence the positioning of the university as a relevant player in solving social problems in the territory where it operates?
-

INVESTIGATION

The proposed research questions integrate different levels of analysis of the impact of service-learning and community engagement, linking impact and educational quality assessment, methodological approaches, conceptual considerations, and ontological reflection.

- How can educational quality indicators and their long-term impact be considered in service-learning and community engagement experiences, taking into account collateral and unintended effects?
- How do methodological approaches impact the relationship between the researcher and the subjects of the research—with their reality and culture—and the validation of results over time?
- How do epistemological and methodological approaches influence the way different educational actors perceive, define, and differentiate impact and contribution in their community?
- What are the determining factors that influence the impact of service-learning and community engagement experiences on the different actors (students, teachers, and community), and how can interdisciplinary approaches and diverse methods enhance this impact?
- How do perspectives on “the other” and the “social” influence the construction of the impact and outcomes of service-learning and community engagement experiences, and what model of the world underlies these representations?

II. IMPLEMENTATION

Implementation research focuses on examining the practices of service-learning and community engagement and the ways in which these practices are effective in achieving particular goals. Implementation studies seek to improve practice and provide guidance on best practices across a broad range of service-learning and community engagement programmatic approaches.

The research agenda identifies questions that center on the process of delivering service-learning and community engagement across a broad range of community, cultural, geographic, disciplinary, and institutional contexts.

DIAGNOSIS

These questions focus on diagnoses.

- How do we ensure participatory diagnoses to generate meaningful projects?
 - How can we carry out an effective approach for detecting:
 - a) needs and capabilities of the environment;
 - b) capabilities and needs of the university;
 - c) the match between them?
 - How do I know if the service I'm providing is truly beneficial to a given community? What preliminary studies can I conduct?
 - What ethical and safety aspects should be considered and implemented? How are they considered in different contexts/countries?
 - What strategies and tools are useful for understanding the community's goals and needs?
 - What is the best model for working with the community partner (steps, objectives, milestones) to achieve better results?
-

COMMUNITY

These questions focus on the connection with the community.

- How do we involve the community in co-constructed processes?
- How do we systematically connect with the community?
- What is community or reality? Where is the boundary?

- How do we generate spaces for exchange that foster networking among community organizations?
- What are the best practices for the participation of end beneficiaries in service-learning and community engagement projects?

-- How can we avoid providing welfare?

MOTIVATION

These questions center on how to motivate students, professors, and the community.

- How can we motivate teachers to engage in service-learning and community engagement?
 - How can we get students engaged in the service project?
 - How can we motivate community members to share personal problems or other sensitive issues that may be helpful for project implementation, but that members are reluctant to discuss? How can we avoid hurting their feelings, invading their personal sphere, or intimidating them?
 - How can we engage community leaders to achieve the impact of service-learning and community engagement?
-

TEACHING ROLE

Questions aimed at identifying skills and tools necessary for the teacher.

- What teacher knowledge and skills need to be deepened/modified to support these experiences and advance collaboration between organizations?
 - What skills should teachers develop?
 - How are teachers trained to foster reflective practice?
 - How much does teacher training influence successful service-learning and community engagement experiences?
-

SOLIDARITY

Examine the role and importance of the concept of solidarity in service-learning.

- How do we best incorporate the dimension of solidarity (and its meaning depending on the context) into the design and execution of a project?
 - How is the concept of "solidarity" interpreted in each context?
-

MULTI/INTERDISCIPLINARY

Questions relating to the approach to be taken in interdisciplinary projects, and how to evaluate them.

- How can we find common ground between disciplines?
 - How can service be monitored if multiple disciplines are involved?
 - To what extent do students who participate in a service-learning or community engagement experience with an interdisciplinary approach have to learn content or methods from a program other than their own?
-

NEW TECHNOLOGIES

Examine the use of new technologies in the implementation of service-learning and community engagement.

- Does the incorporation of new technologies in the implementation of different stages of projects, for example the use of artificial intelligence (AI), improve their impact?
 - Does the use of new technological tools significantly improve all or some of the different stages of a service-learning and community engagement project? (Which tools?/Which stages? In all cases?)
-

TIME

Questions aimed at identifying the moments and duration necessary for implementation.

- When is the best time during the course to engage students in service-learning or community engagement? From the first year or later?

- What are the ideal times for diagnosing, developing, and concluding service-learning or community engagement projects?
 - How much time during the semester should be devoted to theoretical learning to prepare students to provide high-quality service?
-

REFLECTION

Examination of the development of reflection in projects.

- How to achieve deep and critical reflection in students?
-

COMMUNICATION

Questions related to communication within and outside the institution.

- Create direct links between educational authorities and schools and communities.
 - Listen carefully to students.
 - How to implement social, family, and cross-disciplinary connections?
-

LEARNING

Explore the importance of service-learning and community engagement in the curriculum.

- What is the best way to integrate service learning and community engagement into the school curriculum?
-

RESOURCES

Examine the importance of resources

- Where does funding come from to support service-learning and community engagement activities and development?

III. INSTITUTIONALIZATION

Institutionalization research focuses on examining the factors that promote the sustainability and institutionalization of service-learning and community engagement across institutional and community contexts.

Studies in this area seek to conceptualize the idea of institutionalization in light of the changing contexts of educational institutions and the varied approaches to service-learning and community engagement.

INSTITUTIONALIZATION AND ITS MODELS

This category explores models for institutionalizing service-learning and community engagement in institutions at different levels of the educational system. The research question, "How to institutionalize service-learning and community engagement in different contexts?" focuses on identifying methodologies, strategies, and processes for formally integrating it within diverse institutions and communities. The topic refers to understanding the factors that promote the long-term sustainability of this educational practice, adapting to the cultural and structural specificities of each location.

The aim is to explore the key elements that must be considered to achieve the institutionalization of service-learning and community engagement, such as the regulatory and legal framework, and how it can influence the process. It also addresses research on the quality of service-learning and community engagement plans, programs, and projects, as well as the challenges and difficulties that arise during institutionalization. The research also focuses on compiling institutionalization experiences in different countries (successful or unsuccessful), recognizing that each context presents its own unique characteristics. In summary, this topic seeks to provide practical and conceptual guidance on how to consolidate service-learning and community engagement so that it does not depend on individual initiatives, but rather becomes an integral part of the culture and structure of educational institutions and communities.

- How do we institutionalize solidarity-based service-learning and community engagement in different contexts?
- What strategies should be implemented to achieve institutionalization?
- What strategies increase faculty participation?
- What organizational structure is ideal for coordinating the strategy at the university level?
- What is the relationship between institutionalization and the regulatory/legal framework that promotes that institutionalization?
- How can we avoid the commodification of "solidarity" from an institutional perspective?

- What elements or aspects should we consider to say that the proposal for solidarity-based service-learning and community engagement has been institutionalized?
- What elements should be analyzed to establish institutionalization? How is it tracked?
- Do regulations or legal aspects improve the institutionalization of the proposal for solidarity-based service-learning and community engagement?
- Gather institutionalization experiences in each country (delving into the culture of each place has its own challenges). I believe that institutionalization has its details in the cultural context of each place. I believe it warrants further research on institutionalization processes.
- What processes (what steps) are effective in institutionalization in each region?
- How can we problematize the concept of institutionalization to find its most appropriate elements?

SUSTAINABILITY AND BARRIERS

This category explores how to sustain the institutionalization processes of service-learning and community engagement over time, analyzing, for example, resources and decisions. This research topic explores the capacity of educational institutions to maintain and consolidate the changes and reforms they implement over time. It is not just about introducing new policies or programs, but rather ensuring that these innovations are permanently integrated into the structure, culture, and daily operations of the institution. The focus is on how institutions ensure that these processes are not isolated or temporary initiatives, but rather become entrenched and sustainable practices.

This involves analyzing various factors, such as:

- ⇒ *Leadership and governance*: How institutional leadership facilitates or hinders the continuity of changes.
- ⇒ *Organizational culture*: The role of shared values, beliefs, and norms in the acceptance and permanence of new practices.
- ⇒ *Resources and capabilities*: The availability and management of human, financial, and technological resources to sustain institutionalized processes.
- ⇒ *Participation and engagement*: The involvement of the educational community (teachers, students, administrative staff, families) in the appropriation and maintenance of reforms.
- ⇒ *Regulatory frameworks and policies*: The influence of internal and external regulations on the stability of processes.
- ⇒ *Evaluation and adaptation*: The institution's ability to monitor progress, identify challenges, and adjust strategies to ensure sustainability.

In short, the research seeks to understand what enables an educational institution to capitalize on its change efforts and prevent innovations from being diluted or disappeared over time, thus ensuring a lasting impact on the quality and relevance of the education it offers.

- How does one build the engagement of faculty to generate sustainability?
- What is the role of faculty, students, administrators, deans, coordinators, and the rector at the institution in advancing the institutionalization of service-learning and community engagement?
- Who should lead the strategies?
- What incentives or promotion mechanisms exist for faculty to promote the strategies?
- Are there financial incentives or other recognition for faculty leaders in service-learning and community engagement? How are they selected and how do they connect with community partners?
- What support is provided to faculty in implementing service-learning and community engagement?
- How does one implement a program especially dedicated to help faculty and professors increase their interest in service-learning and community engagement?
- What support for faculty fosters good institutional practices?
- How can university administrations enhance service-learning and community engagement projects in a context of economic constraints?
- What strategies increase faculty participation?
- How do we understand and honor (compensate) the invisible work of service-learning and community engagement (faculty, community partners, students)?
- What are the difficulties and challenges to institutionalization?
- What are the challenges and dangers to institutionalization?
- How do we best define the challenges to institutionalization within organizations.
- Is the existence of different faculties with different subcultures an obstacle to institutionalizing service-learning and community engagement? What about a university that is spread across the country?
- How can institutional barriers to faculty rewards be reduced to encourage greater use of service-learning and community engagement?
- What are the risks of institutionalizing service-learning and community engagement in the university?

- What limitations does the institutionalization of service-learning and community engagement entail for students, faculty, and the community?
 - How can the institution provide financial resources for service-learning and community engagement and allocate them equitably?
 - What incentives should be institutionalized to ensure their intermittent implementation?
 - Do funding mechanisms consider community participation, service-learning, and long-term community engagement?
 - How do we change the long-term reward system and the recognition of partners and academic (professional) staff with busy schedules?
 - How are intra-institutional demands built to make service-learning and community engagement sustainable?
 - What elements should be considered to maintain the sustainability of service-learning and community engagement?
 - How should faculty be prepared and trained for proper, sustainable implementation?
 - What teaching practices enable the long-term maintenance of service-learning projects and community engagement?
 - What are the critical dimensions for the sustainability of service-learning and community engagement in a department or program? In different areas?
 - How have educational institutions managed to keep service-learning and community engagement alive?
 - What are the elements that define whether service-learning or community engagement has been institutionalized?
 - What studies can be conducted to determine whether the impact on service-learning will be sustained over the long term?
 - How can we cut through so much red tape to secure financial support from the institution?
 - How can we identify feasible courses?
-

INSTITUTIONALIZATION AND COMMUNITY PARTNERS, AND STUDENTS' AGENCY IN INSTITUTIONALIZATION

The category refers to aspects that, although not always the main focus of the questions analyzed, are fundamental to the full and sustainable development of the institutionalization processes of service-learning and community engagement in educational institutions and their community partners.

Community Partnerships: Analyzes the nature and impact of collaborative and reciprocal relationships between educational institutions and external organizations or communities. Research in this area explores how these partnerships are established, maintained, and evaluated to ensure they are equitable, mutually beneficial, and contribute to the quality of learning and service delivery. The goal is to understand how community voices and needs are genuinely integrated into the design and development of community engagement and service-learning projects.

Student Agency: Examines the active and meaningful role of students in all phases of service-learning and community engagement projects. This involves investigating how their agency, leadership, and responsibility are fostered in identifying community needs, designing solutions, implementing actions, and reflecting on their learning and social impact. The focus is on how students become agents of change and how the service-learning and community engagement experience enhances their personal, academic, and civic development.

In short, this category of research seeks to understand how educational institutions can sustain and scale service-learning and community engagement in ways that promote authentic collaboration with the community and real student empowerment, thereby transforming the educational practice and social commitment of the institution.

- Is service-learning or community engagement institutionalized among community partners (CSOs)?
- What community partnership models promote institutionalization?
- What are the best ways to facilitate student participation in service-learning and community engagement?
- What characteristics are present in universities that require all students to participate in service-learning and community engagement?
- How long should community training be conducted so that students can take ownership of the project?
- How can service-learning and community engagement be institutionalized across different schools?

- How can evidence of service-learning and community engagement developed in the community be documented at the institutional level?
- Is it possible to articulate the development of service-learning and community engagement in universities with its development at lower educational levels?
- Can there be institutionalization at the community level? Can we institutionalize among community partners, or can community partners institutionalize after several service-learning and community engagement commitments?
- How can we institutionalize within the community?
- How is the institutionalization of service-learning and community engagement in our universities reflected in the way professors evaluate the learning process?
- Community outreach and democratic participation.

IV. COVID/POST-COVID

Questions and issues that explore service-learning and community engagement practices during and beyond COVID.

The issues include, but are not limited to:

- new emerging practices for service-learning and community engagement results from the pandemic.
- changes regarding the conduct of service-learning and community engagement research due to COVID.
- impact of COVID on the quality of service-learning and community engagement; and
- advantages and disadvantages of conducting service-learning and community engagement during or after COVID.

TECHNOLOGIES IN SOLIDARITY SERVICE-LEARNING PROJECTS

The prioritized items focus on the use of technologies and the role of virtuality in the development of service-learning and community engagement projects, based on the scenario caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. The questions in this category address how to leverage digital tools to implement or evaluate service-learning and community engagement, and the benefits and limitations of virtuality in service-learning experiences.

- Which populations benefit most from online service? Are there populations that can only benefit from online service-learning or community engagement?
 - Do virtual activities provide a greater number of community partners?
 - How can we leverage the opportunities that technology offers to enhance learning and service experiences?
 - What is the contribution of virtual work to students' service-learning and community engagement projects/activities?
 - What is the effectiveness of online service-learning and community engagement in sustaining their continuity in relation to expected institutional learning outcomes and graduate attributes.
 - How can we connect with the environment in a "virtual" environment?
 - What have we learned from the remote modality (COVID) for service-learning and community engagement projects?
-

IN-PERSON/VIRTUAL

These items focus on the comparison and coordination between in-person and virtual modalities in service-learning and community engagement projects, and on how the methodological design varies depending on the modality (in-person, virtual, or hybrid).

- How can we decide which practices are most appropriate (in-person/online) to achieve the best learning experience?
- What are the potential student learning outcomes in relation to in-person versus virtual service delivery?
- Does face-to-face contact have differential effects on student and community learning outcomes?

IMPACT OF COVID ON LEARNING AND SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT PRACTICES

These items focus on understanding how the COVID-19 pandemic affected the ways we teach, learn, and engage in community service-learning and community engagement projects.

- What supportive service-learning and community engagement practices that emerged during COVID persist and benefit current practices?
- What practices emerged during COVID that expanded institutional and student capacity to engage in service-learning and community engagement?
- What are the new community intervention processes following COVID?
- How did the COVID experience help make changes to the institution's service-learning and community engagement policy?
- How have community needs deepened through the impact of COVID (education, social interaction, economy, health)?
- What were the unexpected outcomes of service-learning during COVID? Were they positive? Was there more self-reflection?
- What are the advantages and disadvantages of service-learning and community engagement in emergency situations. Limits and possibilities.
- What impact did isolation have on the implementation of service-learning and community engagement projects?
- How can service-learning and community engagement help accommodate students whose primary or secondary education was affected by the COVID crisis?

MENTAL HEALTH AND SOCIO-EMOTIONAL SKILLS

These items focus on recognizing, assessing, and strengthening aspects related to psychological well-being, empathy, emotional self-regulation, and relational skills in service-learning and community engagement experiences.

- To what extent have service-learning and community engagement contributed to the mental health of students and teachers during COVID?
- Has service-learning helped overcome social skills that were not developed during COVID?
- Can service-learning help students with mental health issues related to COVID (or in the post-COVID era)?
- What role does mental health play in the teaching-learning process in service-learning and community engagement courses?

V. EQUITY AND SOCIAL ADVANCEMENT

Research in this area focuses on issues that explore the role of equity in service-learning and community engagement practices within and across cultures, populations, and regions. The issues include, but are not limited to, implications for conducting equity-focused research within and across different groups, populations, communities, and/or cultures.

THE STATE OF THE ART ON EQUITY AND SOCIAL ADVANCEMENT

This category focuses on understanding the state of the art regarding the advancement or strengthening of equity and social progress that service-learning and community engagement enable in Latin America and the Caribbean.

- Have equity and justice issues been developed and addressed in Latin America (LATAM) regarding service-learning and community engagement?
-

SENSITIVITY FOR EQUITY AND SOCIAL ADVANCEMENT

This category focuses on research and addressing work topics aimed at developing the sensitivity of students, faculty, and community partners regarding equity and social advancement.

- What are the risks (stereotypes) of not including these themes (equity and social advancement) in service-learning and community engagement projects?
 - Do service-learning and community engagement foster equity and inclusion or generate prejudice and/or rejection?
 - What helps students cultivate greater sensitivity to social, economic, cultural, and religious realities?
 - How do students from minority and majority groups perceive the service-learning and community engagement projects in which they participate when these projects involve members of their own minority group? Are there differences?
 - Can we include the analysis of stereotypes (in literary texts and social discourses) in service-learning and community engagement experiences as a way to recognize equity issues in a community?
 - How can service-learning and community engagement be carried out in elite and wealthy communities?
-

METHODOLOGICAL CONSIDERATIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF EQUITY AND SOCIAL ADVANCEMENT IN SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

The items in this category focus on relevant considerations for ensuring equity and aiming for social advancement when developing service-learning and community engagement experiences.

- How are the specific needs and personal qualities of minorities/marginalized populations considered in service-learning and community engagement?
 - How is equity included in service-learning and community engagement projects in general to prevent harm (failing to include it can be dangerous)?
 - What should be considered in a service-learning and community engagement experience to avoid reproducing inequities or a power-centered stance?
 - What points should be kept in mind to ensure equity when engaging students in service-learning and global community engagement in a different country with a different culture and practices?
 - What is the best way to address issues of equity and social advancement in class and in reflection?
 - How does multidisciplinary faculty and students contribute to a better outcome of service-learning and community engagement?
-

COMMUNITY PARTNER

This category focuses on understanding and exploring how equity and social progress have been developed and enhanced among community partners through various service-learning and community engagement experiences.

- How can community partners play a more integral role in shaping the project so that all parties have an equitable role?
 - How can community engagement projects help empower community members?
 - What is the process for ensuring equity in selecting a community partner?
 - What is the process for becoming a community partner? How does the institution ensure it reaches the largest possible pool of eligible participants?
-

INSTITUTIONAL RESPONSIBILITIES IN EQUITY AND SOCIAL ADVANCEMENT

Focus on the responsibilities of educational institutions to ensure, strengthen, and promote the development of equity and social advancement in service-learning and community engagement experiences in Latin America (LATAM).

- What is the role of universities in their respective contexts regarding equity and social and regional development? What is the relevance of community engagement? Is it possible?
 - How can we build interdisciplinary service-learning and community engagement experiences that are useful as tools for addressing differences between students and other stakeholders?
-

BENEFITS OF STRENGTHENING EQUITY AND SOCIAL ADVANCEMENT

Focus on the potential outcomes, impacts, and/or benefits of addressing and developing equity and social advancement in the various service-learning and community engagement experiences.

- How does service-learning and community engagement impact the academic performance of vulnerable students and their social integration? Does it promote equity?
- Will future workers currently participating in service-learning and community engagement develop more equal ways of relating to their peers and subordinates in terms of, among other aspects, age, gender, nationality, and religion?
- How is social justice perceived in service-learning and community engagement contexts and across different religions?
- How do social asymmetries impact outcomes?
- What are the indicators that reflect the project's approach to equity?

VI. CULTURAL/REGIONAL/TRANS-CULTURAL

Issues that explore service-learning and community engagement practices within and across cultures and regions are to be embraced and discussed, with an eye toward identifying questions or action steps for the research agenda.

The research issues include, but is not limited to:

- conducting research within and across different cultural or geographic settings;
- examining service-learning and community engagement across the educational spectrum;
- community voice;
- multiple frames of service-learning and community engagement.

DECOLONIZATION AND POWER IN SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

This category addresses critical approaches to service-learning and community engagement from a decolonial perspective, questioning power and hegemonic structures, existing inequalities, and dominant epistemologies. It seeks to rethink theoretical and practical frameworks to promote more just, inclusive, and respectful work with communities, avoiding replicating colonial patterns.

- How can we engage in dialogue with others engaged in service-learning and community engagement without imposing our vision or pigeonholing them according to our own conceptual frameworks?
- Why should we rethink hegemonic frameworks of knowledge if we want to work in the South? (Otherwise, we domesticate consciences.)
- Can solidarity-based service-learning and community engagement contribute to resisting hegemonic models from a decolonization perspective? How?
- How can service-learning and community engagement ensure genuine reciprocity between students and the communities they serve while addressing power imbalances?
- How can the different valuation of university action be addressed in an intercultural context where "academic extractivism" is widely prevalent?

INTERCULTURALITY AND DIVERSITY

This category brings together questions that explore how to understand, respect, and work with interculturality and diversity in service-learning and community engagement projects. It focuses on the importance of recognizing cultural, religious, ethnic, and other differences, promoting diverse and intercultural dialogue, and developing skills to interact horizontally and respectfully with diverse communities.

- How can we engage with communities with different cultures and languages to develop joint projects?
 - Are culture and its limitations taken into account in different settings when implementing projects?
 - How much do cultural differences impact service implementation?
 - How does the needs assessment method vary across cultures?
 - What are the elements of service-learning and community engagement in religious communities that implement social projects?
 - What are the common values (e.g., Catholic and Islamic) that can be developed in community participation, service-learning, and community engagement practices?
 - Are there any distinguishing features of the foundations and practices of solidarity-based service-learning and community engagement across cultures, regions, and beliefs? Which ones?
-

COMMUNITY RELATIONSHIP AND PARTICIPATION

This category brings together questions that focus on active and collaborative interaction with communities involved in service-learning and community engagement projects. It explores how to genuinely integrate the community into projects, ensuring that their voice and needs are a fundamental part of the process.

- What cultural aspects should be addressed with the community?
 - Can artistic projects with a service-learning and community engagement approach help provide a reliable reflection of the community's voice, particularly in a multilingual region?
-

METHODOLOGIES AND DIDACTICS IN SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

Identify the tools and skills necessary for students and teachers to carry out service-learning and community engagement projects in intercultural contexts.

- What tools and skills should students and teachers possess to work in communities with different cultures?

- What elements are present in intercultural service-learning and community engagement projects?
 - How can an interdisciplinary approach to service-learning and community engagement enrich cultural understanding?
-

EVALUATION, DIAGNOSIS AND AWARENESS

Questions that seek to understand the importance of the cultural dimension in the evaluation, diagnosis, and awareness-raising processes of projects.

- How can we incorporate the "cultural factor" into diagnosis and assessment?
 - To what extent is awareness-raising relevant to student contextualization?
 - How does the needs assessment method vary across cultures?
 - How can a "Do No Harm" methodology be used to address community intervention in a given context?
-

IMPACT AND RESULTS

Questions related to the impacts of intercultural projects.

- What are the spaces for intercultural encounter/dialogue and their impact beyond the community/institution?
 - How can we generate an impact on participants where they are recognized for the cultural and mutual enrichment?
-

COMPETENCIES

Questions aimed at identifying the skills needed to implement a project in an intercultural setting.

- What tools and skills should students and teachers possess to work in communities with different cultures?
- What should teachers consider when analyzing the cultural environment in which they will be working?
- What advantages are developed when students have intercultural competence before participating in service-learning and community engagement with a community?

VII. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORKS AND THEORIES

The field of service-learning and community engagement has been criticized for being under-theorized and for lacking well-developed and well-tested conceptual frameworks.

Research in this area of work focuses on theory testing and building conceptual models and frameworks that explain various phenomena in the study and practice of service-learning and community engagement.

EPISTEMOLOGY: CRITICAL AND ALTERNATIVE APPROACHES TO SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

This set of questions focuses on the philosophy of education and the epistemology of service-learning and community engagement. A critical perspective emerges from service-learning and community engagement that questions the curriculum and its design, and ultimately, the education system itself.

- What is the epistemological positioning of service-learning and community engagement?
- How can service-learning be unmoored from the dominant paradigms of educational science, so that it is no longer subordinated to these canons?
- What place do critical theories occupy in solidarity-based service-learning and community engagement?
- Explore a socio-critical paradigm (transformative, critical, political).
- What place do the epistemologies of the South, other knowledge systems, and the “undisciplined” have in solidarity-based service-learning and community engagement?
- Consider/create new American and Caribbean paradigms from the “South”.
- Are there theories that explain the learning processes of connecting and interacting with the community?
- How can we develop theoretical studies that question and confirm conceptual tools?
- Critical studies.
- Critical theory.
- Critical histories.
- How can critical perspectives be captured regarding the predominant theoretical framework?

- Pedagogical theories (foundation).
 - Are there positions of solidarity-based service-learning or community engagement that are alternatives to developmentalist models?
-

CLARIFICATION OF CONCEPTS

Very similar to the category of Epistemology, this set of questions represents a substantial step toward defining a robust framework to support the practice.

- From what frameworks/fields has VAW been addressed? How can they dialogue/strengthen/collaborate?
 - From what frameworks are service-learning, community engagement, and VAW based?
 - What conceptual framework models are appropriate for different types of service-learning and community engagement?
 - Regarding the different conceptual constructs present in Chile and Latin America, what are the epistemological considerations involved in speaking of community engagement or outreach in Chilean Higher Education Institutions?
 - What concepts should be evaluated in the conception of service-learning and community engagement?
 - Develop a forum for dialogue and encounter that allows for the development of a "conceptual framework." This makes it possible to unite teams and define a position to address, create, and develop engagement.
 - Work on the development of a conceptual framework that defines participatory and binding strategies for VAW.
 - How does the institution address the meaning and flexible use of extension concepts? Or is it essentially a field of meaningless terms?
-

THEORY/PRACTICE INTEGRATION

This dynamic between theory and practice makes the construction of knowledge more evident.

- How do theory and praxis relate in service-learning experiences? Should there be a balance, and should one of the two prevail?
- What actions should be taken to promote the integration of service-learning and those acquired in service-learning?

- Before developing the service, how do I know if a prior theoretical introduction is required? What is the best way? First theory and then practice, or do they be carried out in a step-by-step manner? Or first practice and then theoretical learning?
- How can we establish a methodology to ensure that knowledge is acquired?
- How can we generate knowledge to contribute to theory through our applications?
- How can we generate knowledge to contribute to theory through our applications?

DIALOGUE WITH OTHER THEORIES

This category explores and situates the epistemological status of service-learning and community engagement in relation to other theories. The questions and elements in this category emphasize the exercise of distinction and critical and comparative construction of the pedagogy that underpins service-learning and community engagement.

- How can we advance the foundation in the diverse theories from other fields?
 - How can we integrate service-learning into dominant paradigms and theories?
 - What references to motivational theory can contribute to strengthening the approach?
 - Disability theory.
 - Feminist theory.
 - Moral development in service-learning.
 - How can Freud's/Maclain's theory of self-actualization be used in service-learning and community engagement? Does service-learning or community engagement help identify purpose?
 - Use of different modes of experiential learning: Which will be most appropriate for service-learning and community engagement, and why?
 - Situated learning.
 - Experiential learning/ Experiential learning models.
 - Does a human rights framework enhance global citizenship and civic awareness in students participating in service learning and community engagement?
-

SOCIOLOGY OF HIGHER EDUCATION

The sociology of education represents a whole context of the institution's impact on society and its dialogue with other institutions and contexts.

- What role or expectations do communities have regarding Chilean universities after the outbreak?
 - What explains the revival of community engagement and outreach in Chile (beyond the CNA).
 - Institutional identities in community engagement. Do definitions depend on institutional trajectories or national regulations?
-

EVALUATION OF SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

The evaluation of service-learning and community engagement is a substantial effort, yet it allows for a better understanding of the terms of impact on learning processes.

- Conceptual frameworks regarding assessment, authentic tasks, and cognitive demands associated with a type of solidarity service-learning and community engagement project.
 - How can we delve deeper into ethical and political aspects of service-learning and community engagement?
 - What quality considerations should be considered in service-learning and community engagement?
 - What tools or variables should be taken into account when assessing whether community service is well-founded?
 - What phases can a social service project be divided into in order to find the most appropriate theoretical frameworks?
 - How can learning be assessed theoretically?
 - What strategies can we use to support a project?
 - What are the conceptual frameworks for institutionalizing service-learning and community engagement in diverse contexts?
-

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE INDIVIDUAL AND THE COLLECTIVE – COMMUNITY AND ACADEMY

This theme is important because it reveals the construction of learning in contact with reality. Reality is understood as a substantial and changing—liquid—condition that often disrupts any planning, in addition to imposing its own time and dynamics on service-learning and community engagement initiatives.

- Relationship between the "individual and the collective" in service-learning and community engagement projects.
- How is community knowledge articulated with academia?
- How should the involvement of social service and academia be?

VIII. METHODOLOGICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Over the years, there has been much debate about appropriate methods for studying service-learning and community engagement.

A broad range of research designs, methods, and approaches is required to fully understand the nature of this field. A broad range of epistemologies is required to design and implement current research on service-learning and community engagement.

STARTING POINTS

Epistemological considerations, research approach, and perspective.

- How can we overcome the closeness between one's own experience and the study, as well as the epistemological and methodological asymmetries in research, to achieve greater objectivity in research and the process of service-learning and community engagement?
- How does service-learning interact with different methodological and epistemic proposals? Which methods have been effective? Are there methodological paradigms more aligned than others with service-learning and community engagement?

TYPES

Provides a sample of some possible types of studies to include in service-learning and community engagement research.

- Longitudinal studies.
 - Case studies of "best practices."
 - Comparative studies.
 - Ethnographic studies.
 - Mixed approaches.
 - Qualitative research.
 - Case studies.
 - Other suggested topics
-

COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION

The questions in this theme reflect on the role of the community within the framework of service-learning and community engagement projects, as well as on ways to consider the community's voice and perspective in research and why these voices are key.

- Community-based participatory action research.
 - How can systematization be integrated in a user-friendly (simple and effective) way for those implementing service-learning and community engagement?
 - What power dynamics might be hidden in the choice of methodology?
-

EVALUATION AND IMPACT

The questions in this theme cover evaluation from different perspectives that encompass evaluation and impact (e.g., methodological conceptual, institutional/systemic, and quality aspects.)

- How can we validate the results and measure the success of a service-learning and community engagement project, while still questioning the concept of impact?
- Who do we evaluate? (Subject of evaluation).
- Appropriateness – relevance.
- Rigor.
- How does the short-term research reward system relate to generating long-term impact, and how can we assess the sustained commitment of leadership to service-learning and community engagement versus the provision of resources?

IX. INSTRUMENTS AND MEASURES

Securing quality research requires valid and appropriate instruments and measures that can secure the best data and provide opportunities for thorough, systematic analyses. Many of the instruments that have been developed for the study of service-learning and community engagement are home grown instruments that are often applied to single studies and are not cultivated further for potential use in other studies. In addition, there are many instruments that are available for studies of service-learning and community engagement, but it is sometimes unclear regarding the suitability of such instruments for programs or populations for which they were not initially designed.

The research agenda identifies issues for improving the instrumentation and measurement of service-learning and community engagement across the many contexts in which the work takes place.

DESIGNING RESEARCH INSTRUMENTS FOR SERVICE-LEARNING AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

These items focus on how to design, select, adapt, and apply instruments that allow for the collection of reliable and relevant data for research into service-learning and community engagement.

- How can instruments be developed that incorporate universal elements while effectively adapting to specific contexts of service-learning and community engagement?
 - How can measurement instruments be designed that allow for long-term analysis of the impact of service-learning and community engagement projects?
 - What standardized instruments can be used in the context of service-learning and community engagement research?
 - What validated research instruments can be used to measure the impact and/or institutionalization of service-learning and community engagement?
 - What instruments are already used to measure the long-term usefulness of the project?
 - Is it possible to create a guide to validated research instruments in Latin America?
 - Investigate the measures currently used in different countries.
-

TYPES OF INSTRUMENTS

These items focus on the consideration of different methodological resources that allow for the collection, recording, and systematization of relevant information to answer research questions.

- Surveys: Measuring participation.
 - Evaluation of all stakeholders through surveys with specific questions.
 - Design instruments that measure: the fulfillment of student expectations; the application of the profession in service-learning; whether the community's needs were met; the impact of the service activity on student learning; and the development of skills and attitudes in students.
 - Development of a self-efficacy instrument for the different elements of the methodology: self-efficacy to identify needs; project planning; reflection; and interacting with people in vulnerable situations.
-

VARIABLES, INDICATORS, AND MEASURES

These items focus on the identification, definition, and operationalization of the aspects to be observed, analyzed, or evaluated in research on service-learning and community engagement.

- What categories and indicators would be essential to consider when constructing an evaluation/research instrument?
 - How can we define better variables for evaluation? Are they applicable to different realities?
 - Identify indicators that can measure service-learning as a whole in different contexts.
 - Determine the variables and their measurement units (number of people, duration of beneficiaries).
 - How can we determine which variables will be measured?
 - How can we develop variables to better enable evaluation? Are they all applicable to different realities?
-

QUALITATIVE-QUANTITATIVE APPROACHES

These items focus not so much on instruments but on research approaches, whether through the objective measurement of variables (quantitative), the understanding of meanings and experiences (qualitative), or a combination of both approaches (mixed). The questions relate to the usefulness, limits, and complementarity of qualitative and quantitative approaches, and how to overcome traditional dichotomies between the two approaches and move toward integrative perspectives.

- How to overcome the quantitative-qualitative divide in the design of instruments for researching service-learning and community engagement projects?
- The need to design quantitative and qualitative instruments (that respond to a logic), with different approaches according to different groups, cultural situations, and regions to ensure the validity and reliability of the results.
- How to overcome the divide between qualitative and quantitative, which has already been questioned in academia?
- Beyond qualitative aspects, what quantitative instruments have been used to research service-learning and community engagement, or to evaluate projects?
- Is it mandatory to develop both a qualitative and a quantitative instrument, or is one sufficient?
- Rigorous structuring of qualitative research to facilitate transferability.
- The problem of locating or questioning the methodology (quantitative or qualitative).

SPECIFIC REALITIES

These items center on recognizing how the particular social, cultural, geographic, or institutional characteristics of contexts and focusing on certain key actors that influence the design of research instruments in service-learning and community engagement.

- What tools can we use to address issues of inequity in a service-learning or community engagement experience with children? (Particularly regarding the difference between boys/girls and adults).
- Develop tools and techniques to assess social impact.
- Tools to measure social responsibility in teachers.
- How can we measure student engagement? Is it necessary?
- Stakeholder perceptions can be measured qualitatively. Are there any tools that can be used as a basis?

- Are there tools that can account for how community mental health and arts education impact outcomes?
 - What tools or methods are relevant for measuring the impact of VAW-Extension?
-

METHODOLOGIES GUIDING INSTRUMENT DESIGN

These items focus not on instruments, but on the methodological approaches that guide research, taking into account the type of knowledge sought to be constructed. The questions focus on the most appropriate methodologies or those consistent with the principles of service-learning and community engagement.

- Can evaluative reflections function as suitable tools for service-learning and community engagement?
- Can the Philosophy for Children method be a tool for research in service-learning and community engagement?
- Is the involvement of project beneficiaries part of the methodological process of data collection?
- Can the Socratic Method be a tool for service-learning and community engagement?
- Can the Action Learning Method be a tool for service-learning and community engagement?

X. REPLICATION

No one study provides all the evidence, understanding, or knowledge that is needed to draw firm conclusions about service-learning or community engagement. Replication is a critical feature of scientific inquiry and research.

Only a handful of service-learning and community engagement studies have been replicated. Replicating high quality studies is a way to strengthen evidence and secure more conclusive findings about the strengths and limitations of service-learning and community engagement practices, outcomes, and approaches.

THE REPLICATION PROCESS

These items focus on how to replicate service-learning and community engagement research.

- Can we replicate a research study that has been validated in a particular cultural context in other contexts?
- Context: Replicate high-quality studies in different contexts to evaluate how service-learning works differently or similarly in different cultural settings.
- Can methodologies and instruments or tools be replicated, but should training be developed to diagnose the situation of each institution?
- What conditions are required to encourage/facilitate comparative studies? What role do these studies serve?

COLLABORATORS

Forum Participants

ARGENTINA (August 28, 2019)

Organized by the Latin American Center for Solidarity Service-Learning (CLAYSS)

Enrique Ochoa (CLAYSS) and **Maria Nieves Tapia (CLAYSS)**

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Organized by the University of Monterrey (UDEM)

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*Note: One participant in this forum requested anonymity and asked that their name not be included in this publication *

ARGENTINA (August 25, 2023)

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*Note: One participant in this forum requested anonymity and asked that their name not be included in this publication *

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Buenos Aires, Argentina

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Organized by the Latin American Center for Solidarity Service-Learning (CLAYSS) and the Barceló Foundation, Buenos Aires.

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